

Polarisation spectral synthesis for Type Ia supernova explosion models

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by

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“I have a friend who’s an artist and has sometimes taken a view which I don’t agree with very well. He’ll hold up a flower and say ‘look how beautiful it is’, and I’ll agree. Then he says ‘I as an artist can see how beautiful this is but you as a scientist take this all apart and it becomes a dull thing’, and I think that he’s kind of nutty. First of all, the beauty that he sees is available to other people and to me too, I believe. Although I may not be quite as refined aesthetically as he is...I can appreciate the beauty of a flower. At the same time, I see much more about the flower than he sees. I could imagine the cells in there, the complicated actions inside, which also have a beauty. I mean it’s not just beauty at this dimension, at one centimeter; there’s also beauty at smaller dimensions, the inner structure, also the processes. The fact that the colors in the flower evolved in order to attract insects to pollinate it is interesting; it means that insects can see the color. It adds a question: does this aesthetic sense also exist in the lower forms? Why is it aesthetic? All kinds of interesting questions which the science knowledge only adds to the excitement, the mystery and the awe of a flower. It only adds. I don’t understand how it subtracts.”

– Richard Phillips Feynman

To my wee little ladies

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Abstract

Despite their relevance across a broad range of astrophysical research topics, Type Ia supernova explosions are still poorly understood and answers to the questions of when, why and how these events are triggered remain unclear. In this respect, polarisation offers a unique opportunity to discriminate between the variety of possible scenarios. The observational evidence that Type Ia supernovae are associated with rather low polarisation signals (smaller than a few per cent) places strong constraints for models and calls for modest asphericities in the progenitor system and/or explosion mechanism.

The goal of this thesis is to assess the validity of contemporary Type Ia supernova explosion models by testing whether their predicted polarisation signatures can account for the small signals usually observed. To this end, we have implemented and tested an innovative Monte Carlo scheme in the radiative transfer code `ARTIS`. Compared to previous Monte Carlo approaches, this technique produces synthetic observables (light curves, flux and polarisation spectra) with a substantial reduction in the Monte Carlo noise and therefore in the required computing time. This improvement is particularly crucial for our study as we aim to extract very weak polarisation signals, comparable to those detected in Type Ia supernovae. We have also demonstrated the applicability of this method to other classes of supernovae via a preliminary study of the first spectropolarimetry observations of superluminous supernovae.

Using this scheme, we have calculated synthetic spectropolarimetry for three multi-dimensional explosion models recently proposed as promising candidates to explain Type Ia supernovae. Our findings highlight the power of spectropolarimetry in testing and discriminating between different scenarios. While all the three models predict light curves and flux spectra that are similar to each others and reproduce those observed in Type Ia supernovae comparably well, polarisation does provide a clear distinction. In particular, we find that one model is too strongly asymmetric and produces polarisation levels that are too high and clearly inconsistent with those detected for the bulk of Type Ia supernovae. Polarisation signals – and their time evolution – extracted for the remaining two models are instead in good agreement with the currently available spectropolarimetry data. Providing a powerful way to connect hydrodynamic explosion models to observed data, the study presented in this thesis is an important step towards a better understanding of Type Ia supernovae from a synthesis of theory and observations.

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Publications

A list of publications resulting from the work undertaken during my 3 years time as a Ph.D student.

Refereed Publications

1. **Bulla, M.**, Sim, S. A., Kromer, M., Seitenzahl, I. R., Fink, M., Ciaraldi-Schoolmann, F., Röpke, F. K., Hillebrandt, W., Pakmor, R., Ruiter, A. J., Taubenberger, S.
Predicting polarization signatures for double-detonation and delayed-detonation models of Type Ia supernovae
2016, MNRAS, **462**, 1039
2. **Bulla, M.**, Sim, S. A., Pakmor, R., Kromer, M., Taubenberger, S., Röpke, F. K., Hillebrandt, W., Seitenzahl, I. R.
Type Ia supernovae from violent mergers of carbon-oxygen white dwarfs: polarization signatures
2016, MNRAS, **455**, 1060
3. **Bulla, M.**, Sim, S. A., Kromer, M.
Polarization spectral synthesis for Type Ia supernova explosion models
2015, MNRAS, **450**, 967
4. Inserra, C., **Bulla, M.**, Sim, S. A., Smartt, S. J.
Spectropolarimetry of superluminous supernovae: insight into their geometry
2016, ApJ, **831**, 79

Chapter 1

Introduction

“E quindi uscimmo a riveder le stelle”

– *Dante Alighieri, Divine Comedy: Inferno XXXIV, 139*

1.1 Type Ia supernovae

Supernovae are among the most energetic phenomena in the Universe. Their brightness can outshine the galaxy in which they occur and reach a few billion times the luminosity of our Sun. Owing to their sudden appearance in the sky – and subsequent fading away – these transient events were originally dubbed “guest stars” or “novae” (abbreviation of the Latin *stellae novae*, new stars). Although the first recorded detection of what we now call a supernova presumably dates back to 185 AD (Zhao et al. 2006), it took more than 17 centuries to start understanding the nature of these spectacular events.

The term supernova (SN) was coined by Baade & Zwicky (1934) to distinguish the extremely bright event seen in the Andromeda galaxy in 1885 from the classical novae more commonly observed. Based on optical spectra around maximum light of fourteen SN events, Minkowski (1941) suggested a first distinction of SNe in two separate classes, depending on whether they showed (Type II SNe) or did not show (Type I SNe) hydrogen lines. Although this empirical classification has remained valid until the present days, the rapidly increasing rate of SNe discovered from the 1980s has led to the identification of new sub-classes. In particular, hydrogen-deficient Type I SNe have been divided in three sub-classes (e.g. Harkness & Wheeler 1990): events characterised by a strong silicon line around 6150 Å (see also Section 1.3.1) are named Type Ia SNe, while the remaining objects are classified as Type Ib or Type Ic SNe depending on whether they show helium lines in their spectra. Characteristic spectra at maximum light are shown for each class in Fig. 1.1 (for a detailed discussion of the spectral differences between various classes see Filippenko 1997b).

Today we know that SNe are associated with the explosion of dying stars and that distinct classes correspond to different progenitors and/or explosion mechanisms (Hoyle & Fowler 1960). As Type II and Ib/c SNe preferentially occur in late-type galaxies (e.g. Barbon et al. 1999; Cappellaro et al. 1999), they are thought to stem from the gravitational collapse of the cores of massive stars ($M \gtrsim 8M_{\odot}$, where M_{\odot} denotes the solar mass). In particular, the different types of core-collapse events are believed to form a sequence of increasing mass in the progenitor stars. While Type II SNe originate from stars that have retained their hydrogen envelope at the time of explosion (and therefore show evidence of hydrogen lines in their spectra), Type Ib/c SNe stem from more massive progenitors that have been stripped off their hydrogen (Ib) or hydrogen-plus-helium outer layers (Ic) prior to explosion. These mass loss episodes may be due to either stellar winds from massive single stars or mass-transfer in binary systems (see Smartt 2009, for a review).

In contrast, Type Ia SNe occur in both late- and early-type galaxies (e.g. Turatto

Figure 1.1: Spectral comparison of different types of SNe at different epochs relative to maximum light (from Turatto 2003).

et al. 1994; Barbon et al. 1999) and are associated with both young and old stellar populations (e.g. Sullivan et al. 2006; Brandt et al. 2010). Together with the absence of hydrogen and helium in their spectra, these facts suggest that a Type Ia SN originates from a star that is born with relatively low mass ($M \lesssim 8M_{\odot}$) and that, prior to explosion, has lost its hydrogen and helium envelopes to become a degenerate carbon-oxygen white dwarf. In the currently favoured scenario to explain Type Ia SNe, this carbon-oxygen white dwarf becomes unstable due to interaction with another star (likely in a binary system, see Section 1.4.1) and explodes as a result of a thermonuclear runaway (Hoyle & Fowler 1960, see also Section 1.4.2). The exact circumstances triggering the explosion, however, remain a mystery (see Section 1.4).

The goal of this thesis is to help establish the explosion mechanism(s) and progenitor channel(s) for Type Ia SNe by studying the geometry of these explosions. Since most of the work of this thesis deals with Type Ia SNe (hereafter referred to as SNe Ia), in the rest of this chapter we will focus on these events only. The astrophysical impact of SNe Ia is discussed in Section 1.2, while an overview of their main observational properties is given in Section 1.3. A review of the proposed progenitor scenarios and explosion mechanisms for SNe Ia is presented in Section 1.4, while different approaches to constraining explosion and progenitor channels are summarised in Section 1.5.

1.2 Astrophysical importance

The importance of SNe Ia in the astrophysical context is manifold. SNe Ia play a key role in the chemical enrichment of galaxies, injecting the interstellar medium with metal-rich material synthesised during the explosion. In particular, SNe Ia are known to be the dominant contributors to the iron production in the Universe and this makes them important tools to investigate galaxy formation and evolution (e.g. Tinsley 1979; Matteucci & Greggio 1986). In addition, SNe Ia – and in general SNe – are known to influence the star formation history of galaxies, with the shock wave originated from the explosion passing through nearby molecular clouds and either triggering or suppressing star formation (e.g. Opik 1953; Krebs & Hillebrandt 1983; Efstathiou 2000). Shock waves associated with SN remnants are also thought to be responsible for the acceleration of Galactic cosmic rays (see Bell 2013, for a recent review).

Perhaps the strongest impact of SNe Ia in the astrophysical field is their use in cosmology as distance indicators. The possibility of measuring cosmic distances using SNe has a long history and relies on the so-called “standard candle” approach. In the latter, the luminosity distance, d_L , of an object with known absolute luminosity L and magnitude M can be estimated as

$$d_L = \sqrt{\frac{L}{4\pi F}} = 10^{(m-M)/5+1} , \quad (1.1)$$

where F and m are the observed flux and magnitude, respectively. Early attempts of using SNe as distance indicators (Baade 1938; van den Bergh 1960; Kowal 1968) were limited by the relatively poor resolution of the data and – most importantly – by the assumption that different types of SNe were all characterised by similar intrinsic luminosities L . As more and more data were gathered in the 1980s, this latter property was proven to be wrong. Nevertheless, astronomers realised that SNe Ia appeared to form a rather homogeneous class (see e.g. Branch & Tammann 1992) and could potentially be employed as distance indicators. Their usage as standard candles was dramatically improved by the discovery that a tight correlation exists between absolute brightness and luminosity decline rate in SNe Ia (Phillips 1993; Hamuy et al. 1995; Phillips et al. 1999). Following earlier suggestions (Barbon et al. 1973; Pskovskii 1977), Phillips (1993) found that the observed absolute magnitude in the B -band, $M_{B,\max}$, was correlated with the magnitude decline in the B -band from peak to 15 d after, $\Delta m_{15}(B)$. That is, brighter SNe Ia declined more slowly than fainter ones. The observed scatter in the peak brightness distribution – which would argue against using SNe Ia as standard candles – could be reduced thanks to this width-luminosity relation (see left panels of Fig. 1.2), thus making SNe Ia “standardisable candles”.

Figure 1.2: *Left-hand panels:* absolute magnitude M vs. time relative to peak brightness for a sample of nearby SNe Ia, before (upper panel) and after (lower panel) correction for the width-luminosity relation (from Perlmutter 2003). *Right-hand panels:* distance modulus $m - M$ (see Eq. 1.1) as a function of redshift (upper panel) for SNe Ia (from Riess 2000). The bottom panel shows the difference between the data and a cosmological model assuming a matter-dominated Universe with no dark energy (cosmological parameters $\Omega_M = 0.3$ and $\Omega_\Lambda = 0$, dotted line). The best match is found for an accelerating Universe with cosmological parameters $\Omega_M = 0.3$ and $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$ (solid line).

Inspired by the findings of Phillips (1993), two different groups (the Supernova Cosmology Project, SCP, and the High-Z Supernova Search Team, HZT) developed more sophisticated techniques to calibrate the absolute brightness of SNe Ia. While the SCP team introduced a stretch factor s to adjust the time-scale axis (Perlmutter et al. 1997; Goldhaber et al. 2001), the HZT group parametrised the light curve shapes in different bands as a function of their peak brightness (Riess et al. 1996). Using these two different calibration approaches, both teams independently found that SNe Ia at high-redshift ($z \sim 0.5$) appeared fainter – and thus more distant – than expected from a matter-dominated Universe (see right panel of Fig. 1.2). This discovery provided compelling evidence for an accelerating expansion of the Universe driven by a (still) mysterious dark energy (Riess et al. 1998; Perlmutter et al. 1999) and was acknowledged with the Nobel Prize in Physics awarded to Saul Perlmutter, Adam Riess and Brian Schmidt in 2011.

1.3 Observables

As seen in Section 1.1, the classification of SNe Ia is purely empirical and based on the observations of spectra at maximum light. Characteristic properties are the absence of hydrogen and helium, and the presence of a deep absorption feature around $\sim 6150 \text{ \AA}$ produced by the Si II $\lambda\lambda 6347, 6371$ doublet, commonly referred to as Si II $\lambda 6355$. According to Li et al. (2011b), about 70% of the observed SNe Ia are spectroscopically very similar and belong to the class of so-called “Branch-normal” or “normal” SNe Ia (Branch et al. 1993). The rest of SNe Ia show peculiarities in both spectral feature strengths and luminosity and can be grouped in different sub-classes. We review the main characteristics of normal SNe Ia in Section 1.3.1, while summarise the properties of peculiar objects in Section 1.3.2.

1.3.1 Normal Type Ia supernovae

Fig. 1.3 shows optical spectra of a normal SN Ia from about two weeks before to about seven months after B -band maximum light. Spectra around peak brightness are dominated by features from neutral and singly-ionised intermediate-mass elements (IMEs, from magnesium to calcium). Beside the strong Si II $\lambda 6355$ line, characteristic features are the Ca II lines at $\lambda\lambda 3934, 3968$ (Ca H and K) and at $\lambda\lambda 8498, 8542, 8662$ (Ca II IR triplet). In addition, there is clear evidence of features associated with Si II $\lambda\lambda 5958, 5979$ (Si II $\lambda 5972$), S II $\lambda\lambda 5454, 5640$, Mg II $\lambda 4481$ and O I $\lambda\lambda 7772, 7774, 7775$ (O I $\lambda 7774$). Spectral lines at early epochs are characterised by pronounced P-Cygni profiles (see e.g. Si II $\lambda 6355$), consisting of a blue-shifted absorption and a redward emission feature. This profile shape is distinctive of expanding outflows where resonant line scattering occurs above a photosphere. Radiation scattered *into* the observer line-of-sight is responsible for the emission feature, while radiation travelling towards the observer and scattered *out-of-sight* by the line is responsible for the blue-shifted absorption component (as the absorbing material expands towards the observer). In particular, the absorption trough of the blue-shifted component is informative of the typical expansion velocities of SN Ia ejecta. Velocities of $\sim 12000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ are typically inferred at maximum light (see e.g. Thomas et al. 2004; Branch et al. 2006).

During the ejecta expansion, the density decreases with time and the line-forming region recedes deeper into the ejecta. As time passes, velocities associated with spectral features are observed to decrease (see e.g. the Si II $\lambda 6355$ line in Fig. 1.3), indicating that outer regions of the ejecta expand faster than inner ones (see also Section 3.2.2). Moreover, while features associated with IMEs gradually weaken with time, lines of

Figure 1.3: Spectral time evolution of the “Branch normal” Type Ia SN 1994D. Epochs are relative to B -band maximum light. Last two spectra ($t \gtrsim 150$ d) are of the similar Type Ia SN 1987L. Data are from Patat et al. (1996) and Filippenko (1997a), as reported by Filippenko (1997b).

iron-group-elements (IGEs, elements from scandium to zinc) start to dominate the spectrum from roughly two weeks past maximum. This points towards a composition of the ejecta core that is rich in heavy elements. Together with the high ejecta velocities, the wealth of IGE lines in the ultraviolet (UV) and bluer optical regions of the spectra leads to strong line blending and flux suppression at short wavelengths. This effect is commonly referred to as “line blanketing”. From about one month after maximum, the ejecta enters the so-called nebular phase. Owing to the expansion of the ejecta, densities at these late times are sufficiently low that only forbidden transitions from IGEs (e.g. [Fe II], [Fe III] and [Co III]) are observed in the spectra as strong emission lines.

Normal SNe Ia are not only spectroscopically, but also photometrically similar (see Section 1.2). Light curves of normal SNe Ia rise to maximum light in about 18–20 days (e.g. Riess et al. 1999; Conley et al. 2006; Hayden et al. 2010; Firth et al. 2015), after which they show a first steep decline of about 3 magnitudes in 30 d, followed by

Figure 1.4: Absolute magnitude in the B -band, $M_{B,\max}$, as a function of the decline rate $\Delta m_{15}(B)$ for a sample of SNe Ia (figure from Hillebrandt et al. 2013). Normal SNe Ia are shown in grey, while peculiar “91bg-like”, “02cx-like” and “91T-like” objects in red, green and lightblue, respectively. The width-luminosity relation from Phillips et al. (1999) is shown with a black solid line.

a slower (roughly one magnitude per month) and exponential decline (see bottom-left panel of Fig. 1.2). At maximum light, they reach an absolute magnitude in the B -band of $M_{B,\max} \sim -19.3$ (Hamuy et al. 1996). Despite the overall homogeneity of normal SNe Ia, however, some scatter around the latter value is seen in the peak brightness. This is shown in Fig. 1.4. As mentioned in Section 1.2, the scatter in the peak brightness is correlated with the decline rate after maximum light, in the sense that dimmer SNe Ia are found to decline faster (Phillips 1993). Typical values for the decline rate $\Delta m_{15}(B)$ in normal SNe Ia span the range between ~ 0.8 and 1.6 mag.

The analysis of SN Ia light curves provides insight in the energetic of these explosions. As first suggested by Truran et al. (1967) and Colgate & McKee (1969), SN Ia light curves are powered by the decay of the radioactive ^{56}Ni . The latter is produced during the thermonuclear explosion and decays (with half-life time of 6.1 d) via electron-capture to the radioactive ^{56}Co . In turn, the unstable ^{56}Co decays (half-life time of 77.2 d) to the stable ^{56}Fe via electron-capture or positron emission. A relation between the amount of ^{56}Ni and the brightness of a SN Ia has been pointed out

by Arnett (1982). Specifically, the so-called Arnett’s rule states that the bolometric luminosity of a SN Ia at maximum light equals the instantaneous energy deposition of ^{56}Ni in the expanding ejecta (but see also Pinto & Eastman 2000a for deviations from this law). Using Arnett’s rule, previous studies have estimated the amount of ^{56}Ni synthesised in normal SNe Ia to range between ~ 0.3 and $0.9 M_{\odot}$, with an average value of $\sim 0.6 M_{\odot}$ (see e.g. Stritzinger et al. 2006). Around maximum light, the amount of energy deposited in the ejecta by the ^{56}Co decay is comparable to that deposited by the ^{56}Ni decay (Arnett 1982). Later on, the $^{56}\text{Co} \rightarrow ^{56}\text{Fe}$ decay becomes the dominant channel and eventually regulates the decline rate of the light curve. This is consistent with the exponential behaviour observed from one month post-maximum and with the detection of forbidden iron and cobalt emission lines in nebular spectra (see above). To a first approximation, the picture presented here provides an explanation for the width-luminosity relation of Phillips (1993) in terms of the ^{56}Ni produced in the explosion. Among all the normal SNe Ia, events synthesising more ^{56}Ni are typically brighter, as the amount of energy deposited in the ejecta is larger, and decline more slowly, as the larger amount of IGEs synthesised results into higher opacities to the escaping radiation.

1.3.2 Peculiar Type Ia supernovae

Thanks to the increasing rate of SNe Ia discovered by recent transient surveys (e.g. Li et al. 2011b), spectroscopically peculiar events have started to emerge in addition to the normal ones. These peculiar objects appear to form distinct sub-classes from the normal SNe Ia, the most important and widely-studied being the so-called “91bg-like”, “02cx-like” and “91T-like” classes (see below). According to Li et al. (2011b), the contributions of these three classes to the total SNe Ia rate is of about 15, 5 and 9%, respectively. Their photometric and spectroscopic peculiarities are shown in Fig. 1.4 and Fig. 1.5, respectively, and discussed in the following.

The spectroscopically peculiar SN 1991bg is the prototype of a class of objects known as “91bg-like” SNe Ia (e.g. Filippenko et al. 1992a; Leibundgut et al. 1993). These objects are roughly 2 mag fainter than the bulk of normal SNe Ia ($M_{\text{B,max}} \sim -17$ mag) and are characterised by rather fast decline rates ($\Delta m_{15}(B) \sim 1.9$ mag). As clearly shown in Fig. 1.4, these sub-luminous SNe Ia do not follow the width-luminosity relation, with typical luminosities roughly one magnitude lower than normal events with similar decline rate. From their low luminosities, values of $0.1 M_{\odot}$ are generally inferred for the ^{56}Ni mass using the Arnett’s rule (e.g. Mazzali et al. 1997). Spectroscopic peculiarities of “91bg-like” objects include a characteristic absorption feature

Figure 1.5: Spectroscopic diversity between SN Ia events. Spectra around maximum for the peculiar SN 2009dc (black, Taubenberger et al. 2011), SN 1991T (pink, Ruiz-Lapuente et al. 1992), SN 2005hk (“02cx-like” object, red, Phillips et al. 2007) and SN 1991bg (blue, Turatto et al. 1996) are compared with the spectrum of a normal SN Ia (grey, Patat et al. 1996) at similar epoch. Identifications of some features with spectral transitions are shown. Flux spectra are reported in a logarithmic scale and have been arbitrarily shifted for illustrative purposes.

around 4000 Å due to Ti II (which is absent in normal events), a strong O I $\lambda 7774$ line and a relatively small ratio of the depth of Si II $\lambda 6355$ to Si II $\lambda 5792$ (see Fig. 1.5). Spectra of these objects are also redder than those of normal SNe Ia at comparable epochs.

A distinct class of sub-luminous events has SN 2002cx as its prototype (Li et al. 2003). In the literature, these objects are typically referred to as “02cx-like” SNe Ia or as Type Iax SNe (Foley et al. 2013). They do not follow the Phillips relation and their estimated ^{56}Ni mass is roughly between 10^{-3} and $0.3 M_{\odot}$ (e.g. Li et al. 2003; Foley et al. 2013). Spectral features around maximum light are associated with low velocities (a factor of \sim two smaller than those seen in normal SNe Ia), indicating slow expansion velocities of the ejecta. In addition, doubly-ionised Fe III features are observed. At variance with normal SNe Ia, spectra of these objects at about one year

after explosion are dominated by narrow lines of permitted Fe II transitions (e.g. Jha et al. 2006), indicating that their ejecta are not yet transparent at these very late epochs.

Taking their name from the peculiar SN 1991T event (e.g. Filippenko et al. 1992b; Phillips et al. 1992; Jeffery et al. 1992), “91T-like” objects are slightly brighter (~ 0.3 mag) than normal SNe Ia and do not follow the width-luminosity relation. At maximum light, spectra of these objects are dominated by doubly-ionised Fe III features as in the “02cx-like” objects (and not by Si II and Ca II lines as in normal events). A few months later, however, their spectra resemble those of normal SNe Ia. More recently, other objects even more luminous than SN 1991T have been found, among which are SN 2003fg and SN 2009dc (see e.g. Howell et al. 2006; Taubenberger et al. 2011). These SNe are characterised by luminosities at least twice as large as those in normal events, rise times larger than ~ 23 d, slow ejecta and the presence of peculiarly strong C II lines in the spectra.

1.4 Theoretical understanding

In this section, we review our current understanding about the progenitor channel(s) and explosion scenario(s) of SNe Ia. We will focus on *normal* SNe Ia, as these objects are the main topic of this thesis, but also comment on peculiar SNe Ia where appropriate.

1.4.1 Progenitor scenarios

As anticipated in Section 1.1, SNe Ia are believed to stem from thermonuclear explosion (see Section 1.4.2) of carbon-oxygen (CO) white dwarfs (WDs). This idea is supported by different observational arguments, including their occurrence in both old and young stellar populations and the absence of hydrogen and helium lines in their spectra. CO WDs are inherently stable objects, as the Fermi pressure of degenerate electrons is able to sustain them against the gravitational collapse. Interaction with another object is therefore a necessary condition to break their stability and lead to a thermonuclear runaway.

Although head-on collisions of WDs have been proposed as a possible explanation for triggering a thermonuclear explosion (e.g. Rosswog et al. 2009; Raskin et al. 2009), these events appear to be too rare to account for the bulk of SNe Ia (but see also Kushnir et al. 2013, for the head-on collision of WDs in triple systems). Hence, it seems likely that the bulk of SNe Ia arises from CO WDs in interacting binary systems. Traditionally, speculations about the nature of the companion star have led to a distinction between two separate progenitor scenarios: the single degenerate (SD; Whelan & Iben 1973) and the double degenerate (DD; Webbink 1984; Iben & Tutukov 1984)

scenario depending on whether the companion is a non-degenerate star or another WD, respectively.

In SD scenarios, a main-sequence (MS) or giant-like star is thought to transfer hydrogen-rich (or possibly helium-rich) material onto a CO WD via stable Roche-lobe overflow. Provided that the mass accretion rate is within a specific range of values (see below), stable hydrogen- or helium-burning can occur on the surface of the WD and the latter can grow in both mass and density. Critical conditions (see Section 1.4.2) eventually leading to a thermonuclear explosion are reached when the central densities of the WD are sufficiently high for carbon to start burning (see Section 1.4.2). In particular, this occurs when the WD mass approaches the so-called Chandrasekhar limit (M_{ch}). Historically, the existence of a critical mass made the SD M_{ch} channel a very appealing candidate to explain the homogeneity observed in SN Ia events. However, both theoretical and observational shortcomings have challenged this scenario (see Maoz et al. 2014, for a recent review). In particular, stable hydrogen-burning is known to occur only within a narrow range of accretion rates, with higher (lower) rates leading to a common-envelope formation (nova explosion) and preventing the WD from approaching the M_{ch} limit (e.g. Nomoto et al. 2007). As a result, binary population synthesis calculations suggest that it might be difficult for this scenario to be the main contributor of normal SNe Ia as the predicted rates are roughly one order of magnitude smaller than those observed (see e.g. Ruiter et al. 2009).

In the DD scenario, two CO WDs with total mass larger than M_{ch} are believed to coalesce due to gravitational wave emission. This scenario has received considerable attention in the past few years as the rates predicted for these mergers might be high enough to explain the bulk of normal SNe Ia (e.g. Ruiter et al. 2009, 2013; Graur & Maoz 2013). In addition, the merger of two CO WDs would naturally explain the absence of hydrogen lines in SN Ia spectra. Historically, the main criticism to the DD scenario is related to the robustness and likelihood of this channel in producing thermonuclear explosions. In particular, these mergers are thought to lead to the disruption of the lighter WD and to the formation of an accretion disc around the more massive WD. Because of the high accretion rates from the disc, carbon-burning is triggered in the outer layers of the WD (and not at the centre as in the SD M_{ch} scenario) and causes the transformation of the CO WD into an oxygen-neon-magnesium WD. When approaching the M_{ch} limit, this WD is predicted to collapse to a neutron star rather than producing a thermonuclear explosion (Saio & Nomoto 1985; Nomoto & Iben Jr 1985). As we will discuss in Section 1.4.3, the disruption of the lighter WD and the formation of a disc might be avoided if the two WDs have similar masses (e.g. Pakmor et al. 2010, 2011, 2012; Moll et al. 2014). In this picture, a “violent merger” of the two stars leads to density and temperature conditions that might be sufficient to trigger a thermonuclear

explosion of the heavier WD even before approaching the M_{ch} limit.

Another progenitor channel in which the explosion of the WD might occur before reaching the M_{ch} limit is the so-called “double-detonation” (sub- M_{ch}) scenario (see Section 1.4.3). In this scenario, a CO WD accretes material from an helium-rich companion star and – because of the relatively low accretion rates – is able to accumulate (rather than burning) an helium layer on its surface. A detonation of this helium surface layer might occur under critical conditions (Section 1.4.3) and the corresponding shock wave trigger a second detonation in the underlying CO core. Depending on whether the donor star is an helium-rich normal star or a helium WD, this scenario can fit in the class of either SD or DD progenitor channels. The double-detonation scenario has been extensively studied in the 1990s (see e.g. Woosley & Weaver 1994; Livne & Arnett 1995), but regained popularity only recently as a promising channel to explain SNe Ia. This is in part (but not only) due to the indication from binary population synthesis that this scenario might provide an important contribution to the SN Ia population (e.g. Ruiter et al. 2011). Whether or not this scenario can reproduce observed flux and spectra of normal SNe Ia, however, is still questionable (see Section 1.4.3).

1.4.2 Thermonuclear explosions

Although there is a general consensus that SNe Ia result from thermonuclear runaways in CO WDs, the explosion mechanism is still debated. As discussed in Section 1.3, SNe Ia are powered by the ^{56}Ni radioactive decay and their spectra show signatures of IMEs (e.g. silicon and calcium) and IGEs (e.g. iron). This indicates that some nuclear processing of the CO material must occur. At sufficiently high density and temperatures (see below), carbon starts burning to higher-mass elements. Because the equation of state for electron degenerate matter depends only weakly on the temperature, the energy production does not cause an expansion and then cooling of the WD. This, together with the high conductivity of the electron-degenerate material and with the strong temperature dependence of the nuclear reactions, leads to a thermonuclear runaway that fully disrupts the WD (Hoyle & Fowler 1960; Arnett 1969; Woosley & Weaver 1986).

To a first approximation, the nucleosynthesis of SNe Ia is controlled by the density of the degenerate material inside the WD. This is shown in Fig. 1.6. At high densities ($\rho \gtrsim 10^8 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$), complete burning to nuclear statistical equilibrium (NSE) takes place, leading to the production of IGEs (mainly ^{56}Ni). Regions at lower densities ($10^6 \lesssim \rho \lesssim 10^8 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$) experience incomplete burning and the production of IMEs (e.g. magnesium, silicon, sulphur and calcium). At even lower densities, carbon is

Figure 1.6: Temperatures and densities at different mass coordinates for a one-dimensional SN Ia model (Badenes et al. 2005, figure from Bravo & Martínez-Pinedo 2012). Different density and temperature conditions in the WD correspond to different burning regimes (see text for an explanation).

burned to oxygen, while below $\sim 10^5 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ nuclear burning ceases.

The physics of the ignition process is largely unknown. In particular, the *number* and *location* of the ignition spatial regions are still debated. In hydrodynamic explosion models, the outcomes depend sensitively on these two parameters, and relatively different results are found depending on whether the burning front is ignited at the centre of the WD or off-centred, and in one or multiple sparks (see e.g. Woosley et al. 2004; Röpke et al. 2007a; Sim et al. 2007). Specific hydrodynamic codes are required to overcome the large range of spatial and time scales involved in the explosion (see Hillebrandt et al. 2013 for a review). In particular, very few studies have modelled the pre-explosion phase to constraint the exact ignition configuration, and the results are controversial. Using simple analytical models, Garcia-Senz & Woosley (1995) and Woosley et al. (2004) favoured a multiple-spark ignition at 150–200 km around the centre of the WD, followed by further ignitions at smaller radii. In contrast, more recent studies (Zingale et al. 2009, 2011; Nonaka et al. 2012) have carried out detailed hydrodynamic calculations of the pre-explosion convective phase in the SD M_{ch} scenario

(see Section 1.4.3) and found that an off-centred ignition in one single spot at ~ 50 km from the centre of the WD is more likely.

Because of this controversy, in modern explosion simulations the ignition is typically inserted artificially when some physically motivated condition has been reached. In the case of a detonation ignition (see below), the burning front is commonly initiated when the density and temperature in one or more spatial regions of the ejecta exceed some critical values ρ_{crit} and T_{crit} (e.g. Jordan et al. 2008; Guillochon et al. 2010; Pakmor et al. 2011). For instance, critical conditions for all the explosion models presented in Chapter 5 of this work are selected according to criteria from Seitenzahl et al. (2009, see also Section 1.4.3).

Once ignited, the combustion front can propagate through the ejecta in two different ways: as a subsonic *deflagration* flame or as a supersonic *detonation* wave. While the deflagration corresponds to a flame mediated by thermal conduction, the detonation propagation is driven by a shock wave. Among the different approaches to model the propagation of deflagration and detonation fronts, one widely-used technique has been first introduced by Reinecke et al. (1999, “level-set” technique). In this approach – implemented in all the hydrodynamic simulations presented in Chapter 5 – the combustion front is modelled as a mathematical discontinuity and its structure is not resolved. This approximation is justified by the fact that the typical scales of the combustion front (1 – 10 mm), are significantly smaller than the size of the WD (~ 2000 km). Depending on the specific propagation mode, this discontinuity moves through the ejecta with different velocities and transforms unburned fuel material into nuclear ash.

1.4.3 Explosion scenarios

Over the past few decades, the SN community has witnessed a long-standing debate about the nature of the progenitor system of SNe Ia (see Section 1.4.1). From the explosion mechanism perspective, however, the crucial question is whether the ignition of the CO WD is triggered when approaching the M_{ch} limit or at a different stage. *Chandrasekhar-mass models* and *non-Chandrasekhar-mass models* have been proposed in the context of both SD and DD progenitor channel (see Fig. 1.7), and are reviewed in the following.

Chandrasekhar-mass models

In M_{ch} models, a CO WD accretes material from a companion star and reaches critical conditions for explosion when approaching the M_{ch} limit. In principle, the com-

	M_{ch}	Non- M_{ch}
SD	MS / giant-like star deflag. / delayed det.	He star double detonation
DD	CO WD deflag. / delayed det.	CO WD detonation He WD double detonation

Figure 1.7: Nature of the companion star (black) and explosion mechanisms (grey) for different SN Ia scenarios.

panion can be either a CO WD (DD system) or a non-degenerate star (SD system). In the former case, however, the accretion rate may be too high for stable accretion to the M_{ch} limit and the outcome of this scenario may be a core-collapse explosion of an oxygen-neon-magnesium WD rather than a thermonuclear explosion of a CO WD (see also Section 1.4.1). Therefore, the M_{ch} model has been most widely discussed in the context of the SD scenario.

A *pure detonation* model of a M_{ch} WD was first investigated by Arnett (1969). In this model, a detonation is ignited at central densities of $2 \times 10^9 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$. As the detonation wave propagates at supersonic velocities, the fuel material ahead of the shock can not expand and is thus burned at the high initial densities of the M_{ch} WD. Under these conditions, carbon burning proceeds to NSE throughout most of the star and thus results into ejecta mainly composed by IGEs (see Section 1.4.2). Despite producing enough energy to power a SN Ia explosion, the pure detonation model is therefore ruled out as it fails to synthesise the IMEs observed in SN Ia spectra.

A *pure deflagration* model offers a natural solution to the lack of IMEs in the ejecta. Owing to the subsonic velocity of the deflagration flame, the unburned fuel material is able to expand ahead of the combustion front. As a consequence, nuclear burning occurs at lower densities and leads to the production of both IGE and IME material. A different problem, however, was originally thought to affect the pure deflagration model: the deflagration flame speed is not sufficiently large and hence the corresponding kinetic energy is not able to unbind the WD. To overcome this limitation, parametrised flame speeds were implemented in the first one-dimensional deflagration models and specific values were selected to reproduce light curves and spectra of SNe Ia. Among these, the still widely-used W7 model of Nomoto et al. (1984) is beyond doubt the most notable example (see also Section 4.4). More recent multi-dimensional explosion models have shown that turbulent motions – not captured in the early one-dimensional models

– play a key role in the propagation of the deflagration wave. Following the generation of hot and low-density ashes below the cold and dense fuel, Rayleigh-Taylor buoyancy instabilities are created in the ejecta. The deflagration flame is accelerated by strong turbulent eddies and, as a result, can reach velocities that are large enough to unbind the WD (Reinecke et al. 2002; Gamezo et al. 2003; Röpke & Hillebrandt 2005). Nevertheless, predictions from multi-dimensional deflagration models are in conflict with properties observed in normal SNe Ia: the amount of ^{56}Ni ($\lesssim 0.4 M_{\odot}$, Röpke et al. 2006) is too low and the ejecta are too strongly mixed to explain the stratification typically observed in normal SNe Ia (Röpke et al. 2007a). In contrast, light curves and spectra derived for this class of models are found to be in good agreement with those observed for the peculiar Type Iax SN events (Kromer et al. 2013, 2015).

An interplay of the pure deflagration and pure detonation models, the so-called *delayed-detonation* model, holds promises for providing a good match to data. Initially, a carbon deflagration is ignited near the centre of the WD but delayed-detonation models posit that during the propagation of the deflagration flame a detonation occurs. At variance with the pure detonation model, here the detonation takes place in a pre-expanded fuel at lower densities and thus production of the IMEs can be achieved. Moreover, the limitations encountered in the pure deflagration model (see above) are easily resolved in the context of a delayed-detonation model. First, the detonation wave produces an increase in the nuclear burning compared to the deflagration flame, thus leading to a larger production of ^{56}Ni in the ejecta. Secondly, the detonation burns out inhomogeneities previously created by the deflagration flame and therefore the ejecta are characterised by a clear stratification: IGEs dominates the inner part of the ejecta, IMEs from the detonation occupy the intermediate regions and some carbon and oxygen are left unburned in the outer layers. In particular, the detonation wave propagates in material with increasingly lower density and thus produces a strong stratification in its products. The exact conditions triggering a detonation, however, are not fully understood and different scenarios have been proposed.

In one class of models, a deflagration-to-detonation transition (DDT) is assumed to occur spontaneously during the propagation of the deflagration flame. In parametrised one-dimensional DDT models (e.g. Höflich et al. 1995), the critical density at which this transition occurs was taken as a free parameter and chosen to be around $1 \times 10^7 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$. Taking into account the effect of turbulent motions in the deflagration regime, more recent studies (e.g. Röpke 2007; Woosley 2007; Woosley et al. 2009; Ciaraldi-Schoolmann et al. 2013) have shown that large turbulent velocity fluctuations ($\gtrsim 5 \times 10^7 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$, see Fig. 1.8) can interact with the deflagration flame and might indeed cause a DDT at densities in the range of $0.5\text{--}1.5 \times 10^7 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$. The spa-

Figure 1.8: A DDT from the explosion model of Röpke (2007). The deflagration flame is shown in blue, while red points indicate region where turbulent velocity fluctuations are larger than $\sim 5 \times 10^7 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ (see color bar) and are believed to trigger a DDT.

tial regions at which the transition takes place, however, are too small to be resolved by current hydrodynamic simulations, and thus the DDT needs to be regarded as a (physically well motivated) assumption. Light curves and spectra predicted for recent one-dimensional (Blondin et al. 2013, 2015) and multi-dimensional (Kasen et al. 2009; Röpke et al. 2012; Seitzzahl et al. 2013; Sim et al. 2013) DDT explosion models show a good agreement with data (see left panels of Fig. 1.9). In particular, in multi-dimensional explosion models the deflagration flame is initiated via the ignition of one or multiple sparks near the WD centre, while the subsequent detonation(s) are artificially inserted in regions with sufficiently strong turbulent velocities (e.g. Seitzzahl et al. 2009; Ciaraldi-Schoolmann et al. 2013). Strong deflagrations – corresponding to many ignition sparks – cause a large pre-expansion of the ejecta and then a DDT occurring at relatively low densities. This leads to a small amounts of synthesised ^{56}Ni and to relatively faint SNe Ia. In contrast, weaker deflagrations result into brighter SNe Ia. Whether or not the brightness dispersion in different sequences of DDT models can reproduce the width-luminosity relation (see Section 1.2) is unclear (Kasen et al. 2009; Sim et al. 2013).

Another possible mechanism to produce a delayed detonation has been first suggested by Plewa et al. (2004). In this scenario, referred to as gravitationally confined detonation (GCD), a deflagration is ignited in a single spark near the centre and propagates towards the WD surface. Upon reaching the surface, the flame is confined by the WD gravity and accelerates fuel material laterally. As a consequence, two fuel fronts

sweep around the WD surface and converge at the opposite side. At this point, strong compression of the fuel material is thought to trigger a detonation that fully disrupts the WD. Following Plewa et al. (2004), different incarnations of the GCD scenario have been recently carried out (e.g. Plewa 2007; Jordan et al. 2008; Seitzzahl et al. 2016). Comparatively large differences are found in the predictions of these models and no agreement has yet been reached as to whether this scenario can account for the observed properties of normal SNe Ia.

Non-Chandrasekhar-mass models

Strong stratification of the ejecta (in good agreement with data, see Section 1.5) is obtained if the detonation shock wave propagates through increasingly less dense regions (see above). In addition, IME production requires incomplete burning and thus sufficiently low densities in the fuel material. In the SD M_{ch} scenario, this is only possible by invoking a pre-expansion of the ejecta via a deflagration phase since a pure detonation would burn the WD almost entirely to IGEs. In contrast, densities in sub- M_{ch} WDs are typically lower compared to M_{ch} WDs and thus a pure detonation might be a viable mechanism there. This was investigated by Sim et al. (2010), who found that bare CO WDs with masses between 0.97 and 1.15 M_{\odot} are able to produce IMEs and a clear stratification in the ejecta (see their fig. 1), with ^{56}Ni in the right range observed for SNe Ia (0.3–0.8 M_{\odot} , cf with Section 1.3.1). In particular, the typical observed value, 0.6 M_{\odot} , is synthesised for a WD with $\sim 1.1 M_{\odot}$. A good match with data is also found in terms of light curves and spectra. The crucial question is then how a detonation can be triggered in a otherwise-stable 1.1 M_{\odot} WD. In the following, we discuss two possibilities: a double-detonation and a violent merger scenario.

In the *double-detonation* scenario, the explosion is triggered by the detonation of a helium surface layer that has been accreted from a non-degenerate (SD) or degenerate (DD) helium-rich companion star (see Section 1.4.1). The shock wave from this detonation then triggers a second detonation in the core. In early double-detonation models, helium masses of about 0.1–0.2 M_{\odot} were thought to be necessary to ignite a detonation. As a consequence, large amounts of ^{56}Ni were synthesised in the outer ejecta, in clear disagreement with observations (e.g. Höflich & Khokhlov 1996; Nugent et al. 1997; Woosley & Kasen 2011). More recent studies (Bildsten et al. 2007; Shen & Bildsten 2009) have suggested that lower masses ($\sim 3 \times 10^{-3} - 0.1 M_{\odot}$ for WD masses larger than 0.8 M_{\odot}) may be sufficient to trigger a detonation in the helium layer. In particular – compared to lower mass WDs – more massive WDs accrete helium at a higher rate and thus require lower shell masses for triggering helium burning. Provided that an helium detonation occurs, Fink et al. (2007) demonstrated that a secondary detonation

in the underlying CO core seems inevitable. Guided by this, Fink et al. (2010) explored six different realisations with CO core masses increasing from 0.81 to 1.38 M_{\odot} and helium shell masses selected to decrease from 0.13 to $3.5 \times 10^{-3} M_{\odot}$ to meet minimum conditions from Bildsten et al. (2007, see above). Light curves and spectra predicted by this set of models (Kromer et al. 2010) reproduce SN Ia observations reasonably well and – as expected from Sim et al. (2010) – the best match is found for a CO core of $\sim 1.1 M_{\odot}$ (see also Section 5.1). Compared to earlier double-detonation models, a negligible amount of ^{56}Ni is produced in the shell ($\lesssim 1.7 \times 10^{-3} M_{\odot}$). In contrast, however, a significant mass of IGEs such as chromium and titanium are synthesised in the shell. Opacity from these elements produce strong line blanketing and lead to spectra that are much redder than observed. As suggested by an exploratory model of Kromer et al. (2010), this issue might be resolved by changing the initial composition of the helium shell, e.g. by pollution with some ($\sim 30\%$) carbon and oxygen material that can limit burning to NSE. Unfortunately, no self-consistent hydrodynamical model has yet been performed to test this possibility.

The *violent merger* scenario is another possible channel for detonating a sub- M_{ch} WD. As mentioned in Section 1.4.1, the merger of two CO WDs with nearly equal masses can be strong enough to avoid the disruption of the lighter star and to create conditions for a detonation of the more massive one. This scenario was first investigated by Pakmor et al. (2010) for two 0.9 M_{\odot} CO WDs. Following criteria from Seitenzahl et al. (2009), a detonation is inserted when reaching temperatures and densities of about 3×10^9 K and 4×10^6 g cm $^{-3}$, respectively. Because of the rather low densities of the exploding sub- M_{ch} WD, burning to NSE is limited to few regions of the ejecta and only 0.1 M_{\odot} of ^{56}Ni are synthesised during the explosion. Predicted light curves are therefore fainter than those observed in normal SNe Ia and more consistent with light curves of peculiar “91bg-like” events (although the time evolution appear to be too slow). Guided by the findings of Sim et al. (2010), a second simulation was carried out by Pakmor et al. (2012) in which the primary mass was changed to 1.1 M_{\odot} . Not too surprisingly, this explosion configuration yields 0.64 M_{\odot} of ^{56}Ni from the primary star. In contrast, the secondary star is characterised by relatively low densities and mostly burns to oxygen (see Section 5.1). Because of the large asymmetries in the ejecta, light curves and spectra predicted by this model show a strong viewing-angle dependence. Observables are typically in good agreement with data of normal SNe Ia (see right panels of Fig. 1.9), although the light curve evolution is again too slow compared to observations (e.g. rise time of about 21 d, cf with Section 1.3.1). In a recent study, Pakmor et al. (2013) have suggested a double-detonation mechanism in the context of a violent merger as a promising channel to explain SNe Ia. Compared to the double-detonation described above, the helium material accreted onto the 1.1 M_{\odot} WD

is ignited dynamically during the violent merger. Therefore, a lower helium shell mass (0.01 instead of 0.055 M_{\odot} , cf with Fink et al. 2010) is required to trigger a detonation and burning products from the shell may not strongly affect light curves and spectra (see above). Although promising, this possibility has to be tested with detailed radiative transfer calculations.

1.5 Constraining explosion and progenitor scenarios

In the previous section, we have seen that different explosion mechanisms and progenitor scenarios have been suggested to explain SNe Ia. Different approaches have been adopted in the past to try to discriminate between explosion mechanisms/progenitor channels.

From the observational side, much effort has been devoted to searching for specific signatures that would help differentiating between SD and DD scenarios. Examples include (but are not limited to, see the recent review of Maoz et al. 2014) searching for signatures of the surviving non-degenerate companion star in SN remnants (e.g. Ruiz-Lapuente et al. 2004; Kerzendorf et al. 2009); looking for signatures of the interaction between the SN ejecta and either the companion star (e.g Bloom et al. 2012; Cao et al. 2015) or some circumstellar material (e.g. Patat et al. 2007); searching for the progenitor system in pre-explosion images (e.g. Li et al. 2011a); comparing observed SN Ia rates and delay-time-distributions (i.e. the times from the progenitor formation to the SN explosion, see e.g. Maoz et al. 2010) with those predicted by binary population synthesis for different progenitor scenarios (Hachisu et al. 2008; Mennekens et al. 2010; Ruiter et al. 2011). Despite much effort, no consensus has been reached as some observational evidences point towards DD channels while others favour SD scenarios (Maoz et al. 2014).

Another approach is that of using SN Ia observed spectra to infer properties of the explosion models. This is, for instance, the principle behind the so-called abundance tomography (Stehle et al. 2005), in which optimal fitting of observed spectral time series is performed and used to extract the element composition of the ejecta in velocity space. This approach has been useful to highlight the strong stratification of SN Ia ejecta (see Section 1.3) and to compare the latter to the element distributions predicted by hydrodynamic explosion models. Abundance tomography, however, is only one-dimensional and it is usually not obvious how to quantify the connection between the inferred abundance stratification and the often complex multi-dimensional structures predicted in explosion models.

Figure 1.9: Comparison between spectra observed for SN 2011fe (red) and those predicted by two different explosion models (Röpke et al. 2012): one DDT model from Seitenzahl et al. (2013, left panels) and the violent merger model of Pakmor et al. (2012, right panels). Synthetic angle-averaged spectra are shown in black, while angle-resolved spectra in grey. Simulated spectra are shown (from top to bottom) at 6.4, 12.4, 18.6 and 26.9 d post-explosion, while observed spectra of SN 2011fe are reported at similar epochs.

Modelling the explosions is another means to test different scenarios and understand how/whether they can be observationally distinguished from each other. In this “forward-modelling” approach, explosion models are tested by predicting synthetic observables (e.g. light curves and spectra) via radiative transfer simulations and comparing them with data. Based on light curves and spectra only, however, discrimination between different models remains challenging. For instance, this was recently pointed out in the work by Röpke et al. (2012), where predictions from a DDT (Seitenzahl et al. 2013) and a violent merger (Pakmor et al. 2012) model were compared to observations of the very nearby and well-studied Type Ia SN 2011fe. As shown in Fig. 1.9, both models reproduce spectra of SN 2011fe comparably well. It is hard, however, to favour one model over the other. In the next chapter we will see how polarisation can be used as an opportunity to discriminate between different explosion scenarios.

Chapter 2

Polarisation in Type Ia supernovae

*“If I have seen further, it is by standing on the shoulders of giants”
– Isaac Newton*

Brightness and colour are the most familiar properties of light as these can be perceived with our own naked eyes. There exists, however, a third property: polarisation. Despite being impossible to observe without special filters, polarisation is as important as brightness and colour since it brings information about the orientation in which the electric field of light is oscillating. Most astrophysical sources are known to be incoherent and to emit unpolarised light, with the electric field orientation randomly changing with time. Polarisation, however, can be acquired through several mechanisms. These include scattering by either charged particles (Thomson or Compton scattering), atoms and molecules (Rayleigh scattering) or small dust grains (Mie scattering), resonant line scattering, selective absorption by aligned grains and strong magnetic fields. Therefore, polarisation is a powerful tool in studying astrophysical events as it carries the imprint of the different physical interaction(s) undertaken by the radiation on its way from the source to the observer. After defining some relevant quantities, in this chapter we discuss how polarimetry can be used to gain better insights into the nature of SN Ia explosions.

2.1 General principles of polarisation

Light is a transverse wave, meaning that its electromagnetic components oscillate in a plane perpendicular to the direction of propagation. Assuming for simplicity radiation propagating in the z direction, we can describe the electric field \mathbf{E} in terms of its components E_l and E_r along two orthogonal reference axes l and r in the xy plane:

$$E_l(t) = E_{0l}(t) \cos\left(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} z\right) \quad (2.1)$$

$$E_r(t) = E_{0r}(t) \cos\left(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} z + \delta(t)\right), \quad (2.2)$$

where t is time, ω the wave frequency, λ the wavelength, $E_{0l}(t)$ and $E_{0r}(t)$ the electric field amplitudes and $\delta(t)$ a phase shift between the two components.

2.1.1 Polarisation ellipse

For a purely monochromatic wave, amplitudes and phase shift are constant over time and the light is said to be *completely polarised*. Under these circumstances, Eqs. (2.1) and (2.2) can be rewritten as

$$E_l(t) = E_{0l} \cos\left(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} z\right) \quad (2.3)$$

$$E_r(t) = E_{0r} \cos\left(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} z + \delta\right) . \quad (2.4)$$

Combining the two equations above, and after some algebra, we obtain the equation of an ellipse, that is:

$$\left[\frac{E_l(t)}{E_{0l}}\right]^2 + \left[\frac{E_r(t)}{E_{0r}}\right]^2 - 2\frac{E_l(t)}{E_{0l}}\frac{E_r(t)}{E_{0r}}\cos\delta = \sin^2\delta . \quad (2.5)$$

Therefore, as time passes and the wave propagates in the z direction, the tip of the electric field vector \mathbf{E} traces out an ellipse in the xy plane and the light is said to be *elliptically polarised*. Two special cases are those of *linearly polarised* and *circularly polarised* light. In the former, we have $\delta = 0$ or $\delta = \pi$ so that the ellipse degenerates to a straight line (i.e. the electric field oscillates along a constant direction):

$$E_l(t) = \pm \frac{E_{0l}}{E_{0r}} E_r(t) . \quad (2.6)$$

In the latter, we have $\delta = \pm\frac{\pi}{2}$ and equal amplitudes $E_{0l} = E_{0r} \equiv E_0$ so that the ellipse degenerates to a circle:

$$E_l^2(t) + E_r^2(t) = E_0^2 . \quad (2.7)$$

Specifically, the sign of the phase shift δ defines the sense of rotation of the electric field when viewed anti-parallel to the direction of propagation: $\delta = -\frac{\pi}{2}$ corresponds to a clockwise rotation (and the wave is said to be right-handed circularly polarised) while $\delta = +\frac{\pi}{2}$ to a counter-clockwise rotation (left-handed circularly polarised).

The polarisation ellipse defined by Eq. (2.5) is illustrated in Fig. 2.1. The ellipse can be described in terms of two angles: the *polarisation angle* χ – defining the orientation of the ellipse with respect to the reference axes l and r – and the *ellipticity angle* γ – derived from the ratio between the semi-minor, b , and the semi-major, a , axis of the ellipse, $\tan\gamma = b/a$. It can be shown (Goldstein 2011) that these two angles are related to the amplitudes and the phase shift of the wave through the following two equations:

$$\tan 2\chi = 2\frac{E_{0l}E_{0r}}{E_{0l}^2 - E_{0r}^2} \cos\delta \quad 0 \leq \chi \leq \pi , \quad (2.8)$$

$$\sin 2\gamma = 2\frac{E_{0l}E_{0r}}{E_{0l}^2 + E_{0r}^2} \sin\delta \quad -\frac{\pi}{4} < \gamma \leq \frac{\pi}{4} . \quad (2.9)$$

Linear polarisation ($\delta = 0, \pi$) corresponds to $\chi = \text{const}$ and $\gamma = 0$, circular polarisation ($\delta = \pm\frac{\pi}{2}$ and $E_{0l} = E_{0r}$) to $\chi = 0$ and $\gamma = \pm\frac{\pi}{4}$.

Figure 2.1: The polarisation ellipse traced out by the electric field \mathbf{E} in the plane lr orthogonal to the direction of propagation. The polarisation angle χ and the ellipticity angle γ are indicated.

2.1.2 Stokes parameters

As shown by Eq. (2.5), the electric field vector of a monochromatic wave traces out an ellipse in the plane perpendicular to the direction of propagation. Following the electric field, however, is observationally not feasible as the typical oscillation period for the propagating wave, $T = 2\pi/\omega$, is too small (e.g. of the order of 10^{-14} s in the optical range). Instead, one can measure the intensity of a beam, that is a time average of the square of the electric field over an interval that is much longer than the oscillation period. Therefore, a more convenient way of representing polarisation is through the so-called Stokes parameters – first introduced by George Gabriel Stokes in 1852 – that describe the polarisation ellipse of Eq. (2.5) in terms of measurable intensities.

Expressions for the Stokes parameters can be derived by performing the time average ($\langle \dots \rangle$) of the polarisation ellipse in Eq. (2.5):

$$\frac{\langle E_l^2(t) \rangle}{E_{0l}^2} + \frac{\langle E_r^2(t) \rangle}{E_{0r}^2} - 2 \frac{\langle E_l(t) E_r(t) \rangle}{E_{0l} E_{0r}} \cos \delta = \sin^2 \delta \quad (2.10)$$

Owing to the periodicity of the electric field components (see Eqs. 2.3 and 2.4), time averages can be computed over a single oscillation period T . Multiplying Eq. (2.10) by $4E_{0l}^2 E_{0r}^2$ and calculating time averages using

$$\langle E_i(t) E_j(t) \rangle = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T E_i(t) E_j(t) dt \quad i, j = 1, r \quad (2.11)$$

we obtain:

$$2E_{0r}^2 E_{0l}^2 + 2E_{0l}^2 E_{0r}^2 - (2E_{0l} E_{0r} \cos \delta)^2 = (2E_{0l} E_{0r} \sin \delta)^2 . \quad (2.12)$$

This can be rewritten in a more convenient form by adding and subtracting $E_{0l}^4 + E_{0r}^4$ to the left-hand side:

$$(E_{0l}^2 + E_{0r}^2)^2 - (E_{0l}^2 - E_{0r}^2)^2 - (2E_{0l} E_{0r} \cos \delta)^2 = (2E_{0l} E_{0r} \sin \delta)^2 . \quad (2.13)$$

The four terms inside the parentheses have the dimensions of intensity and lead to the definition of the Stokes parameters:

$$I = E_{0l}^2 + E_{0r}^2 \quad (2.14)$$

$$Q = E_{0l}^2 - E_{0r}^2 \quad (2.15)$$

$$U = 2E_{0l} E_{0r} \cos \delta \quad (2.16)$$

$$V = 2E_{0l} E_{0r} \sin \delta . \quad (2.17)$$

These parameters can be arranged into a four-dimensional Stokes vector $\mathbf{S} = (I, Q, U, V)$ or, alternatively, in terms of a dimensionless Stokes vector $\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{S}/I = (1, q, u, v)$. With the definitions above, Eq. (2.13) can be rewritten as either

$$I^2 = Q^2 + U^2 + V^2 \quad (2.18)$$

or

$$1 = q^2 + u^2 + v^2 , \quad (2.19)$$

which express the relationships between the four Stokes parameters for a completely-polarised monochromatic wave. Stokes parameters Q , U and V (but not q , u and v) are additive, so that the sum of two beams with Stokes vectors S_1 and S_2 is a beam with Stokes vector $S_{\text{tot}} = S_1 + S_2$.

While I indicates the total intensity of the wave, the meaning of Q , U and V can be understood by writing these quantities in terms of the angles χ and γ of the polarisation ellipse. First, comparing the definitions of the Stokes parameters above to Eqs. (2.8)

and (2.9) gives

$$\tan 2\chi = \frac{U}{Q} \quad 0 \leq \chi \leq \pi, \quad (2.20)$$

$$\sin 2\gamma = \frac{V}{I} \quad -\frac{\pi}{4} < \gamma \leq \frac{\pi}{4}. \quad (2.21)$$

Then, the combination of the latter two relations with Eq. (2.18) leads to the following representation of the dimensionless Stokes vector \mathbf{s} in terms of χ and γ :

$$\mathbf{s} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ q \\ u \\ v \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \cos 2\gamma \cos 2\chi \\ \cos 2\gamma \sin 2\chi \\ \sin 2\gamma \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.22)$$

A *linearly polarised* wave ($\gamma = 0$) is completely defined by the Stokes parameters Q and U ($V = 0$), with the polarisation angle χ specified by Eq. (2.20). In particular, Q expresses the difference in intensity between the electric field components along l and r (see Eq. 2.15): $\chi = 0$ corresponds to $q = 1$ and an electric field oscillating along l , $\chi = \pi/2$ to $q = -1$ and an electric field oscillating along r . The Stokes parameter U , instead, represents the difference in intensity between the components along two orthogonal axes counter-clockwise rotated (as viewed antiparallel to the direction of propagation) of $\pi/4$ with respect to l and r : $\chi = \pi/4$ corresponds to $u = 1$, while $\chi = \frac{3}{4}\pi$ to $u = -1$. Finally, a *circularly polarised* wave ($\chi = 0$ and $\gamma = \pm\pi/4$) is completely described by the Stokes parameter V ($Q = U = 0$): $\gamma = \pi/4$ corresponds to $v = 1$ and to a right-handed polarised wave, while $\gamma = -\pi/4$ to $v = -1$ and to a left-handed polarised wave. Electric fields for the special cases mentioned above are summarised pictorially in Fig. 2.2.

2.1.3 Partially polarised light

In the previous sections, we have assumed that the light was monochromatic and completely polarised. In practice, however, beams of radiation always consist of a superposition of monochromatic waves. Phase shifts, $\delta(t)$, and amplitudes, $E_{0i}(t)$, are not constant over time and the light is said to be *partially polarised*. Provided that the phase shifts and amplitudes vary slowly compared to the frequency ω of the wave, the

Figure 2.2: *Upper panels.* Oscillation orientations of the electric field for four different linearly polarised states. *Lower panels.* Polarisation circle traced out by the electric field in two different circularly polarised states. Normalised Stokes parameters and polarisation (upper) and ellipticity (lower) angles are stated for each panel.

Stokes parameters of Eqs. (2.14)–(2.17) can be replaced by appropriate time averages

$$I = \langle E_{0l}^2(t) + E_{0r}^2(t) \rangle \quad (2.23)$$

$$Q = \langle E_{0l}^2(t) - E_{0r}^2(t) \rangle \quad (2.24)$$

$$U = 2 \langle E_{0l}(t) E_{0r}(t) \cos \delta(t) \rangle \quad (2.25)$$

$$V = 2 \langle E_{0l}(t) E_{0r}(t) \sin \delta(t) \rangle \quad (2.26)$$

and the Stokes formalism presented above is still valid. As shown by Chandrasekhar (1960), the Stokes parameters for a partially polarised wave satisfy

$$I^2 \geq Q^2 + U^2 + V^2 \quad (2.27)$$

or equivalently

$$1 \geq q^2 + u^2 + v^2, \quad (2.28)$$

Figure 2.3: Polarisation effect of Thomson scattering. An incoming unpolarised beam is scattered by an electron and becomes linearly polarised in a direction perpendicular to the scattering plane (plane defined by the incoming and outgoing beams).

where the equality sign holds for a completely polarised wave (cf. with Eqs. 2.18 and 2.19). From this, we can define the polarisation degree P as

$$P = \frac{\sqrt{Q^2 + U^2 + V^2}}{I} = \sqrt{q^2 + u^2 + v^2} \quad 0 \leq P \leq 1 \quad . \quad (2.29)$$

$P = 1$ corresponds to completely polarised light, while $P = 0$ to unpolarised light.

2.2 Polarising and depolarising contributions in supernovae

2.2.1 Electron scattering

Thomson scattering by free electrons is the chief mechanism to polarise radiation in SNe. Free electrons are relatively abundant in SN ejecta, and this is especially true at early epochs when the ionisation fraction is highest (see also Fig. 4.7). As first described by Sir J. J. Thomson, the original formulation of the Thomson scattering law refers to *unpolarised radiation*: if an unpolarised beam is scattered by a charged particle in a direction making an angle Θ with the incoming direction, the scattered radiation (i) follows a dipole pattern, with intensity depending on the scattering angle through a factor $(\cos^2\Theta + 1)$ and (ii) is linearly polarised in a direction perpendicular to the scattering plane (i.e. the plane defined by the incoming and outgoing beams) and with polarisation percentage

$$P = \frac{1 - \cos^2\Theta}{1 + \cos^2\Theta} \quad . \quad (2.30)$$

In particular, the outgoing beam is unpolarised for $\Theta = 0$ (forward scattering) and $\Theta = \pi$ (back scattering), fully polarised ($P = 1$) for $\Theta = \pi/2$ and partially polarised for intermediate scattering angles. The basic scattering process is illustrated in Fig. 2.3.

As first shown by Chandrasekhar (1960), Thomson scattering for *polarised radiation* can be conveniently described in terms of the Stokes parameters. In particular, an incoming beam of radiation characterized by a Stokes vector \mathbf{S}_{in} is transformed to a beam with $\mathbf{S}_{\text{out}} = A_{\text{es}}(\Theta)\mathbf{S}_{\text{in}}$, where $A_{\text{es}}(\Theta)$ is the phase matrix for Thomson (and Rayleigh) scattering

$$A_{\text{es}}(\Theta) = \frac{3}{4} \begin{pmatrix} \cos^2\Theta + 1 & \cos^2\Theta - 1 & 0 & 0 \\ \cos^2\Theta - 1 & \cos^2\Theta + 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2\cos\Theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 2\cos\Theta \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.31)$$

It is readily verified that this formulation reduces to that stated above for the particular case of unpolarised radiation (i.e. with $Q_{\text{in}} = U_{\text{in}} = V_{\text{in}} = 0$). In addition, a closer look to the phase matrix in Eq. (2.31) shows that Thomson scattering is *not* able to create circular polarisation from unpolarised radiation, that is $V_{\text{in}} = 0$ implies $V_{\text{out}} = 0$ for any scattering angle Θ . In other words, circular polarisation satisfies a transfer equation that is independent from linear polarisation (Chandrasekhar 1960).

2.2.2 Line scattering

Together with electron scattering, *bound-bound* line interactions are the major source of opacity in SNe (see e.g. Pinto & Eastman 2000b). The influence of line scattering on polarisation was first investigated by Hamilton (1947). Neglecting the effect of collisions, he showed that the polarising contribution of *resonance* line scattering can be described via the hybrid phase matrix

$$A_{\text{ls}}(\Theta) = \frac{3}{4}E_1 \begin{pmatrix} \cos^2\Theta + 1 & \cos^2\Theta - 1 & 0 & 0 \\ \cos^2\Theta - 1 & \cos^2\Theta + 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2\cos\Theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 2\frac{E_3}{E_1}\cos\Theta \end{pmatrix} + E_2 \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.32)$$

where E_i are coefficients related to the total angular momentum quantum numbers of the upper and lower state of the specific transition. Normalisation of $A_{\text{ls}}(\Theta)$ requires that $E_1 + E_2 = 1$. First we note that – as was the case for Thomson scattering – line scattering is not able to create circular polarisation from unpolarised radiation. The hybrid phase matrix in Eq. (2.32) can be seen as the combination of a dipole polarising term (almost identical to the electron scattering phase matrix A_{es} in Eq. 2.31) and an isotropic depolarising term, with relative contributions depending on the E_1 and E_2 coefficients. Although most of the line transitions are only weakly polarising as they have E_1 coefficients that are much smaller than 1, polarisation may arise in cases where the

dipole is the dominant term (Chandrasekhar 1960; Jeffery 1989, 1991). For instance, the transition from a lower level with total angular momentum $j = 0$ to an upper level with $j = 1$ is associated with coefficients $E_1 = 1$ and $E_2 = 0$ and thus acts as a polarising contribution (Jeffery 1989).

Despite expressing the polarising contribution of resonant lines in a simple form, the Hamilton prescription does not take into account collisional processes. The net effect of *collisional processes* would be of leading to a complete redistribution in the upper and lower levels of the transition and thus to destroy the polarisation information. This assumption – occurring when collisional timescales are much shorter than the characteristic time for the transition – has been made in previous polarisation studies (e.g. Höflich et al. 1996; Howell et al. 2001; Kasen et al. 2003). For optically thick lines, an additional process responsible for destroying the intrinsic polarisation acquired via line scattering is that of *multiple scattering* of photons in the resonant region, which causes a loss of information on directionality and hence polarisation (Kasen et al. 2003). Therefore, the intrinsic polarisation from line scattering in SNe is typically diluted (if not destroyed) by collisional processes and/or multiple scattering in optically thick lines. When modelling polarisation in SN ejecta, electron scattering is thus usually considered as the main polarising process while line scattering assumed as a depolarising contribution (see e.g. Jeffery 1991; Höflich et al. 1996; Kasen et al. 2003). In the rest of this work, we will also adopt this assumption.

2.2.3 Magnetic field

Wolstencroft & Kemp (1972) suggested that a strong magnetic field in SN explosions might produce circular polarisation in the optical range. At the time of writing, only three attempts have been made to find circularly polarised light around SNe and no clear detection has ever been reported. Although Wolstencroft & Kemp (1972) measured a circular polarisation level of $v = -0.08 \pm 0.04$ per cent around the Type I SN 1972E, determining what fraction of this signal was intrinsic to the SN is challenging as the observations were carried out on a single night and with broad-band polarimetry (see Section 2.3.3). Circular polarisation consistent with zero was found in the spectropolarimetry of the Type Ia SN 1983G (McCall et al. 1984) and of the Type Ia SN 2012fr ($v = 0 \pm 0.2$ per cent; Maund et al. 2013) around maximum light.

Although future observational and theoretical studies will be needed to assess the extent to which part of the radiation from SNe can be circularly polarised, that goes beyond the scope of this thesis. In the rest of this work, we will therefore neglect circular polarisation (i.e. $v = 0$) and discuss only linear polarisation. In our spectropolarimetric modelling, this assumption is justified by the fact that the explosion models investi-

gated (see Chapters 4 and 5) do not include magnetic fields and that – in scattering atmospheres in the absence of magnetic field – the radiative transfer equation for linear and circular polarisation can be decoupled (see Eqs. 2.31 and 2.32 and discussion in Sections 2.2.1 and 2.2.2).

2.3 Linear polarisation as a probe of the supernova geometry

In the context of SNe, the most important aspect of polarimetry is that it allows one to study the geometry of these explosions. This is crucial for spatially unresolved astrophysical events like SNe, since information on the shape of these explosions is difficult to obtain from light curves and flux spectra (but see e.g. Maeda et al. 2010). In this section we illustrate how the detection (or non-detection) of linear polarisation from SNe can be used as a direct probe of their geometry.

2.3.1 Continuum polarisation

As discussed in Section 2.2.1, Thomson scattering is the main contributor to the continuum polarisation in SNe. Thomson scattering – limit of the wavelength-dependent Compton scattering for low frequencies – is approximately a grey process in the optical range, and thus the continuum polarisation in the optical is inherently *wavelength-independent*.

The left panel of Fig. 2.4 shows how a spherical electron-scattered photosphere would appear if it could be resolved. Because of the spherical symmetry, the projection of the photosphere as viewed by an observer is circular. Double arrows in this projected surface are representative of the linear polarisation vectors at different locations on the photodisk: their orientations indicate the oscillation direction of the electric field (as in Fig. 2.2), while their sizes are proportional to the degree of polarisation. First, we see that the polarisation angle (i.e. the orientation of each arrow) is always orthogonal to the radial direction. This can be understood by noting that radiation preferentially travels in the radial compared to the tangential direction and recalling that linear polarisation from electron scattering is always oriented perpendicular to the scattering plane (Section 2.2.1). Second, we notice that the degree of polarisation increases when moving from the center to the limb of the photosphere. This is because the radiation field at the limb is more isotropic compared to the inner regions, i.e. most of the radiation coming from the limb has travelled in the outward radial direction and then been scattered by an electron at angles close to $\Theta = \pi/2$.

With the current available instrumentation, even the most nearby SNe are too distant to be resolved and one can only measure an integrated polarisation level over the

Figure 2.4: Q and U continuum polarisation levels (bottom panels) predicted for different electron-scattering photospheres (top panels, adapted from Kasen et al. 2003). The left panels illustrate the case of a spherical photosphere, for which the projected surface is circular for any orientation. Middle and right panels show instead elliptically-projected photospheres from ellipsoids with different orientations. Double arrows indicate the orientation of the electric field, with their sizes proportional to the degree of polarisation. Blue arrows indicate contributions to Q , red arrows to U .

entire apparent photodisk. If the projection of the SN along the line-of-sight to the observer is *circular* – as in the spherical case discuss above – the integrated continuum polarisation will be null (i.e. $Q = U = 0$, see bottom left panel) since every contribution will be cancelled by an orthogonal contribution one quadrant away. In fact, recalling that the Stokes parameters are additive (see Section 2.1), any polarising contribution with Stokes parameters Q_1 and U_1 will be balanced by an orthogonal contribution with Stokes parameters $Q_2 = -Q_1$ and $U_2 = -U_1$.

If instead we have deviations from a circular symmetry in the projected photosphere, an imperfect cancellation of the Stokes vectors will lead to a net polarisation signal. In the case of an *elliptical* projection, for instance, contributions from the major axis will dominate over those from the minor axis. Two examples are shown in Fig. 2.4: elliptical projections with the major axis aligned in the horizontal direction (as viewed by the observer, middle panel) will be associated with $Q > 0$ and $U = 0$, while projection with the major axis rotated by $\pi/4$ in the clockwise direction (right-hand panel) with $U < 0$ and $Q = 0$.

Figure 2.5: Formation of the inverted P-Cygni polarisation profile (adapted from Kasen 2004) in a simple ellipsoidal model with line scattering occurring above (white region) the electron-scattering photosphere (grey region). See text for explanation.

2.3.2 Line polarisation

As mentioned in Section 2.2.2, line scattering in SNe can be considered as a depolarising contribution. As we will see in this section, however, this does not necessarily mean that the effect of line scattering is simply to decrease the polarisation level in the continuum. In particular, we will discuss two models that lead to different modulations in the polarisation signatures across spectral features: (i) a simple ellipsoidal model in which line scattering occurs above an electron-scattering photosphere and (ii) a “clumpy-ejecta” model in which line opacity is concentrated into clumpy regions above the photosphere. A different scenario incorporating the basic ideas of these two models is also presented.

We first consider a simple ellipsoidal model in which line scattering occurs above the electron-scattering photosphere (see Fig. 2.5) and gives rise to P-Cygni profiles in the flux spectra (see Section 1.3.1). To understand the specific polarisation modulation induced by line scattering, we need to distinguish between the emission peak and the blue-shifted absorption trough of the P-Cygni profile. The emission peak consists of unpolarised photons that are scattered by the line towards the observer, thus diluting the polarisation signal produced by electron-scattering. This leads to a polarisation

decrease across the emission peak of the P-Cygni profile. In contrast, the absorbing material preferentially blocks photons from the more forward-scattered (i.e. less polarised) inner regions, thus increasing the relative contribution of the highly polarised flux from the outer regions (see above). This leads to a polarisation *increase* across the absorption trough of the P-Cygni profile. As a result, the combination of these two effects gives rise to the so-called *inverted P-Cygni* polarisation profile, originally predicted by McCall et al. (1984, see also Jeffery 1989) and then first observed by Cropper et al. (1988) in the polarisation spectra of the well-studied SN 1987A.

The argument above suggests that the continuum polarisation level may be somehow related to the polarisation peak in the absorption trough. Leonard et al. (2001) argued that – in the limit where only unpolarised photons are scattered out-of-sight by the line – an upper bound on the absorption trough polarisation, $P_{\text{trough}}^{\text{max}}$, can be expressed as

$$P_{\text{trough}}^{\text{max}} = P_{\text{cont}} \frac{I_{\text{cont}}}{I_{\text{trough}}}, \quad (2.33)$$

where P_{cont} is the polarisation in the continuum region and I_{cont} and I_{trough} are the flux intensities in the continuum and line trough, respectively. Although this relation is probably an oversimplification (see also discussion in Leonard et al. 2001), it shows that in an ellipsoidal model some continuum polarisation must exist in order to produce a peak in the absorption trough of a line. As a consequence, Leonard et al. (2005) suggested that the detection of a weakly-polarised continuum in a SN with strongly-polarised features would argue against ellipsoidal models. In addition, as the electron-scattering and line opacity in this model share the same geometry, no difference in the polarisation angle is expected between the continuum and the lines (see also Section 2.3.3).

As illustrated in Fig. 2.6, an alternative way of producing polarisation changes in the line absorption trough is that of *partial covering* caused by asymmetrically-distributed material located above the electron-scattering photosphere (Leonard et al. 2001; Kasen et al. 2003; Hole et al. 2010). For instance, consider the simple case of Section 2.3.1 in which null continuum polarisation results from a circular projection of the electron-scattered photosphere. Now suppose that some absorbing material is concentrated into an asymmetric “clumpy” region above the electron-scattering photosphere (left panel of Fig. 2.6). The line opacity of this material will unevenly block the underlying photosphere and – provided that the clump size is comparable to the projected photospheric surface – produce a polarisation peak in the spectrum. In the specific case illustrated in Fig. 2.6, the clump region preferentially absorbs negative- U contributions and hence gives origin to a positive- U peak in the spectrum (Q is consistent with zero because of

Figure 2.6: Same as left- and middle- upper panels of Fig. 2.4, but with two “clumpy” line opacity regions (in orange) obscuring part of the negative- U electron-scattered contributions (adapted from Kasen et al. 2003). See text for explanation.

symmetry). The right panel of Fig. 2.6 shows a second example, where the absorbing material partially covers an elliptically-projected photosphere. For this configuration, the continuum will be polarised with $Q > 0$ while the absorption trough with $U > 0$, that is we will have a change of $\pi/4$ in the polarisation angle.

An alternative model for producing line polarisation has been proposed by Kasen et al. (2004). In this model, which to some extent can be regarded as a combination of the ellipsoidal and the “clumpy-ejecta” model, a *hole* is carved out in the ejecta of the SN by the interaction with a non-degenerate companion star (SD system, see Section 1.4.1). While similar predictions to the ellipsoidal model are found for orientations far away from the hole, very weakly polarised continua (~ 0.1 per cent) and prominent line polarisation (~ 1 per cent) are produced for viewing angles closer to the hole (see their fig. 10).

We note that, unlike the ellipsoidal model, the “clumpy-ejecta” model and the “ejecta-hole” model can potentially (i) produce a line-trough polarisation even for a symmetric photosphere with null continuum polarisation (e.g. left panel of Fig 2.6); (ii) predict strong line polarisation features for weakly-polarised continua; (iii) cause a rotation in the polarisation angle between the continuum and the line (e.g. right panel of Fig 2.6).

Regardless of the specific model responsible for introducing line polarisation, it is clear that the detection of polarisation across SN spectral features signals some sort of asymmetry in the element distribution. In addition, we have seen that different polarisation percentage levels (and possibly polarisation angles) are predicted for the continuum

and the spectral features. To summarise, polarisation detected in the *continuum* indicates large-scale asymmetries in the electron-scattering photosphere, while polarisation across *spectral features* is reflective of asphericities in the element distribution.

2.3.3 Q/U plane and dominant axis

As shown in the previous two sections, polarimetry can give us insights into the geometry of SN explosions. *Broad-band polarimetry*, where the Stokes parameters are measured over wide broad-band filters, is useful to build intuition about the overall polarisation level in SNe but is not capable of distinguishing between continuum and line polarisation contributions. In contrast, *spectropolarimetry* allows one to measure Stokes parameters as a function of wavelength and hence to separate continuum and line polarisation signals. In this respect, a valuable tool for linking polarisation signatures to the SN ejecta structure is the so-called *Q/U plane*, in which Q and U values are plotted as a function of wavelength. We illustrate the importance of the *Q/U plane* by means of two examples (see below), in which polarisation spectra have been calculated for two idealised configurations using our test code (see Section 3.5).

Fig. 2.7 shows the *Q/U plane* calculated for an *axisymmetric* ellipsoidal atmosphere in which electron scattering and line scattering can occur. Line opacity for an artificial 6000 Å transition has been used for these calculations. As discussed in Section 2.3.2, the presence of line scattering leads to an inverted P-Cygni profile in the polarisation spectrum (left-middle panel). However, as the continuum and line opacity share the same geometry, the polarisation modulation across the spectral feature does not introduce any rotation in the polarisation angle (left-bottom panel). From Eq. (2.20), a constant polarisation angle χ means a constant ratio between U and Q as a function of wavelength. Therefore, the *Q/U plane* for this model is characterised by a straight line (right-bottom panel) that defines the so-called *dominant axis* of the system (Wang & Wheeler 2008). In particular, the angle defined by the dominant axis in the *Q/U plane*, 2χ , is directly related to the orientation of the axis of symmetry of the ellipsoid, χ , in the projected plane towards the observer (right-upper panel).

If now we break the axial symmetry in the line opacity distribution, for instance introducing a “clumpy” region as discussed in Section 2.3.2, we observe a different distribution of the points in the *Q/U plane* (Fig. 2.8). As the electron-scattering photosphere is axisymmetric, the continuum region is still characterised by a constant polarisation angle χ . At wavelengths associated with the spectral feature, however, we see changes in both polarisation percentage and angle that result into a *loop* in the *Q/U plane*.

Figure 2.7: Spectropolarimetric signatures predicted by our test code for an axisymmetric ellipsoidal model (upper right panel) including opacities for electron-scattering and for a line transition with rest-frame wavelength of 6000 \AA . Left panels show flux (upper), polarisation percentage P (middle) and angle χ (lower) in the wavelength region between 5600 and 6200 \AA . The vertical line marks the rest wavelength of the artificial 6000 \AA . The corresponding Q/U plane is reported in the bottom right panel. The yellow star marks the averaged polarisation level in the continuum range, while the straight line indicates a weighted least-squares fitting to the simulation data. Pixel-to-pixel variations in the spectra, and thus deviations from the straight line in the Q/U plane, are due to Monte Carlo noise in the simulation (see also Section 4.3).

As illustrated by the two examples above, the Q/U plane provides a natural way of visualising to what extent SN ejecta are axisymmetric. The presence of a dominant axis in the Q/U plane indicates an overall axial symmetry in the ejecta, while departures from the dominant axis (e.g. loops) are reflective of line opacity distributions breaking the axial symmetry of the system.

Figure 2.8: Same as Fig. 2.7, but including a single clumpy line opacity region as illustrated in the upper right panel. The straight line in the Q/U plane indicates the linear fitting of the data points in Fig. 2.7.

2.4 Observing Type Ia supernovae in polarisation

Although the earliest polarimetric observation of a SN dates back to 1968 (Serkowski 1970), the first systematic observational campaigns were started in the mid 1990s. Collecting polarimetric data for several SNe, two different programs – one led by Lifan Wang and Craig Wheeler at the McDonald observatory (Wang et al. 1996) and one by Alex Filippenko and Leonard Douglas at the Keck telescope (Leonard et al. 2000) – first highlighted a clear distinction between thermonuclear and core-collapse events. Thermonuclear SNe Ia were characterised by (i) low continuum polarisation levels (smaller than ~ 0.4 per cent) and by (ii) an overall polarisation signal that was larger at earlier (around maximum) compared to later epochs. In contrast, core-collapse SNe were (i) significantly polarised ($P > 1$ per cent in the continuum) and (ii) characterised by larger polarisation at later compared to earlier epochs. Compared to core-collapse events, SNe Ia have been interpreted as rather spherical explosions with the largest asymme-

tries in the outer compared to the inner regions of the ejecta.

After a brief discussion on the problems introduced by interstellar polarisation (Section 2.4.1), in this Section we focus on thermonuclear SNe Ia and summarise our current knowledge about the geometry of these explosions. For a more detailed overview, we refer the reader to the comprehensive review of Wang & Wheeler (2008).

2.4.1 Interstellar polarisation

Polarisation from interstellar dust can introduce a severe complication when observing SNe. Interstellar polarisation (ISP) is caused by elongated dust particles that are aligned by the interstellar magnetic field and preferentially absorb radiation with electric field oriented perpendicular to it (Davis Jr & Greenstein 1951). Light interacting with interstellar dust will therefore acquire linear polarisation, with a wavelength-independent polarisation angle parallel to the interstellar magnetic field orientation. This additional polarisation contribution, introduced by interstellar dust in either the SN host galaxy or the Milky Way, makes the interpretation of the intrinsic SN polarisation signal more difficult.

For the Milky Way, Serkowski et al. (1975) have found an empirical relation – known as Serkowski law – expressing the ISP wavelength dependence as

$$P_{\text{ISP}}(\lambda) = P_{\text{max}} \exp\left(-K \ln^2 \frac{\lambda_{\text{max}}}{\lambda}\right). \quad (2.34)$$

Here P_{max} indicates the maximum degree of polarisation, occurring at λ_{max} , while K can be evaluated following the relation from Whittet et al. (1992), $K = 0.01 + 1.66 \lambda_{\text{max}}(\mu\text{m})$. In addition, they determined empirical relations between reddening and polarisation studying a large sample of Galactic star. Specifically, they found that line-of-sights associated with a reddening $E(B - V)$ display polarisation levels P_{max} in the range between 0 and $9.0 \times E(B - V)$ per cent depending on the polarisation efficiency of the dust grains. Moreover, λ_{max} is found to be related to the total-to-selective absorption ratio through $R_V = 5.5 \lambda_{\text{max}}(\mu\text{m})$. For Galactic values, $R_V = 3.1$ and thus $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 0.56 \mu\text{m}$.

At variance with the SN intrinsic polarisation signal, the interstellar contribution is characterised by a constant polarisation angle and by the absence of time evolution. Therefore, these two properties should in principle allow us to distinguish the two polarisation signals. In practice, although different approaches have been proposed to properly subtract the interstellar contribution from SN polarisation spectra, no completely satisfactory technique has yet been identified. A widely used approach relies

on the assumption that certain spectral ranges – such as regions affected by strong line blending and/or the emission peaks of strong P-Cygni profiles – are intrinsically unpolarised (see also Section 2.2.2). A measure of the Stokes parameters Q and U in these ranges, coupled with the Serkowski law in Eq. (2.34) and the fact that the ISP polarisation angle is constant, allows one to subtract the ISP from the observed spectra (note that this technique assumes the Serkowski law to be valid also in the host galaxy). Another technique has been proposed by Wang et al. (2001), in which the ISP is estimated from the distribution of points in the Q/U plane assuming that the SN ejecta are perfectly axisymmetric. The safest technique is probably the observation of a SN at late-epochs (from about one month after maximum light), when the intrinsic polarisation is expected to be null due to the ejecta expansion. Although promising, this approach has been applied to a very small number of SNe (Wang et al. 2003; Tanaka et al. 2010; Patat et al. 2012) since sufficiently good signal-to-noise in the polarisation spectra is typically difficult to achieve at these late times.

2.4.2 Normal Type Ia supernovae

In normal SNe Ia, *continuum polarisation* is typically quite low ($\lesssim 0.4$ per cent) prior to optical maximum, pointing towards very small departures from a global spherical symmetry. Continuum polarisation levels are generally inferred in the wavelength range between ~ 6400 and 7200 \AA , a region usually assumed to be devoid of strong lines and thus reflective of the continuum level (Pinto & Eastman 2000b; Kasen et al. 2004; Leonard et al. 2005; Patat et al. 2009). In the rest of the paper, we will refer to this region as the “pseudo-continuum” region. The extent to which SNe Ia deviates from perfectly symmetrical explosions is usually quantified in the context of electron-scattering dominated ellipsoidal models. As shown by Höflich (1991), continuum polarisation levels lower than 0.4 per cent can be reproduced by ellipsoidal photospheres with asphericities smaller than ~ 10 per cent (i.e. axis ratios larger than 0.9, see his fig. 4). These values, however, are predicted for ellipsoids viewed along an equatorial orientation (where the polarisation is maximum) and should thus be considered as lower limits on the asphericities of SN Ia ejecta. More aspherical ellipsoid would be required for observer orientations out of the equatorial plane.

Although very low levels are detected in the continuum, significant polarisation (up to ~ 1 per cent) is found across the *line* profiles of optical spectral features, suggesting that asymmetries in the element distribution are present. Furthermore, polarisation levels across line features are often associated with loops in the Q/U plane, pointing towards departure from axial symmetry. Line polarisation is typically stronger before maximum light and decreases thereafter (but see the case of calcium in Patat et al. 2009

Figure 2.9: Distribution of Si II $\lambda 6355$ peak polarisation at 5 d before B -band maximum for 19 normal SNe Ia (Wang et al. 2007; Patat et al. 2009; Maund et al. 2013; Patat et al. 2014; Porter et al. 2016).

and Zelaya et al. 2013). This behaviour is opposite to that observed in core-collapse events and indicates that the outer layers in SN Ia ejecta are more asymmetric than the inner ones.

The Si II $\lambda 6355$ line is usually polarised in SNe Ia. Polarisation levels across this spectral feature typically reach their peak around one week before maximum (Wang et al. 2007, but see discussion in Porter et al. 2016) and are generally smaller than 1 per cent (see Fig. 2.9). It is remarkable that all the five SNe with Si II $\lambda 6355$ polarisation larger than 0.9 per cent (SN 1997bp, SN 2002bo, SN 2004dt, SN 2004ef and SN 2006X; Leonard et al. 2005; Wang et al. 2007; Patat et al. 2009) display relatively high photospheric velocities and large temporal variations in the Si II $\lambda 6355$ profile, belonging to the “high-velocity gradient” (HVG) class of Benetti et al. (2005), the “broad-line” class of Branch et al. (2006) and the “high-velocity” class of Wang et al. (2009). This is consistent with the suggestion of Leonard et al. (2005) that polarisation signatures and line velocities might correlate in SNe Ia. We will come back to this property in Section 2.4.4.

Together with the the Si II $\lambda 6355$ line, the Ca II IR triplet is typically the most polarised spectral feature in SNe Ia. In particular, transition from a strongly polarised

high-velocity component to a more weakly polarised low-velocity component is often observed from pre- to post-maximum. This was originally seen in SN 2001el (Wang et al. 2003), the first SN Ia to be observed at multi-epochs and with good signal-to-noise. While no clear polarisation signal was observed across the photospheric low-velocity component, the high-velocity feature (see Section 1.3) of the Ca II IR line was polarised at levels of 0.7 per cent before maximum and then unpolarised a week past maximum. In addition, the high-velocity features showed a distinct loop in the Q/U plane, which was explained by Kasen et al. (2003) in terms of a two-component model with an axisymmetric photosphere and a detached clumped shell of absorbing material (see also Section 2.5). A similar transition from high- to low-velocity components was also observed in two other SNe Ia with multi-epoch and high-quality spectropolarimetric observations (SN 2006X, Patat et al. 2009, and SN 2012fr, Maund et al. 2013).

While significant polarisation signals are found for the Si II $\lambda 6355$ and Ca II IR lines, very weak (if not null) polarisation levels are typically measured across other optical features¹. This is especially true for spectral regions with $\lambda \lesssim 5000 \text{ \AA}$ that are affected by strong line blanketing and thus dominated by the depolarising contribution of line scattering. As a result, a rise in polarisation level from blue to red wavelengths is frequently observed in SNe Ia (e.g. Wang et al. 1997, 2003; Leonard et al. 2005; Chornock & Filippenko 2008) and ascribed to the decreasing line blanketing at longer wavelengths.

A final aspect is the apparent lack of polarisation across the O I $\lambda 7774$ feature. Despite being seen in flux spectra of normal SNe Ia (see Section 1.3), this feature appears not to be polarised. In particular, even when investigating relatively polarised objects as SN 2004dt and SN 2006X, Wang et al. (2006) and Patat et al. (2009) were only able to place upper limits of ~ 0.3 per cent on the O I $\lambda 7774$ degree of polarisation. Based on the spectropolarimetric data of SN 2004dt, Wang et al. (2006) have interpreted the fact that silicon, calcium and oxygen features are seen at similar velocities, but with different polarimetric properties, as evidence that aspherically-distributed IMEs should spatially coexist with the more spherically-distributed oxygen layer. This interpretation was supported by predictions from delayed-detonation models (Howell et al. 2001; Höflich et al. 2006, see also Section 2.5).

¹An exception to this behaviour is found for highly polarised objects like SN 2004dt (Leonard et al. 2005; Wang et al. 2006) and SN 2006X (Patat et al. 2009), where polarisation peaks associated with Mg II, Si II, S II, Fe II and Si III lines are observed at levels between 0.3 and 1 per cent.

2.4.3 Peculiar Type Ia supernovae

Subluminous “91bg-like” SNe Ia (Section 1.3.2) show different polarisation signatures compared to normal SNe Ia. So far, only two objects of this class have been observed in polarisation: SN 1999by (Howell et al. 2001) and SN 2005ke (Patat et al. 2012). While characterised by relatively small line polarisation, both objects display a continuum level that is higher (0.3-0.8 per cent) than normal SNe Ia. This points towards global asphericities in the ejecta of sub-luminous SNe Ia that are larger compared to normal SNe Ia (up to 15%, Höflich 1991).

Polarisation spectra for subluminous Type Iax SNe Ia are available for only one object, namely SN 2005hk (Chornock et al. 2006; Maund et al. 2010b). Compared to normal events, no peculiarities are found in the polarisation spectra, with low levels (~ 0.3 per cent) across both the continuum and the main spectral features.

Polarisation observations of over-luminous SNe Ia are available for only two objects: the “91T-like” SN 2001V and the peculiar SN 2009dc. Spectropolarimetric data of SN 2001V have never been published, but Wang et al. (2007) reported a Si II $\lambda 6355$ degree of polarisation consistent with zero about a week before maximum (see also Section 2.4.4). SN 2009dc was observed in polarisation by Tanaka et al. (2010) at 5.6 d past-maximum. This SN was found to be spectropolarimetrically similar to normal SNe Ia, with a continuum level smaller than 0.3 per cent and Si II $\lambda 6355$ and Ca II IR triplet lines associated with loops in the Q/U planes and polarised at 0.5 and 0.7 per cent levels, respectively. Whether or not this is a general feature of over-luminous SNe Ia remains to be seen.

2.4.4 Correlations

Wang et al. (2007) suggested that the peak polarisation of the Si II $\lambda 6355$ line inversely correlates with luminosity for normal SNe Ia. Specifically – studying 14 spectroscopically normal SNe Ia – they found a correlation between the Si II $\lambda 6355$ polarisation level at 5 d before maximum and the decline rate $\Delta m_{15}(B)$ (see left-hand panel in Fig. 2.10). As seen in Section 1.2, the latter quantity is known to anti-correlate with luminosity in normal SNe Ia, in the sense that brighter events have smaller $\Delta m_{15}(B)$ (i.e. decline more slowly). The strongly-polarised SN 2004dt and the sub-luminous SN 1999by did not follow this relation. This finding was strengthened by successive observations, with spectroscopically normal events (SN 2006X, Patat et al. 2009, SN 2012fr, Maund et al. 2013, and SN 2014J, Patat et al. 2014; Porter et al. 2016) following this trend. However, the peculiar sub-luminous SN 2005ke (Patat et al. 2012) was found to be a significant outlier from this relation. The correlation suggests that fainter and faster-declining

Figure 2.10: *Left-hand panel:* correlation between the Si π λ 6355 polarisation at 5 d before maximum and $\Delta m_{15}(B)$ (adapted from Wang et al. 2007). Filled circles represent SNe included in the Wang et al. (2007) dataset, while open symbols show four SNe taken from the literature (Patat et al. 2009, 2012; Maund et al. 2013; Patat et al. 2014; Porter et al. 2016). The straight line indicates the linear fit from Wang et al. (2007) including only spectroscopically normal SNe Ia (blue filled points). *Right-hand panel:* correlation between the Si π λ 6355 polarisation at 5 d before maximum and its velocity gradient $\dot{v}_{\text{Si II}}$ (from Maund et al. 2010a). The solid and dashed line indicates the linear fit to the normal SNe Ia (black points) excluding and including SN 2004dt, respectively. The over-luminous SN 2001V and the sub-luminous SN 1999by and SN 2005ke are outliers to this relation. Lower limits on the polarisation of three objects are shown in purple. The vertical dashed line divides LVG and HVG SNe (Benetti et al. 2005).

SNe Ia are more strongly polarised than brighter and slowly-declining SNe Ia. This might be reflective of the more complete nuclear burning (and thus higher production of ^{56}Ni) associated with brighter SNe Ia, which tends to destroy inhomogeneities in the ejecta and hence dilute the polarisation signal (Wang et al. 2007).

Another correlation was suggested by Maund et al. (2010a) between the polarisation and the time velocity evolution of the Si π λ 6355 line. As shown in the right-hand panel of Fig. 2.10, in the Si π profile the polarisation at 5 d before maximum is found to correlate with the temporal evolution of the velocity at the absorption minimum, defined as the averaged daily gradient of the expansion velocity, $\dot{v}_{\text{Si II}} = -\Delta v / \Delta t$ (Benetti et al. 2005). This implies that the latter is due to asymmetries in the SN ejecta (see also Maeda et al. 2010). The over-luminous SN 2001V and the sub-luminous SN 1999by and SN 2005ke are outliers to this relation. Therefore, as anticipated in Section 2.4.2, SNe Ia belonging to the HVG class (high $\dot{v}_{\text{Si II}}$, Benetti et al. 2005) are typically more strongly polarised than those in the LVG class (low $\dot{v}_{\text{Si II}}$). As suggested by Maund

et al. (2010a), this trend might be indicative of a silicon distribution offset from the centre viewed from different orientations. Compared to viewing angles close to the offset direction, orientations significantly away from it are associated with a silicon layer that is thinner and more evenly excited by the underlying photosphere (see also fig. 2 of Höflich et al. 2006). Therefore, the Si II λ 6355 line is characterised by a smaller velocity gradient (low \dot{v}_{SiII} , LVG) and a lower degree of polarisation.

2.5 Previous theoretical studies

In this section, we give a summary of the theoretical studies that have been performed in the past to model polarisation in SNe Ia. Previous polarisation predictions for SNe Ia have been generally made by remapping the outputs of one-dimensional hydrodynamic models to idealised geometries with simple departures from spherical symmetry. These idealised geometries are well suited for building intuition and establishing the framework for interpreting polarisation data.

The first polarisation model for SNe Ia was presented by Wang et al. (1997) within the framework of a delayed-detonation scenario (see Section 1.4.3). In an effort to interpret spectropolarimetric data of SN 1996X, they adopted the density and composition predicted by one spherical DDT model from Höflich et al. (1997) and mapped them to two-dimensional ellipsoids. They found a reasonable match with flux and polarisation spectra of SN 1996X for an axis ratio of 0.89 and a viewing angle of 30° . The same approach was later applied to different flavours of the DDT scenario and used to interpret polarisation data of the sub-luminous SN 1999by (Howell et al. 2001) and SN 2005ke (Patat et al. 2012) and of the strongly-polarised SN 2004dt (Höflich et al. 2006).

A similar remapping from a one-dimensional to a two-dimensional axisymmetric structure was utilised by Dessart & Hillier (2011) to predict polarisation observables for core-collapse Type II SNe. One important aspect of this work was to show how subtle cancellation and optical-depth effects can affect the modelled polarisation signals. In particular, these effects can produce sign reversal in the Stokes parameter spectra as a function of wavelength (see also Section 4.5.1) and relatively small signals even for strongly asymmetric ejecta. Unfortunately, at the time of writing, no polarisation predictions for SN Ia models have been presented by this group (see also discussion in Blondin et al. 2011).

In the context of the single-degenerate scenario, Kasen et al. (2004) carried out a parametrised study and calculated polarisation signatures for a configuration in which a non-degenerate companion star carves out a conical hole in the ejecta of an exploding WD (Marietta et al. 2000). Calculations were carried out assuming axial symmetry of

the ejecta and adopting the same compositional structure predicted by the W7 model (see Section 1.4.3). As mentioned in Section 2.3.2, polarisation spectra extracted for this model were strongly viewing-angle dependent and characterised by a bimodal behaviour. Orientations 90° -away from the hole were associated with continuum polarisation levels around 0.8 per cent and with inverted P-Cygni profiles across strong optical features. Viewing angles closer to the hole, instead, produced line-dominated spectra, with very low signals in the continuum ($\lesssim 0.2$ per cent) and strong polarisation peaks (1-2 per cent) across spectral lines.

The first study to investigate polarisation signatures for nonaxisymmetric geometries was carried out by Kasen et al. (2003). As mentioned in Section 2.4.2, the main goal of this work was to reproduce the loop created by the Ca II IR high-velocity component in the Q/U plane of SN 2001el. This was done using a parametrised two-component model, with the ejecta divided into an ellipsoidal photosphere and a detached high-velocity line-forming region breaking the axial symmetry. Polarisation profile for the Ca II IR triplet were synthesised exploring four different geometries for the high-velocity material: a spherical shell, an ellipsoidal shell or toroid with an axis of symmetry rotated from the photospheric one, and a clumped spherical shell. The best match with data was found for the clumped shell model. Further support to this scenario was provided by the semi-analytical work of Hole et al. (2010), which showed how randomly distributed clumpy structures can account for the high polarisation levels and loops in the Q/U plane observed across the spectral features of several SNe Ia.

Following exploratory investigations by Plewa et al. (2004) and Kasen & Plewa (2005), polarisation calculations for the GCD scenario (see Section 1.4.3) were carried out by Kasen & Plewa (2007) based on the axisymmetric explosion model of Plewa (2007). The overall spherical symmetry in the density distribution of the GCD model results into continuum polarisation levels ($\lesssim 0.1$ per cent) that are slightly lower than those observed in SNe Ia. Nonetheless, polarisation signatures extracted across the Si II $\lambda 6355$ and the Ca II IR profiles are strongly viewing-angle dependent and can reach up to 2 per cent levels for some orientations. At the time of writing and to the best of our knowledge, the work of Kasen & Plewa (2007) is the only previous study performing spectropolarimetry for the full ejecta morphology predicted by a multi-dimensional hydrodynamic simulation.

2.6 Motivation for this thesis

Despite much effort, answers to the questions of when, why and how SN Ia explosions are triggered remain unclear. As seen in Chapter 1, recent explosion simulations have led to a better understanding of the physics involved, and comparisons of syn-

thetic light curves and spectra with observations have played a key role in identifying which explosion scenarios are most promising. However, unambiguous discrimination between models is still challenging, even for the best nearby SNe. In particular, despite their ejecta morphologies are strikingly different (see e.g. Figs. 5.1 and 5.2), modern explosion models predict spectra at maximum light that are relatively similar to each others and that match those observed in SNe Ia comparably well (Röpke et al. 2012). In this respect, polarisation offers a unique opportunity to probe asymmetries in the modelled ejecta and thus to discriminate between the variety of possible explosion scenarios. As discussed in this chapter, the observational evidence that SNe Ia are associated with rather low levels of polarisation ($\lesssim 1$ per cent) demands modest asphericities in the progenitor system and/or explosion mechanism, thus providing the means to effectively test different explosion models.

In the past, polarisation calculations for SNe Ia have been typically carried out by remapping the outputs of one-dimensional models to idealised geometries with simple departures from spherical symmetry (see Section 2.5). These geometries include – for instance – ellipsoidal structures, clumped and toroidal shells or large scale asymmetries associated with ejecta overrunning the companion star (see Section 2.5). However, quantitative comparisons between predictions of multidimensional explosion models and data require that polarisation calculations are made for the complete density and composition distributions predicted by hydrodynamic simulations. To date, this type of calculations has been performed by only one study (Kasen & Plewa 2007) as the computational cost for extracting very low polarisation signals ($\lesssim 1$ per cent) with good signal-to-noise ratio is much larger than that needed for extracting flux spectra (a factor of ~ 1000 , see Kasen & Plewa 2007).

During this thesis we have developed a Monte Carlo scheme to calculate polarisation signatures for multi-dimensional SN explosion models. Special attention has been focused on exploring different noise-reduction techniques to reduce the computing time required for extracting observables from our simulations. In Chapter 3 we give details of the methodology used and present the validation of our polarisation scheme via an idealised test code.

In Chapter 4 we discuss the implementation of this polarisation scheme in the Monte Carlo radiative transfer code `ARTIS` (Kromer & Sim 2009) and present test calculations for simple models. First, we use the well-known one-dimensional W7 model (Nomoto et al. 1984; Iwamoto et al. 1999) to verify that our scheme can accurately recover zero polarisation from a spherical model. Then, we investigate the impact of aspherical ejecta on the polarisation spectra by calculating synthetic observables for prolate and oblate two-dimensional ellipsoidal models with SN Ia compositions.

In Chapter 5 we present a spectropolarimetric investigation of three modern multi-dimensional SN Ia explosion models. Specifically, we extract light curves, flux and polarisation spectra for one double-detonation, one delayed-detonation and one violent merger model. We compare predictions of models to data (and each other) and assess the extent to which their geometries can be distinguished via polarisation. Implications for the three different explosion scenarios are also discussed.

Although the focus of this thesis is on thermonuclear SNe Ia, in Chapter 6 we present a preliminary application of our polarisation scheme to a different type of SNe. In particular, we use our test code to interpret the first spectropolarimetric observations of a “superluminous” SN, an event belonging to a class of extremely bright transients that have been discovered and extensively studied in the past few years. In Chapter 7 we finally summarise our work and give an outlook for our future studies.

Chapter 3

A Monte Carlo scheme for polarisation

“The most beautiful thing we can experience is the mysterious. It is the source of all true art and science. He to whom the emotion is a stranger, who can no longer pause to wonder and stand wrapped in awe, is as good as dead – his eyes are closed. The insight into the mystery of life, coupled though it be with fear, has also given rise to religion. To know what is impenetrable to us really exists, manifesting itself as the highest wisdom and the most radiant beauty, which our dull faculties can comprehend only in their most primitive forms – this knowledge, this feeling is at the center of true religiousness.”

– Albert Einstein

In this chapter we outline the Monte Carlo scheme developed to calculate polarisation for SN explosion models. We start with a brief overview on Monte Carlo methods (Section 3.1) and on their use in radiative transfer simulations (Section 3.2). We then describe the general approach adopted to include polarisation in our Monte Carlo code in Section 3.3 and discuss different Monte Carlo noise reduction techniques in Section 3.4. Finally we present an idealised test code to validate our polarisation scheme (Section 3.5.1) and to select the most suitable technique for producing low signal-to-noise polarisation spectra (Section 3.5.2). Part of the contents of this chapter has been published in the Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society journal (Bulla et al. 2015).

3.1 Monte Carlo methods

Monte Carlo approaches are widely used across a variety of different disciplines (e.g. physical sciences, particle physics, engineering, biology, medicine, statistics and finance) as they are particularly valuable in addressing complex problems that can not be solved analytically. Their application in the astrophysical context is manifold. In observations, Monte Carlo methods can be used – for instance – to demonstrate the feasibility of an observational campaign, to quantify instrumental uncertainties or to estimate parameters during the data analysis (e.g. Wall & Jenkins 2012). In theoretical works, they are commonly used for e.g. radiative transfer problems (see Section 3.2), hierarchical structure formation models of the Universe (e.g. Kauffmann & White 1993) or binary population synthesis studies (e.g. Belczynski et al. 2002).

The common ingredient to all Monte Carlo calculations is the statistical sampling of a probability function via the generation of random numbers. Suppose that the outcomes x of a process are distributed over the interval $[x_{\min}, x_{\max}]$ and that their likelihood is described by a probability density function (PDF) $f(x)$ satisfying the following two conditions:

$$f(x) \geq 0 \quad \forall x \in [x_{\min}, x_{\max}] , \quad (3.1)$$

$$\int_{x_{\min}}^{x_{\max}} f(u) du = 1 . \quad (3.2)$$

Then the probability to draw a random value X between x and $x + dx$ is given by

$$\Pr(x \leq X \leq x + dx) = f(x) dx . \quad (3.3)$$

A proper sampling of $f(x)$ is the key feature of any Monte Carlo simulation. The *first* step – common to all the different Monte Carlo approaches – is the generation of

Figure 3.1: *Left-hand panel:* mapping of a random variable ξ between 0 and 1 to a value x using the CDF (inverse transform method). *Right-hand panel:* sampling of a value x from the PDF using a rejection technique. Green and red points indicate points that are selected or rejected, respectively (see text for explanation).

random variables ξ uniformly distributed in the interval $[0,1]$. Computationally, this is done by using “pseudo-random” number generators. These involve a seed and a call to a function that generates a long sequence of uncorrelated numbers. Particular attention needs to be taken that the random number generator is sufficiently good, in the sense that it creates sufficiently long streams of uncorrelated values (see a more detailed discussion in chapter 7 of Press 2007). In this thesis we adopt the `gsl_rng_ran3` algorithm of the GNU Scientific Library (GSL). The *second* step involves the mapping of each random number ξ to a value x in the interval $[x_{\min}, x_{\max}]$, which can be done in a number of ways. In the following, we outline the two approaches used in this thesis.

The first approach – usually referred to as the *inverse transform method* – involves the use of the cumulative distribution function (CDF)

$$F(x) = \Pr(x_{\min} \leq X \leq x) = \int_{x_{\min}}^x f(u) du . \quad (3.4)$$

This function expresses the probability of drawing a value X smaller than x from the PDF. Given that $F(x_{\min}) = 0$ and $F(x_{\max}) = 1$, $F(x)$ can be regarded as a uniform distribution over the interval $[0,1]$. Therefore

$$\xi = F(x) = \int_{x_{\min}}^x f(u) du \quad (3.5)$$

specifies a mapping from a random number $\xi \in [0, 1]$ to a particular value x , provided that F can be inverted analytically

$$x = F^{-1}(\xi) , \quad (3.6)$$

or the integral in Eq. (3.5) can be solved numerically. For instance, consider the problem of generating a random radial position r inside a sphere of radius R . Using Eq. (3.5) and Eq. (3.6) with the PDF

$$f(u) = \frac{4\pi u^2}{\frac{4}{3}\pi R^3} \quad (3.7)$$

we obtain the following relationship

$$r = R\sqrt[3]{\xi} . \quad (3.8)$$

The latter can be used to properly convert the random numbers ξ – uniformly generated between 0 and 1 – into a radial position r . This mapping is illustrated in the left panel of Fig. 3.1, where $x_{\min} = 0$ and $x_{\max} = R$.

The second approach – commonly referred to as *rejection method* – is particularly useful when the CDF of Eq. (3.5) can not be either inverted analytically or integrated numerically. In such cases the random numbers are sampled directly from the PDF using a “hit and miss” approach. First a random number $\xi_1 \in [0, 1]$ is mapped to a value x in the interval $[x_{\min}, x_{\max}]$ as

$$x = \xi_1 (x_{\max} - x_{\min}) + x_{\min} . \quad (3.9)$$

Then a second random number, ξ_2 , is drawn and used to select a value y between 0 and the maximum of the PDF, f_{\max} :

$$y = \xi_2 f_{\max} . \quad (3.10)$$

If $y \leq f(x)$, x is selected. Otherwise, a new pair of random variables (ξ_1, ξ_2) is drawn until the above condition is satisfied. This procedure – relying on a simple geometric argument – is illustrated in the right panel of Fig. 3.1 for a Gaussian function.

3.2 Monte Carlo radiative transfer

Radiative transfer calculations describe the propagation of radiation through a medium where scattering, absorption and emission processes can occur. Under special conditions (e.g. plane-parallel or spherical geometries), the equations governing the radiative transfer can be solved analytically (Chandrasekhar 1960). In most cases, however, the

modelled media are too complex and numerical approaches are required. Among different techniques, Monte Carlo methods have proven to be well-suited for this purpose and have thus been widely used in the astrophysical context (see e.g. Auer 1968; Abbott & Lucy 1985; Mazzali & Lucy 1993; Wood et al. 1996; Long & Knigge 2002; Ercolano et al. 2003; Sim 2005; Harries 2000, 2011; Robitaille 2011). First, they are relatively simple to implement and less likely to be affected by numerical errors (Auer 2003). Second, they can easily address complex geometries and multi-dimensionality as all the interaction processes are treated locally. Finally, Monte Carlo calculations parallelise well and can thus be carried out on massive super-computers (see e.g. Rosenthal 2000).

In the following we outline the Monte Carlo scheme used in this thesis for modelling radiative transfer in SNe. In particular, we describe the main operation properties of our code and introduce quantities that are relevant for the polarisation discussion of Section 3.3. A more detailed description will be given in Chapter 4 when we discuss our multi-dimensional radiative transfer code ARTIS (Kromer & Sim 2009). Our approach is closely based on that described in a series of papers by Leon Lucy (e.g. Lucy 1999a,b, 2002, 2003, 2005) and implemented by (Sim 2007; Kromer & Sim 2009).

3.2.1 Rest frame and comoving frame

The radiative transfer problem is solved by simulating the propagation of photon packets through an expanding medium (see below). In general, the radiative transfer calculations are performed in the rest frame (rf, quantities denoted unprimed), while interactions with matter are treated in the comoving frame (cmf, primed quantities). Following photon packets as they make their way across the ejecta thus requires to transform their properties from rf to cmf each time an interaction with matter occurs. In particular, the direction of propagation \mathbf{n} can be transformed to

$$\mathbf{n}' = \frac{\left[\mathbf{n} - \frac{\mathbf{v}}{c} \left(\gamma - \frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma+1} \frac{\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{v}}{c} \right) \right]}{\gamma \left(1 - \frac{\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{v}}{c} \right)}, \quad (3.11)$$

following Castor (1972), while the frequency ν converted to ν' according to the Doppler formula

$$\nu' = \nu \gamma \left(1 - \frac{\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{v}}{c} \right), \quad (3.12)$$

where \mathbf{v} is the local velocity of the ejecta, c the speed of light and γ the Lorentz factor.

3.2.2 Main assumptions

Two important assumptions are made in our code. First, our calculations assume *homologous expansion* at all epochs, which means that the kinetic motion of the ejecta is the dominant contribution to the energy density of the system (i.e. free expansion). Under this approximation, the velocity v of the ejecta at a given time t is proportional to the radial position r :

$$\mathbf{v} = v \hat{\mathbf{r}} = \frac{r}{t} \hat{\mathbf{r}} . \quad (3.13)$$

While in free expansion, photons are also continuously red-shifted in frequency in the cmf. This can be demonstrated by differentiating the Doppler formula in Eq. (3.12) along the photon path length s :

$$\frac{dv'}{ds} = v \left[\frac{d\gamma}{ds} \left(1 - \frac{\mu v}{c} \right) - \frac{\gamma}{c} \frac{d(\mu v)}{ds} \right] , \quad (3.14)$$

where μ is the cosine of the angle between s and the radial direction. The two derivatives in square brackets can be easily calculated in homologous expansion (see e.g. Jeffery 1995) to give

$$\frac{d\gamma}{ds} = \frac{\gamma^3 v}{c^2 t} \left(\mu - \frac{v}{c} \right) \quad (3.15)$$

and

$$\frac{d(\mu v)}{ds} = \frac{c - \mu v}{c^2 t} . \quad (3.16)$$

Substituting Eqs. (3.15) and (3.16) in Eq. (3.14) we obtain

$$\frac{dv'}{ds} = -\frac{v\gamma^3}{ct} \left(1 - \frac{\mu v}{c} \right)^2 < 0 , \quad (3.17)$$

proving that the cmf frequency ν' is continuously redshifted as the packet moves throughout the ejecta. The free-expansion phase of the ejecta is predicted to start around 10 s after explosion in SNe Ia (e.g. Röpke 2005), thus providing an excellent approximation at 2 d post-explosion, when our calculations are usually initiated.

The second major assumption we make is the so-called *Sobolev approximation* (Sobolev 1960), which posits that the interaction of a photon with each line occurs at a single point along its trajectory through the ejecta. This approximation is valid provided that the macroscopic properties of the ejecta do not vary significantly within the line interaction region Δs . In the simple case where $\gamma = 1$ and $\mu = 1$, the interaction region can be easily estimated from Eq. (3.14) as

$$\Delta s = \left| -c \frac{\Delta \nu' / \nu}{d\nu'/ds} \right| = \left| -\frac{v_{\text{th}}}{dv'/ds} \right| , \quad (3.18)$$

where v_{th} is the thermal Doppler width of the line. Eq. (3.18) shows that the Sobolev approximation is well justified in the presence of large velocity gradients dv/ds . If we introduce a characteristic velocity, v_0 , and a characteristic length, s_0 , over which the macroscopic properties of the ejecta change, Eq. (3.18) can be rewritten as

$$\Delta s = \frac{v_{\text{th}}}{v_0} s_0 . \quad (3.19)$$

The Sobolev approximation ($\Delta s \ll s_0$) is well justified in SN Ia ejecta as the typical Doppler width of spectral lines ($v_{\text{th}} \sim 5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) is much smaller than the expansion velocities ($v_0 \sim 10\,000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$). When combined with the assumption of homologous expansion, the Sobolev approximation leads to a great simplification in handling line opacities. Indeed, the possibility to interact with a large number of spectral lines is easily addressed since photons are continuously red-shifting in frequency on their way through the expanding ejecta (see Eq. 3.17) and thus encounter each line sequentially and only once.

3.2.3 Creating and initialising Monte Carlo quanta

Following Abbott & Lucy (1985) and Lucy (1999a), we discretise the radiation field in Monte Carlo quanta each representing an ensemble of indivisible and identical photons. Every Monte Carlo packet is generated at a specific position (randomly selected according to the modelled source of radiation, see e.g. Section 4.1) and assigned initial energy ϵ'_i and frequency ν'_i . A random initial direction $\mathbf{n}'_i = (\sin \theta \cos \varphi, \sin \theta \sin \varphi, \cos \theta)$ is then given to each packet assuming isotropic emission. Specifically, we independently draw two random numbers ξ_1 and ξ_2 from a uniform distribution over the interval $[0,1]$ and select θ and φ according to

$$\cos \theta = 2\xi_1 - 1 \quad (3.20)$$

and

$$\varphi = 2\pi\xi_2 . \quad (3.21)$$

The latter equations are derived inverting Eq. (3.5) with the appropriate PDFs $f(\theta) = \sin \theta/2$ and $f(\varphi) = 1/2\pi$, respectively.

3.2.4 Propagating Monte Carlo quanta

The propagation of the Monte Carlo quanta is followed in the rf. Therefore we first transform \mathbf{n}'_i to \mathbf{n}_i and ν'_i to ν_i using Eq. (3.11) and Eq. (3.12) with $\mathbf{v} \rightarrow -\mathbf{v}$. Once launched in the computational domain, the Monte Carlo packet travels until it interacts with matter. How far a packet can travel before interacting is determined by sampling

an optical depth τ_r from the PDF $f(\tau) = e^{-\tau}$. In particular, substituting the latter in Eq. (3.5) we find

$$\xi_1 = 1 - e^{-\tau_r}, \quad \xi_1 \in [0, 1) \quad (3.22)$$

which can be easily inverted to obtain

$$\tau_r = -\ln(1 - \xi_1), \quad \xi_1 \in [0, 1) . \quad (3.23)$$

The code accounts for line opacity (treated in the Sobolev approximation, see Section 3.2.2) and continuum opacity due to electron scattering, bound-free and free-free absorption. Exploiting the method outlined by Mazzali & Lucy (1993), we use the randomly sampled optical depth τ_r to determine the physical path length travelled by the packet and whether the latter experiences a continuum or a line interaction. As shown in Fig. 3.2, we first calculate the trajectory point \mathbf{r}^* at which the packet interacts with the next spectral line (using the Sobolev approximation, see Section 3.2.2). Secondly, we determine the continuum optical depth accumulated up to that point as

$$\tau_{\text{cont}}^* = \int k_{\text{cont}} \rho ds , \quad (3.24)$$

where k_{cont} is the continuum attenuation coefficient (in $\text{cm}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$ units), ρ the local density and the integral is performed over the path length s between the starting point \mathbf{r} and \mathbf{r}^* . If (i) the continuum opacity is greater than the random optical depth ($\tau_{\text{cont}}^* > \tau_r$), a continuum event is selected and the path length calculated inverting

$$\tau_r = \int k_{\text{cont}} \rho ds . \quad (3.25)$$

In this case, we also draw a random number ξ_2 to choose which specific continuum interaction occurs. We take this event to be an electron scattering when $\xi_2 < k_{\text{sc}}/k_{\text{cont}}$ – where k_{sc} denotes the scattering attenuation coefficient – or a continuum absorption (bound-free or free-free) otherwise. If instead (ii) the sum of continuum and line opacity is greater than the random optical depth ($\tau_{\text{cont}}^* + \tau_{\text{sob}} > \tau_r$), the packet is moved to the Sobolev point \mathbf{r}^* and a line event occurs. Otherwise, (iii) we move the packet to \mathbf{r}^* and repeat the process for the next spectral line.

Upon moving the packet to the interaction point, we first transform its properties from rf to cmf (Eqs. 3.11 and 3.12) and then update them according to the specific event selected. In an electron scattering event, the Monte Carlo packet is assigned a new direction of propagation according to the scattering angles Θ and Φ selected. In the case of unpolarised radiation (cf. with Section 3.3.2), the former is chosen by

Figure 3.2: Procedure to choose whether a continuum or a line event occurs during the propagation of a photon packet (Mazzali & Lucy 1993). See text for explanation.

sampling the Rayleigh scattering function

$$f(\Theta) = \frac{3}{4}(\cos^2 \Theta + 1) \quad (3.26)$$

using a rejection technique and the latter as

$$\Phi = 2\pi\xi, \quad \xi \in [0, 1] . \quad (3.27)$$

For all other interactions (bound-bound, bound-free and free-free absorption), the packet is re-emitted in a random direction (i.e. we assume isotropic emission, see discussion in Section 2.2.2).

3.3 Including polarisation

Before addressing the question of how to extract synthetic observables from our simulations (Section 3.4), here we describe the implementation of polarisation in our radiative transfer code. In Section 3.3.1 we introduce the reference frame to which the polarisation Stokes vectors are defined. Then, in Section 3.3.2, we describe how the polarisation vectors are assigned to each Monte Carlo packet and how these are transformed following interaction with matter. Our polarisation scheme adopts a method similar to that introduced by Chandrasekhar (1960) and discussed in terms of a Monte

Figure 3.3: The meridian plane coordinate system adopted in the Monte Carlo code. The Stokes vector is defined in the plane orthogonal to the direction of propagation, \mathbf{n} . As described in Section 2.1, Q is defined as the intensity difference between two perpendicular reference axes, \mathbf{l} and \mathbf{r} , whereas U is the equivalent difference with \mathbf{l} and \mathbf{r} counter-clockwise rotated by 45 degrees (viewed antiparallel to \mathbf{n}).

Carlo implementation by Code & Whitney (1995), Whitney (2011) and Kasen et al. (2006).

3.3.1 Reference frame

Linear polarisation is introduced in our code by assigning a Stokes vector $\mathbf{S} = (I, Q, U)$ to each Monte Carlo packet. As discussed in Section 2.1, the definition of the Stokes vector is relative to a pair of reference axes \mathbf{l} and \mathbf{r} determined in the plane orthogonal to the direction of propagation \mathbf{n} (i.e. the plane in which the electromagnetic wave oscillates). Although these reference axes need to be perpendicular to each other, their specific orientations on the plane they define is arbitrary. Therefore, this offers us a degree of freedom in selecting the reference frame. In line with previous studies (e.g. Chandrasekhar 1960; Code & Whitney 1995; Kasen et al. 2006), we choose the two reference axes so that \mathbf{l} lies in the meridian plane (plane defined by \mathbf{n} and the polar axis z) and $\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{l}$ (see Fig. 3.3). With this convention, Q is defined as the difference between intensity I_l with electric field oscillating along \mathbf{l} and intensity I_r with electric

field oscillating along \mathbf{r} ; U is the equivalent difference in intensities with the reference axes \mathbf{l} and \mathbf{r} counter-clockwise rotated by 45 degrees (as viewed looking antiparallel to \mathbf{n}) to give

$$\mathbf{a} = \frac{\mathbf{l} - \mathbf{r}}{\sqrt{2}} \quad , \quad \mathbf{b} = \frac{\mathbf{l} + \mathbf{r}}{\sqrt{2}} \quad . \quad (3.28)$$

The resulting Stokes vector \mathbf{S} is then expressed as

$$\mathbf{S} = \begin{pmatrix} I \\ Q \\ U \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} I_l + I_r \\ I_l - I_r \\ I_a - I_b \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \updownarrow + \leftrightarrow \\ \updownarrow - \leftrightarrow \\ \nearrow - \nwarrow \end{pmatrix} \quad , \quad (3.29)$$

while the orientation of the net electric field (see Fig. 2.1 with $\gamma = 0$) is described by the unit vector

$$\hat{\mathbf{e}} = (\cos\chi) \mathbf{l} - (\sin\chi) \mathbf{r} \quad . \quad (3.30)$$

For instance, a Monte Carlo packet with $\mathbf{S} = (I, I, 0)$ is associated with a polarisation angle $\chi = 0$ (see Eq. 2.20) and thus describes an electric field oscillating along $\hat{\mathbf{e}} = \mathbf{l}$; a packet with $\mathbf{S} = (I, 0, I)$ is instead associated with $\chi = \pi/4$ and thus with an electric field oscillating along $\hat{\mathbf{e}} = \mathbf{a}$.

3.3.2 Creating and propagating polarised packets

At the time they are created (see Section 3.2.3), Monte Carlo packets are assigned a dimensionless Stokes vector \mathbf{s}_0 and assumed to be unpolarised, that is $\mathbf{s}_0 = (1, 0, 0)$. During the radiative transfer calculation, the Stokes parameters of the packet remain unchanged while travelling through the ejecta and can only be altered by interactions with matter.

When an interaction occurs, we first transform the incoming Stokes vector \mathbf{s}_i in the rf to \mathbf{s}'_i in the cmf. This is done through the following sequence of steps: (a) we calculate the polarisation angle χ_i from the incoming Stokes vector \mathbf{s}_i ; (b) we derive the orientation of the electric field in the rf, $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_i$, using Eq. (3.30); (c) we transform $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_i$ to $\hat{\mathbf{e}}'_i$ using the Lorentz transformation

$$\hat{\mathbf{e}}'_i = \hat{\mathbf{e}}_{i,\parallel} + \gamma \left[\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{i,\perp} + \mathbf{v} \times (\mathbf{n}_i \times \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i) \right] \quad , \quad (3.31)$$

where \mathbf{n}_i is the incoming direction of the packet, and $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{i,\parallel}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{i,\perp}$ the components of $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_i$ parallel and perpendicular to the velocity \mathbf{v} , respectively; (d) we determine the cmf reference axes \mathbf{l}' and \mathbf{r}' from the aberrated direction of propagation \mathbf{n}'_i (Eq. 3.11) and calculate the polarisation angle χ'_i between $\hat{\mathbf{e}}'_i$ and \mathbf{l}' (Eq. 3.30); (e) we finally compute the Stokes vector \mathbf{s}'_i from χ'_i and making use of the fact that the polarisation p_i is Lorentz

Figure 3.4: The geometry adopted for electron scattering in the coordinate system introduced by Chandrasekhar (1960) with the additional reference axes \mathbf{l}'_i and \mathbf{l}'_f defined in the text. A packet moving along \mathbf{n}'_i is scattered through an angle Θ to a new direction \mathbf{n}'_f . The reference axis \mathbf{l}'_i (and accordingly the Stokes vector) are rotated through an angle i_1 into the scattering plane (in red) and through an angle i_2 after scattering.

invariant (Cocke & Holm 1972). This transformation procedure is summarised as

$$\mathbf{s}_i \xrightarrow{(a)} \chi_i \xrightarrow{(b)} \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i \xrightarrow{(c)} \hat{\mathbf{e}}' \xrightarrow{(d)} \chi'_i \xrightarrow{(e)} \mathbf{s}'_i . \quad (3.32)$$

Following transformation to the cmf, the Stokes parameters can be updated in accordance with the physical interaction that occurs. For *bound-bound*, *bound-free* and *free-free* absorptions, the packet is assumed to retain no information on polarisation (see discussion in Sections 2.2.1 and 2.2.2) and is reemitted in a random direction with zero polarisation:

$$q'_f = 0 \quad u'_f = 0 . \quad (3.33)$$

If instead the packet undergoes *electron scattering*, a scattering angle Θ is properly sampled (see below), a new direction \mathbf{n}'_f is computed and the Stokes vector is transformed via the scattering matrix $A_{es}(\Theta)$ in Eq. (2.31). After applying the scattering matrix, the dimensionless Stokes vector is normalised so that its first component is equal to 1. As shown in Fig. 3.4, since $A_{es}(\Theta)$ is defined in the scattering plane, the

Stokes vector is first rotated into this plane and then rotated back to the meridian frame after the scattering matrix $A_{\text{es}}(\Theta)$ has been applied, i.e.

$$\mathbf{s}'_f = R(\pi - i_2) A_{\text{es}}(\Theta) R(-i_1) \mathbf{s}'_i, \quad (3.34)$$

where

$$R(\phi) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos 2\phi & \sin 2\phi \\ 0 & -\sin 2\phi & \cos 2\phi \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.35)$$

is the matrix to rotate the Stokes vector by an angle ϕ clockwise when facing the source. The rotation angles i_1 and i_2 are computed with the convention that $q' = 1$ represents an electric field oscillating in the scattering plane. Following Code & Whitney (1995), the scattering angle Θ is chosen by sampling the PDF

$$f(\Theta, i_1, \mathbf{s}'_i) = \frac{3}{4} \left[(\cos^2 \Theta + 1) + (\cos^2 \Theta - 1)(q'_i \cos 2i_1 - u'_i \sin 2i_1) \right] \quad (3.36)$$

from Eq. (3.34) and using a rejection technique (see Section 3.1). Note that Eq. (3.36) provides a generalization of the scattering function in Eq. (3.26) for polarising radiation.

Finally the procedure summarised by Eq. (3.32) is inverted (with $\mathbf{v} \rightarrow -\mathbf{v}$) and used to transform the outgoing Stokes vector in the cmf, \mathbf{s}'_f , to the rf, \mathbf{s}_f .

3.4 Spectrum extraction techniques

The main drawback of Monte Carlo methods is their stochastic nature, which leads to solutions that are affected by Monte Carlo noise. In order to distinguish intrinsic signals from statistical noise in the extracted observables, one needs to track a sufficiently large number of Monte Carlo quanta. However, while the computational time is directly proportional to the number of packets, the signal-to-noise ratio increases with the square root of the number of packets. The computational power required to achieve a sufficiently good signal-to-noise in the observables can thus become prohibitive even on massive super-computers, particularly when we want to extract very weak signals (e.g. polarisation) from the simulations. Therefore, it is important to attempt to optimise Monte Carlo methods. In the following we discuss three different extraction techniques, with the aim of selecting the most suitable to synthesise observables with low Monte Carlo noise. In Section 3.4.1 we present a simple direct counting approach, while in Section 3.4.2 and 3.4.3 we explore alternative techniques.

3.4.1 Direct counting technique

In the Direct Counting Technique (DCT), Monte Carlo quanta are followed along their trajectories and their Stokes parameters updated at each interaction, following the procedure outlined in Section 3.3. Packets that reach the outer boundary of the computational domain are collected in bins according to their final direction \mathbf{n} and frequency ν and the resulting spectra are computed as

$$\begin{pmatrix} I \\ Q \\ U \end{pmatrix} = \sum \frac{\epsilon}{\Delta t \Delta \nu 4\pi r^2} \mathbf{s}_f, \quad (3.37)$$

where \mathbf{s}_f is the dimensionless Stokes vector of the escaping packet, ϵ its rf energy, r the distance of the observer from the system and the sum is performed over all the packets that escaped in the selected angular bin, time interval $[t - \Delta t/2, t + \Delta t/2]$ and frequency range $[\nu - \Delta \nu/2, \nu + \Delta \nu/2]$. We note that I , Q and U in Eq. (3.37) have the dimensions of a flux.

The direct counting approach provides a simple way of computing polarisation spectra for different viewing angles, i.e. for different observers. However, the need to average contributions from packets that escape in the same angular bin but with different angles inevitably leads to an approximate result: if the number of angular bins is too small, summing contributions from different angles will produce a poor estimate of the observables seen by a single observer orientation; if instead too many angular bins are used, the number of packets escaping per bin becomes small, leading to high Monte Carlo noise.

3.4.2 Event based technique

In this approach (Event-Based Technique, EBT) we still follow the propagation of Monte Carlo packets exactly as before. However, whenever a packet interaction occurs the propagation is suspended, and a “virtual” packet (Kerzendorf & Sim 2014) is created and handled as described below. Once the “virtual” packet calculation is completed, the propagation of the original packet is resumed and this process repeated for every following interaction. This approach is similar to, and inspired by, that used by Yusef-Zadeh et al. (1984, see also Robitaille 2011), Knigge et al. (1995) and Long & Knigge (2002). Following the notation introduced by Lucy (2002), hereafter we will refer to the original Monte Carlo packets as r -packets (monochromatic packets of ultraviolet-optical-infrared radiation) and to the “virtual” packets as v -packets (see also Section 4.1).

Figure 3.5: Sketches of the principle behind the EBT (left panel) and the TBT (right panel). EBT: for every interaction of the r -packet, a v -packet is created and sent directly to a specific observer. Its Stokes parameters are treated in accordance with the specific interaction and are added as contributions to the emergent spectrum. TBT: contributions in the TBT come not only from trajectories that are terminated by physical interactions of the r -packet (as in the EBT, black points) but also from those terminated by numerical events (r -packets crossing boundaries, white points). The arc segment represents the outer boundary of the computational domain.

When a v -packet is created, it is always launched in the direction of a selected observer, \mathbf{n}_{obs} , and has cmf frequency and energy set equal to those of the r -packet at the point of creation (see left-hand panel of Fig. 3.5). Since the v -packet is forced to go to the observer, the scattering angle is now not determined by sampling either an isotropic distribution (bound-bound, bound-free and free-free absorption) or Eq. (3.36, electron scattering), but rather calculated as

$$\cos \Theta = \mathbf{n}'_{\text{in}} \cdot \mathbf{n}'_{\text{obs}} . \quad (3.38)$$

The Stokes parameters, initially set equal to those of the incoming r -packet, are transformed in accordance with the physical process selected for the r -packet. If the r -packet is scattered by an electron, the cmf Stokes vector of the v -packet is transformed according to Eq. (3.34), with the scattering angle Θ determined by Eq. (3.38). If instead a new r -packet is created from a line, bound-free or free-free absorption, we create an unpolarised v -packet (see Sections 2.2.1 and 2.2.2).

Once created and assigned a rf frequency, a rf energy (ϵ), a direction of propagation and a Stokes vector (\mathbf{s}_f), the ν -packet is propagated through the ejecta towards the observer and it is interpreted as a contribution to a bin in the emergent spectrum. Specifically, the flux (I) and polarisation (Q and U) spectra in a given frequency bin $[\nu - \Delta\nu/2, \nu + \Delta\nu/2]$ and time interval $[t - \Delta t/2, t + \Delta t/2]$ can be expressed as

$$\begin{pmatrix} I \\ Q \\ U \end{pmatrix} = \sum \frac{\epsilon}{\Delta t \Delta \nu r^2} \mathbf{s}_f \cdot \left(\frac{d\text{Pr}}{d\Omega} \Big|_{\text{EBT}} e^{-\tau_{\text{esc}}} \right), \quad (3.39)$$

where the sum is performed over all the ν -packets escaping in the selected frequency and time bins, r is the distance of the observer from the system and the two terms inside parentheses are weighting factors accounting for the probability that the ν -packet could reach the observer. Because the ν -packet is forced to go to the observer, we first account for the probability per unit solid angle associated with the chosen direction, that is:

$$\frac{d\text{Pr}}{d\Omega} \Big|_{\text{EBT}} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{4\pi} & \text{bound-bound, bound-free, free-free absorption} \\ \frac{1}{4\pi} f(\Theta, i_1) & \text{electron scattering} \end{cases}. \quad (3.40)$$

The exponential factor in Eq. (3.39) accounts for the probability that the ν -packet could reach the observer without further interactions, with the optical depth to the boundary, τ_{esc} , computed as

$$\tau_{\text{esc}} = \tau_{\text{cont}} + \sum \tau_{\text{sob}}. \quad (3.41)$$

Here the sum is performed over all the line opacities (τ_{sob}) encountered by the ν -packet on its trajectory to the boundary and the continuum opacity, τ_{cont} , is computed as an integral of the continuum attenuation coefficient, k_{cont} , over trajectory length:

$$\tau_{\text{cont}} = \int k_{\text{cont}} \rho ds, \quad (3.42)$$

The advantage of the ν -packet technique is that it allows us to compute spectra and light curves for any specific viewing angle, avoiding the need to average contributions from different angles in the same bin. Unlike in the direct counting approach, where an r -packet makes a single contribution to the emergent spectrum, the final spectra in the EBT also contain (appropriately weighted) information derived from every interaction that the r -packet undergoes (see left-hand panel of Fig. 3.5). For these reasons, we expect this technique to produce spectra and light curves with lower Monte Carlo noise. However, the need of creating and handling ν -packets introduces a computa-

tional overhead that could make the EBT less efficient than the DCT. Such possibilities are explored quantitatively in Section 3.5.2.

3.4.3 Trajectory based technique

In the EBT described above, we used all the r -packets to provide us with an ensemble of physical events, and then for each event in the ensemble we computed the probability of it giving rise to a photon escaping to the observer. In the third technique (Trajectory-Based Technique, TBT) we instead obtain from the r -packets an ensemble of packet trajectories, which can be taken as a discrete representation of the radiation field in the simulation. We can then estimate observables by summing over this ensemble of trajectories, computing for each the probability that interactions of radiation on that path could have given rise to photons escaping to the observer.

This summation is achieved by generating a v -packet for each trajectory path Δl (including those terminated by numerical events, e.g. packets crossing grid cell boundaries) and sending it towards the observer at \mathbf{n}_{obs} (see right-hand panel of Fig. 3.5). The v -packet contribution to the emergent spectrum is first weighted by the probability per unit solid angle ($d\text{Pr}/d\Omega|_{\text{TBT}}$) that photons on the path Δl could have undergone an interaction that gave rise to re-emission/scattering towards the observer. As with the EBT, we must also account for the probability of any scattered/emitted radiation reaching the observer via a suitable mean exponential factor, $\langle e^{-\tau_{\text{esc}}} \rangle$. Thus, in the TBT, we compute synthetic observables via

$$\begin{pmatrix} I \\ Q \\ U \end{pmatrix} = \sum \frac{\epsilon}{\Delta t \Delta v r^2} \mathbf{s}_f \cdot \left(\frac{d\text{Pr}}{d\Omega} \Big|_{\text{TBT}} \langle e^{-\tau_{\text{esc}}} \rangle \right), \quad (3.43)$$

where the summation is again over v -packets in the selected frequency and time bins. Formally, the exponential weight factor of a v -packet in the TBT should be computed as

$$\langle e^{-\tau_{\text{esc}}} \rangle = \frac{\int_l^{l+\Delta l} e^{-\tau_{\text{esc}}(l')} dl'}{\Delta l}, \quad (3.44)$$

where the integral runs over the trajectory path Δl . To first order, however, this can be approximated by generating the v -packet at the mid point of Δl and computing the exponential factor from its flight (as described in Section 3.4.2); i.e.

$$\langle e^{-\tau_{\text{esc}}} \rangle = e^{-\tau_{\text{esc}}(l+\Delta l/2)}. \quad (3.45)$$

In principle, $d\text{Pr}/d\Omega|_{TBT}$ can be formulated to account for all (effective) scattering/fluorescence processes. However, since we are primarily interested in studying contributions to the emergent polarisation spectrum, we focus only on electron scattering, for which

$$\left. \frac{d\text{Pr}}{d\Omega} \right|_{TBT} = \frac{1}{4\pi} f(\Theta, i_1, \mathbf{s}'_1) k_{sc} \Delta l . \quad (3.46)$$

A key difference between the EBT and the TBT is that, in the latter, every trajectory element of the r -packets contributes to the synthetic observables, whereas, in the former, only physical interaction events contribute. For instance, in the limit of optically thin ejecta many more v -packets would contribute to the emergent spectrum in the TBT compared to the EBT (see Fig. 3.5). However, a drawback of the TBT is that $\tau_{\text{esc}}(l + \Delta l/2)$ should describe the mean probability of escape for points along the trajectory element (see Eq. 3.45), rather than the exact probability of escape from the interaction point, as in the EBT. For an r -packet trajectory with moderate optical depth ($\tau \gtrsim 1$), this approximation may lead to a poor estimate of the observables. Breaking the trajectory into smaller paths (with $\Delta\tau \ll 1$) and generating v -packets at each midpoint may be required, slowing down the code and making the TBT less efficient than the EBT (see Section 3.5.2).

3.5 Test code

In the following we present a simple test code, with the aim of validating our polarisation scheme (Section 3.5.1) and selecting the most suitable of the techniques described in Section 3.4 to synthesise spectra with low Monte Carlo noise (Section 3.5.2). In this code, packets are generated with null polarisation in a small inner sphere (to mimic a point source) and then allowed to propagate into an envelope where either interactions with electrons or continuum absorptions can occur. Here time evolution for the ejecta is neglected.

3.5.1 Polarisation scheme validation

To validate the polarisation scheme, we first focus our attention on the DCT and choose to reproduce a simple configuration described by Hillier (1994): as shown in Fig. 3.6, a point source is surrounded by a detached spherical shell with a dimensionless inner radius $R_{\text{min}} = 2.0$ and outer radius $R_{\text{max}} = 30.0 R_{\text{min}}$, with a prolate density distribution

Figure 3.6: The geometry adopted by Hillier (1994) and used for our test calculations. Monte Carlo quanta are created inside a spherical shell of radius R_{\min} , propagate into a region with a prolate density distribution and are free to escape when they reach the outer spherical shell at $R_{\max} = 30.0R_{\min}$. $N_e(r, \beta)$ is the electron density distribution and $N_{e0} = N_e(R_{\min}, 0)$.

$N_e(r, \beta)$ such that

$$\sigma_e N_e(r, \beta) = \chi_0 \left(\frac{R_{\min}}{r} \right)^2 (1 + 10 \cos^2 \beta) , \quad (3.47)$$

where σ_e is the Thomson cross section and r and β express the radius and the polar angle inside the envelope. The χ_0 parameter is related to the solid-angle averaged (from inner to outer boundary) optical depth, $\tau_{\text{ave}} = 2.888\chi_0$, and can be varied to investigate the impact of different scattering optical depth on the polarisation signal. Neglecting absorption and assuming a pure electron scattering envelope, the continuum polarisation as a function of χ_0 is shown in Fig. 3.7 for four different viewing angles i (22.5° , 45° , 67.5° and 90°). The agreement between our predicted values and the expected curves from Hillier (1994) is encouraging. We also carried out calculations in which we include continuum absorption opacity. These show good agreement with the predicted dependence of the continuum polarisation on the albedo (ratio of the scattering to the total opacity, see Fig. 3.8).

Figure 3.7: Continuum polarisation as a function of χ_0 and τ_{ave} for 4 different viewing angles for the setup described in Section 3.5.1. Symbols indicate predictions from our test calculations, while the lines are reported from Hillier (1994) for comparison. The Monte Carlo noise error bars are not shown since they are smaller than the symbol sizes.

3.5.2 Comparison between different techniques

A convenient means to compare the three techniques for extracting observables outlined in Section 3.4 is by studying their accuracy in reproducing continuum polarisation for a given configuration. We did this by repeatedly running our test code a number ($N_{\text{sim}} = 500$) of times for each technique (with different random number seeds determined by the wall-clock time) and comparing the distributions of polarisation values obtained using each method. For these experiments, we chose a configuration in which a point source illuminates a surrounding atmosphere, chosen to be a constant density oblate ellipsoid with axis ratio of two, i.e.

$$\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} + \frac{z^2}{c^2} = 1, \quad a = b = 2c. \quad (3.48)$$

Figure 3.8: Continuum polarisation as a function of the albedo (black points) for the setup described in Section 3.5.1, together with the predicted curve (dashed line) from Hillier (1994). Here the observer inclination is 90° and $\chi_0 = 1$. The Monte Carlo noise error bars are not shown since they are smaller than the symbol sizes.

In all the simulations, 10^6 packets have been created, a pure scattering atmosphere has been assumed (i.e. no line opacity and albedo equal to 1) and the scattering coefficient has been set to $k_{\text{sc}} = 1/a$ and kept constant throughout the ejecta. As mentioned in Section 3.4.1, continuum polarisation levels estimated from the DCT may be either inaccurate or have large uncertainties depending on whether the number of angular bins is small or large, respectively. By repeating the calculations of Section 3.5.1 with different choices of the number of bins, we found that 51 angular bins provide a reasonable compromise and we therefore adopt this in the DCT calculations. The results of the comparison between the three techniques are reported in Table 3.1 and shown in Fig. 3.9 and Fig. 3.10.

For an observer along the y -axis (Fig. 3.9), the projection of the model along the line-of-sight is circular and we expect to find null polarisation. The Q and U values in every technique are indeed consistent with zero but, because of Monte Carlo noise, a

Table 3.1: Average values and standard deviations of the distributions of q and u values predicted on 500 simulations by the DCT, EBT and TBT. The system is an oblate ellipsoid with axis ratio of two viewed along the z -axis (circular projection) and along the x -axis (elliptical projection). The averaged runtime, \bar{t} , is reported for each distribution.

Circular	$\bar{q} \pm \sigma_q$ (per cent)	$\bar{u} \pm \sigma_u$ (per cent)	\bar{t} (s)
DCT	0.16 ± 0.23	0.00 ± 0.24	3.9
EBT	0.00 ± 0.04	0.00 ± 0.04	22.3
TBT	0.00 ± 0.03	0.00 ± 0.03	123.0
Elliptical	$\bar{q} \pm \sigma_q$ (per cent)	$\bar{u} \pm \sigma_u$ (per cent)	\bar{t} (s)
DCT	3.81 ± 0.28	-0.02 ± 0.29	3.9
EBT	3.82 ± 0.04	0.00 ± 0.04	26.3
TBT	3.81 ± 0.03	0.00 ± 0.03	144.5

Figure 3.9: Q and U continuum polarisation distributions of $N_{sim} = 500$ runs with the DCT (top panels), the EBT (middle panels) and the TBT (lower panels). The adopted geometry is an oblate ellipsoid with axis ratio of two, as described in Section 3.5.2. The system is viewed along the minor axis, orientation for which the projection is circular. For each distribution, a solid vertical line indicates the average value, \bar{x} , and the grey shaded area marks \pm one standard deviation, σ . The average values and the standard deviations of each plot are reported in Table 3.1 together with the average runtimes, \bar{t} .

Figure 3.10: Same as Fig. 3.9, but with the oblate ellipsoid viewed along the major axis (elliptical projection).

distribution of values is obtained. The width of this distribution provides a convenient quantification of the Monte Carlo noise introduced by each method. As expected, the standard deviations obtained with the EBT and TBT methods are smaller than with the DCT method, by factors of ~ 6.6 and ~ 8.6 , respectively. Given that Monte Carlo noise is expected to scale with the square root of the number of packets, the DCT could reach the same signal-to-noise ratio as the EBT (TBT) with a factor of ~ 45 (~ 75) more packets. Although the v -packet routine introduces computational overheads in the EBT and TBT (see Table 3.1), the direct counting approach would still be a factor of ~ 7.5 (~ 2.5) slower than the v -packets technique. We also note that, even with the same signal-to-noise ratio, the DCT would be less accurate in predicting polarisation values because of the need to average contributions from different viewing angles (via angular binning): indeed, closer inspection shows that the Q distribution for the DCT is shifted towards positive values. In the binning approach contributions to the spectra come from r -packets escaping close to, but not exactly along, the z direction and thus the average value of Q is slightly positive.

If viewed down the x -axis (Fig. 3.10), the projection becomes an ellipse (as in the middle panel of Fig. 2.4) and thus we expect to see a polarisation signal. The three

techniques agree in reproducing a continuum polarisation of $p \sim 3.8$ per cent but, again, the DCT gives a much broader distribution of values, indicating that it is more severely affected by noise in the simulation. In order to reach the same standard error of the mean of the EBT (TBT), the DCT would require a factor of ~ 50 (~ 100) more packets, making the total runtime a factor of ~ 7.5 (~ 3) longer than the v -packets scheme.

This simple comparison shows that the v -packet approaches are more precise in estimating polarisation, allowing us to reach a given Monte Carlo noise with many fewer Monte Carlo quanta (and substantially shorter runtimes) than the simple DCT would require. As already anticipated in Section 3.4.3, the EBT is indeed more efficient than the TBT because the runtime for the latter is limited by the need of breaking r -packet trajectories with moderate optical depth ($\tau \gtrsim 1$) into smaller paths (with $\Delta\tau \ll 1$), in order to give accurate results for τ_{esc} . Specifically, for the calculations presented in this section, trajectories have been broken into path lengths with optical depth of the order of $\Delta\tau = 0.1$. We note that, although we have carried out polarisation tests here, this improvement in Monte Carlo noise could also be exploited for extracting high-quality observables of any sort (see e.g. Section 4.4).

Chapter 4

Implementing polarisation in ARTIS

“Scientific progress is the discovery of a more and more comprehensive simplicity...The previous successes give us confidence in the future of science: we become more and more conscious of the fact that the universe is cognizable.”

– Georges Edouard Lemaître

In this chapter we describe the implementation of our polarisation scheme (Chapter 3) into the 3D, time-dependent radiative transfer code `ARTIS`. After a brief overview of `ARTIS` (Section 4.1), we outline the implementation of polarisation in Section 4.2. In Section 4.3 we then comment on our choices of representing polarisation signals and estimating Monte Carlo noise levels in all the `ARTIS` calculations presented in this thesis. Finally, we test the new version of the code with simple models for SNe Ia: the one-dimensional W7 explosion (Section 4.4) and two-dimensional ellipsoidal models with SN Ia composition (Section 4.5). Part of the contents of this chapter has been published in the *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* journal (Bulla et al. 2015).

4.1 `ARTIS`

`ARTIS` (Applied Radiative Transfer In Supernovae) is a three-dimensional, time-dependent Monte Carlo radiative transfer code developed by Kromer & Sim (2009). The code is closely based on the approach proposed by Lucy (2002, 2003, 2005) and was developed as an extension to the grey-opacity radiative transfer code of Sim (2007). Assuming homologous expansion (Section 3.2.2), `ARTIS` simulates Monte Carlo radiation transport in SN Ia ejecta and is thus well-suited to calculate observables (light curves and spectra) for multi-dimensional hydrodynamic explosion models.

As already discussed in Section 3.2.3, the radiation field is discretised in Monte Carlo packets each representing an ensemble of indivisible and identical photons (Abbott & Lucy 1985; Lucy 1999a). In particular, `ARTIS` adopts the same prescription of Lucy (1999a) and Lucy (2005) and assumes that each Monte Carlo packet carries the same amount of energy during the simulation. That is, every packet keeps the same energy while travelling through the ejecta and, when interacting with matter, it is re-emitted with the same energy it had before interaction. Nevertheless, frequency redistribution is still allowed during interactions with matter and thus each Monte Carlo packet needs to be interpreted as representing a varying number of photons in the course of the simulation. A major advantage of this indivisible, equal energy packet formalism is that it provides the possibility to track each packet trajectory one-by-one. As each packet propagates independently from the other packets, a parallelisation scheme is implemented in `ARTIS` which allows for its use on massive super-computers. Packets are divided in groups and distributed to a number of multiple cores that independently perform their own calculation. 1024 cores are typically adopted for all the calculations presented in this thesis.

During the simulation, packets are named according to their energy content. Following Lucy (2002), r -packets and γ -packets refer to monochromatic packets of ultraviolet-optical-infrared radiation and of γ -rays, respectively. Instead, k -packets

and i -packets do not represent radiation but rather packets containing kinetic and internal energy, respectively. In this work we follow the same notation of Lucy (2002) and refer to the “virtual packets” introduced in Sections 3.4.2 and 3.4.3 as v -packets (see also Section 4.2).

As a first step, the code discretises the total radioactive energy available for a given SN model in indivisible, equal energy Monte Carlo quanta (see above). These are then placed in the model ejecta according to the distribution of ^{56}Ni . After sampling a decay transition from the $^{56}\text{Ni} \rightarrow ^{56}\text{Co} \rightarrow ^{56}\text{Fe}$ radioactive chain (Lucy 2005), each Monte Carlo quantum is transformed into a γ -packet with cmf photon energy and frequency assigned according to the specific γ -ray line selected. γ -packets then start to propagate and heat the ejecta via Compton scattering, photoelectric absorption and pair production. Under the assumption of radioactive equilibrium, the kinetic thermal energy acquired by the ejecta is immediately re-emitted (e.g. via free-free and free-bound processes) as ultraviolet-optical-infrared radiation. Fundamentally, this can be described as down-scattering of energetic γ -packets into r -packets via the creation of a k -packet. r -packets are then followed in their propagation throughout the ejecta and their properties updated upon interaction with matter. Once they leave the computation domain, the escaping r -packets are finally collected in different angular (see Section 3.4.1), time and frequency bins and used to generate viewing-angle dependent light curves and spectra. For a more extensive description of the code, we refer the reader to Sim (2007) and Kromer & Sim (2009).

ARTIS has been successfully applied to a number of multi-dimensional explosion models for SNe Ia: violent merger (Pakmor et al. 2010, 2012; Kromer et al. 2013), pure detonation (Sim et al. 2010; Marquardt et al. 2015), double-detonation (Kromer et al. 2010; Sim et al. 2012), delayed-detonation (Sim et al. 2013; Ohlmann et al. 2014; Seitenzahl et al. 2016) and deflagration (Kromer et al. 2013; Fink et al. 2014; Kromer et al. 2015) models. Predictions of light curves and spectra have allowed for a direct comparison of models to data (and each other), thus shaping the development of the SN Ia field on both theoretical and observational sides (see e.g. Hillebrandt et al. 2013, for a review).

4.2 Implementing polarisation

In this work, we have implemented polarisation into ARTIS by assigning a Stokes vector to each r -packet and by transforming this according to the physical process the packet undergoes (see Section 3.3). For the DCT, the same binning approach already used in the code for spectra and light curves is readily extended to compute polarisation spectra.

As mentioned in Section 3.4.3, the v -packet TBT should yield spectra with lower Monte Carlo noise for a given number of r -packets compared to the EBT since contributions to the polarisation spectra come from every event in the r -packet histories, including both physical interactions and numerical events (e.g. packets crossing grid cell boundaries). However, accurate results from the TBT require that care is taken in the calculation of τ_{esc} , which can introduce a large computational overhead for complicated opacity distributions. Indeed, our test calculations (Section 3.5.2) suggested that this additional computational overhead can ultimately make the TBT less efficient than the EBT. Consequently, we have chosen to implement a v -packet routine using the EBT that can be used to compute synthetic observables from ARTIS. Here we note that v -packets do not interfere with the propagation of r -packets and thus do not change the energy flow during the simulation.

The v -packet routine allows us to compute flux and polarisation spectra for multiple observers, simply by using a loop to generate v -packets over a set of different viewing angles. Several input parameters can be chosen to optimise performance in the calculations. First, the calculation of the optical depth τ_{esc} , see Eq. (3.41), can be stopped when the v -packet reaches a maximum value $\tau_{\text{esc}}^{\text{max}}$: v -packets with high optical depth to the boundary would make vanishingly small contributions to the final spectrum (because of the exponential factor, see Eq. 3.39) and can thus be neglected. Since the computation cost of the v -packet methods is dominated by the calculation of τ_{esc} , the runtime is strongly affected by this parameter. We have carried out test calculations to verify that setting $\tau_{\text{esc}}^{\text{max}} = 10$ and neglecting v -packets with higher optical depth does not affect the final result, and adopted this as our default value for all the calculations presented in this thesis. Our implementation also includes the option to generate v -packets only in a selected spectral interval. Because spectropolarimetric observations usually cover the optical region of the spectrum, our default wavelength range is 3500 – 10000 Å. Given that much of the runtime of the code can be consumed in computing τ_{esc} for packets in the bluer regions, which easily reach $\tau_{\text{esc}}^{\text{max}}$ because of strong iron-line blanketing, this particular cut in wavelength speeds up the calculations by a factor of ~ 4 compared to calculations with no wavelength cut. Finally, the v -packet routine can be switched on or off for timesteps as chosen by the user (note that the activation or deactivation of v -packets has no effect on the r -packet propagation).

4.3 Polarisation representation and Monte Carlo noise

Polarisation is sometimes represented in terms of the Stokes parameters Q and U , sometimes in terms of degree of polarisation P and polarisation angle χ . When dealing with low signal-to-noise levels, however, the former representation is usually preferred as

P is known to suffer from the so-called polarisation bias (see e.g. Patat & Romaniello 2006, and references therein). Specifically, every contribution to Q and U in our simulations will be distributed around the true value \bar{Q} and \bar{U} because of Monte Carlo noise fluctuations. In the presence of small signals, Q and U contributions can assume both positive and negative values. Given that the polarisation percentage P is defined positive, however, negative Q and U contributions will add only in the positive direction leading to a systematic overestimate of the true value \bar{P} . Therefore, in this work we will usually work in terms of the Stokes parameters as these do not suffer from the polarisation bias. We will, however, use P when comparing our models with data as the comparison is more straightforward in terms of absolute percentage levels and this representation has been widely used in previous studies.

Polarisation Q and U spectra extracted for symmetric explosion models (e.g. 1D models, see Section 4.4) are expected to be consistent with zero since every contribution to each Stokes parameter is cancelled by an orthogonal contribution one quadrant away. In contrast, aspherical geometries may lead to a polarisation signal that manifests in both Q and U . In such cases, we follow Leonard et al. (2001) and Wang et al. (2003) and for every observer we transform Q and U to a new set of Stokes parameters Q_{rot} and U_{rot} . Specifically, we first determine the dominant axis in the Q/U plane and identify the corresponding angle $\alpha_{\text{rot}} = 2\chi_{\text{rot}}$ (see Section 2.3.3). We then use Eq. (3.35) and rotate the original Stokes vector $\mathbf{S} = (I, Q, U)$ by α_{rot} to define the new Stokes vector

$$\mathbf{S}_{\text{rot}} = \begin{pmatrix} I_{\text{rot}} \\ Q_{\text{rot}} \\ U_{\text{rot}} \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{R}(\alpha_{\text{rot}})\mathbf{S} = \begin{pmatrix} I \\ Q \cos \alpha_{\text{rot}} + U \sin \alpha_{\text{rot}} \\ -Q \sin \alpha_{\text{rot}} + U \cos \alpha_{\text{rot}} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (4.1)$$

We note that this procedure is performed as a post-processing step after the end of each simulation and adopted only for presenting results. In special cases where the ejecta are perfectly symmetric about one axis (see e.g. Fig. 2.7), the rotation in Eq. (4.1) will bring all the polarisation signal along Q_{rot} while U_{rot} will be consistent with zero (within the Monte Carlo noise level). A particular instance of this is given by 2D explosion models, in which the azimuthal symmetry about the z axis results in $\alpha = 0$ and thus $Q_{\text{rot}} = Q$ and $U_{\text{rot}} = 0$. In more general cases – where an axial symmetry might not be present – Q_{rot} will carry the strongest polarisation signal while U_{rot} will be reflective of departures from a single-axis geometry. Here we note that the rotation in Eq. (4.1) corresponds to a rotation of the reference frame (\mathbf{l}, \mathbf{r}) described in Section 3.3.1 by an angle χ_{rot} .

As discussed in Section 3.4, an important drawback of Monte Carlo calculations is their stochastic nature: Monte Carlo noise in the extracted spectra can become suffi-

ciently large to make the identification of real features challenging. This is particularly crucial when extracting low levels of polarisation ($\lesssim 1$ per cent) such as those observed in SNe Ia. In this work we will estimate the Monte Carlo noise in the spectra by using the fact that our ARTIS calculations are typically carried out on multiple cores which provides us with a set of independent estimates for any given observable (see Section 4.1). In particular, we divide the simulation outputs into eight subsets, each comprising one eighth of the cores, and calculate an emerging spectrum for each of them. Spectral differences between different subsets are representative of the Monte Carlo noise and estimated by computing residuals from a mean spectrum.

4.4 A first test case: the one-dimensional W7 model

Although much effort has been recently directed at developing multi-dimensional explosion models (Rosswog et al. 2009; Jordan et al. 2012; Kushnir et al. 2013; Moll et al. 2014; Fink et al. 2014), the one-dimensional parameterised deflagration model W7 (see Section 1.4.3) is still widely used since its composition and structure provide reasonable agreement with observations of normal SNe Ia (Kasen et al. 2006; Kromer & Sim 2009; Jack et al. 2011; van Rossum 2012; Gall et al. 2012). Here we calculate ARTIS flux and polarisation spectra for this model aiming to: (i) compare the accuracy of the DCT and the EBT in reproducing flux spectra at different epochs; (ii) test our polarisation implementation on a spherically symmetric system for which null polarisation spectra are expected.

For this calculation we simulate $N_q = 8.192 \times 10^7$ Monte Carlo packets and compute spectra over 111 logarithmic time-steps from 2 to 120 d after explosion. We bin the final spectra of both the DCT and the EBT in logarithmic wavelength bins with $\frac{\Delta\lambda}{\lambda} = 3.912 \times 10^{-3}$. For this test, local thermodynamic equilibrium (LTE) has been assumed for all time-steps¹. The calculation was carried out by mapping the spherically symmetric W7 model onto a 100^3 Cartesian grid, through which the packets were propagated. The v -packet EBT is activated from 10 to 30 d after explosion and only for r -packets with emergent rf wavelength between 3500 and 10000 Å. Spectra for the EBT are computed for the viewing angles $\mathbf{n}_{\text{obs},1} = (0, 0, 1)$ and $\mathbf{n}_{\text{obs},2} = (1, 0, 0)$. Since the model is spherically symmetric, spectra extracted for both orientations are – within the MC noise levels – identical and in the following we will present results for $\mathbf{n}_{\text{obs},1}$. Compared to the DCT, the runtime penalty associated with using the v -packet routine in the EBT is found to be less than a factor of two, with the advantage that the number of packets

¹We note that LTE is a crude approximation, especially for epochs after maximum light. We will, however, confine most of our discussion to relatively early epochs when the LTE approximation should be reasonable.

Figure 4.1: Spectra for the W7 model at 15, 20 and 25 d after explosion computed with the DCT (black lines) and EBT (red lines). The spectra are computed for an observer at $\mathbf{n}_{\text{obs}} = (0, 0, 1)$. The model supernova is assumed to be at 1 Mpc.

contributing to the emergent spectrum is a factor of ~ 115 higher.

Fig. 4.1 shows flux spectra calculated with the EBT at 15, 20 (around B -band maximum light) and 25 d after explosion. These are compared with spectra extracted with the DCT using 10 Θ viewing-angle bins. The latter number is chosen to achieve a reasonable level of Monte Carlo noise in the spectra and is the same adopted in previous studies using ARTIS to calculate light curves and flux spectra of SN Ia explosion models (e.g. Kromer & Sim 2009; Kromer et al. 2010; Pakmor et al. 2012; Sim et al. 2013). In Section 3.5.2 we chose a number of 51 viewing-angle bins as a reasonable value to obtain accurate angle-resolved results with relatively low Monte Carlo noise for a

Figure 4.2: Accuracy of the DCT and the EBT in reproducing continuum polarisation consistent with zero. The W7 model has been used for this test calculation. Polarisation spectra are computed at 20 d after explosion with the DCT (black lines) and EBT (red lines). The increase in Monte Carlo noise at longer wavelengths is due to the lower flux in the spectrum (see Fig. 4.1).

simple ellipsoidal configuration. Reducing the number of viewing-angle bins to 10 does not affect the accuracy of the results (given that the observables in a 1D model are the same for different viewing angles) but instead merely decreases the Monte Carlo noise in the predicted spectra (see below).

The agreement between the two techniques is very good, with the EBT being much less affected by Monte Carlo noise, as expected. Specifically, the standard deviation of the residual in the v -packet spectrum is estimated to be 13.8 times smaller than that calculated for the angle-resolved direct counting spectrum. We note that the factor

by which the noise improves does depend on the number of angular bins used (the improvement is less dramatic – but still significant – if fewer bins are used). However, our choice of 10 bins is rather conservative (c.f. Section 3.5.2 where it was found that ~ 51 bins were required for accurate representation of a simple 2D model).

Polarisation spectra around maximum light in the B -band are reported in Fig. 4.2. As expected from a one-dimensional model, the average q and u throughout the whole spectral range are consistent with zero for both techniques, with the signal-to-noise decreasing towards the red because of the lower flux level. The decrease in Monte Carlo noise when comparing the DCT to the EBT is remarkable: the standard deviation in the q (u) spectrum is a factor of 13.1 (14.2) larger in the former compared to the latter, in good agreement with our findings from the flux spectra. This simple comparison clearly shows that the v -packet technique is superior for producing accurate polarisation levels.

4.5 A second test-case: two-dimensional ellipsoidal models

In this section, we test the accuracy of our polarisation scheme in reproducing polarisation spectra for multi-dimensional explosion models. Guided by previous studies (e.g. Höflich 1991; Howell et al. 2001; Kasen et al. 2003; Dessart & Hillier 2011; Patat et al. 2012, see Section 2.5), we choose ellipsoidal models with SN Ia composition as a starting point to explore aspherical geometries. In particular, here we aim at laying the groundwork for the study that will be presented in Chapter 5 and demonstrate how asymmetries in the ejecta distribution can be effectively characterised by investigating their polarimetric signatures. For this purpose, rather aspherical ellipsoids will be used (see below) to produce relatively large polarisation levels that can be easily discriminated from Monte Carlo noise levels. Therefore, we do not expect polarisation spectra extracted in this section to give a perfect match to those observed in SNe Ia.

For our study, we use a model equivalent to that of Kromer & Sim (2009), which has a prolate ejecta morphology (PEM), and also consider a similar model with an oblate ejecta morphology (OEM). Specifically, we assume ellipsoidal isodensity surfaces with density profile

$$\rho(\xi) \propto \begin{cases} \exp\left(-\frac{\xi}{\xi_0}\right) & \xi < \xi_{\max} \\ 0 & \xi > \xi_{\max} \end{cases} . \quad (4.2)$$

The parameter ξ is defined in terms of the components of velocity in cylindrical polar

coordinates $v = (v_r, v_z)$ as

$$\xi = \begin{cases} \sqrt{h^2 v_r^2 + v_z^2} & \text{OEM} \\ \sqrt{v_r^2 + h^2 v_z^2} & \text{PEM} \end{cases}, \quad (4.3)$$

where $\xi_0 = 2750 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and h is the axis ratio of the ellipsoid, that is the ratio between the semi-minor and semi-major axis. Here we limit our study to an axis ratio $h = 0.5$ and fix the maximum velocity parameter $\xi_{\text{max}} = 13\,750 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. We adopt a composition for both models that is roughly appropriate for SNe Ia. Specifically, the total mass and chemical yields of the ejecta are chosen to be the same as for the W7 model and a stratified composition with three ellipsoidal zones ($h = 0.5$) is assumed. The model is set up by filling the ejecta from the centre to accommodate the W7 yields of the different element groups: the innermost region is filled with “iron group” elements ($21 \leq Z \leq 30$), the middle with IMEs ($9 \leq Z \leq 20$) and the outermost with low-mass elements ($Z \leq 8$). The transitions between the different layers are at $\xi \sim 8000$ and $\xi \sim 10\,500 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. Relative abundances of the elements inside each zone are kept fixed to the W7 values.

LTE radiative transfer calculations have been performed over 111 logarithmic time-steps from 2 to 120 d after explosion. $N_q = 2.458 \times 10^8$ and $N_q = 4.096 \times 10^7$ Monte Carlo quanta have been generated for the PEM and OEM, respectively. Since the redder regions of the polarisation spectra are typically noisier due to the lower flux (i.e. fewer Monte Carlo quanta per frequency bin; see Fig 4.2), an additional simulation has been carried out for the PEM (OEM), with $N_q = 8.192 \times 10^7$ (4.096×10^7) and with the EBT routine called only for $\lambda > 6000 \text{ \AA}^2$. The two simulations have thus been combined to produce final spectra for the EBT in the whole range between 3500 and 10000 \AA . Spectra are computed with the EBT from 10 to 30 d after explosion and for two extreme viewing angles: along the z -axis, $\mathbf{n}_{\text{obs},1} = (0, 0, 1)$, and along the x -axis, $\mathbf{n}_{\text{obs},2} = (1, 0, 0)$.

4.5.1 Flux and polarisation spectra

In Fig. 4.3 we compare the v -packet total flux spectra at 19 d after explosion for the two ellipsoidal models. We find the same strong viewing-angle dependencies reported by Kromer & Sim (2009). For a given morphology, packets escaping along the major axis see a velocity range twice as large compared to the minor axis and the corresponding spectrum is therefore characterised by broader features and stronger line blending;

²This cut in wavelength considerably speeds up the calculation since the v -packet routine is called a factor of ~ 25 times fewer compared to calculations with the entire range 3500 – 10000 \AA .

Figure 4.3: Spectra for the PEM (top panel) and the OEM (bottom panel) calculated with the EBT at 19 d after explosion. Black/green lines are for an observer orientation along z/x ($\mathbf{n}_{\text{obs},1}/\mathbf{n}_{\text{obs},2}$ in the text). Fluxes are given for a distance of 1 Mpc. Scaled isodensity contours are shown for each viewing angle.

moreover, the spectrum viewed along the major axis is fainter since the projected area along this axis is smaller and the typical opacity is higher. The same geometrical arguments can also be used to compare spectra for the two different geometries: spectra viewed down the minor (major) axis are qualitatively similar, because packets see the same velocity range, but the prolate ellipsoid is fainter than the oblate due to the smaller projected surface.

Polarisation spectra for the observer orientation $\mathbf{n}_{\text{obs},1}$ are consistent with zero for both models, reflecting the overall spherical symmetry of the projected surface. However, observer orientations from which the model has an elliptical projected surface ($\mathbf{n}_{\text{obs},2}$) produce a clear polarisation signal. This is shown in Fig. 4.4, where we have set $Q_{\text{rot}} = Q$ and $U_{\text{rot}} = U$ (i.e. $\alpha_{\text{rot}} = 0$, see Section 4.3) since the model is axisymmetric about the z axis. Owing to the azimuthal symmetry of the model, Q_{rot} carries all the polarisation signal while U_{rot} remains consistent with zero. In particular, deviations

Figure 4.4: Flux and polarisation spectra at 19 d after explosion for the PEM (upper panels) and the OEM (lower panels). The observer is placed at $\mathbf{n}_{\text{obs},2}$ (along x). Identification between polarisation features and lines in the spectrum are shown with blue vertical lines. The error bars mark the averaged Monte Carlo noise level in the polarisation spectra below (blue) and above (red) 6400 Å. For clarity, polarisation spectra are smoothed using a Savitzky-Golay filter, a low-pass filter in which every data point is replaced by a new value obtained from a least-square polynomial fit over a window centred at the point. Here we use a first-order polynomial and a window of 3 pixels (~ 50 Å). The flux is given for a distance of 1 Mpc. Scaled isodensity contours are shown in green.

Figure 4.5: Flux spectrum (solid black line) and Q_{rot} polarisation spectrum (red line) around the Si II $\lambda 5979$ and Si II $\lambda 6355$ features for the PEM viewed along the x -axis. Rest wavelengths of the two lines are marked by vertical dashed lines. Inverted P-Cygni profiles for the two silicon lines can be identified in the Q_{rot} spectrum.

from zero in the U_{rot} spectrum are associated with statistical fluctuations and can be used as a convenient proxy for the Monte Carlo noise in the Q_{rot} spectrum. Indeed, the averaged U_{rot} spectrum in the PEM (OEM) is equal to $|U_{\text{rot}}| = 0.08$ (0.19) per cent, in good agreement with the Monte Carlo noise levels of 0.09 (0.21) per cent estimated with the approach described in Section 4.3.

Similar degrees of polarisation (~ 1 per cent) are found in the “pseudo-continuum” region $6400 - 7200 \text{ \AA}$ (see Section 2.4.2). Specifically, a negative Q_{rot} is found for the PEM and a positive Q_{rot} for the OEM, as expected from electron-scattering dominated ellipsoidal models (see Section 2.3.1).

Spectra extracted for both the PEM and the OEM are characterised by strong ($\sim 1 - 2$ per cent) polarisation across spectral lines. Polarisation peaks are associated with the blue-shifted absorption trough, while a decrease in polarisation is found in the emission wing of the P-Cygni profile. This leads to the inverted P-Cygni profile shape discussed in Section 2.3.2. This is clearly apparent in the two Si II lines at ~ 5979 and $\sim 6355 \text{ \AA}$ (see Fig. 4.5).

Figure 4.6: Colour maps of normalised I (left panels), Q_{rot} (middle panels) and U_{rot} (right panels) distributions projected on the velocity plane (v_y, v_z). The maps are computed for the PEM using the EBT and selecting the emergent v -packets between 16.5 and 21.5 d after explosion and in the wavelength regions 3500 – 6000 Å (upper panels) and 6400 – 7200 Å (lower panels). Solid lines mark the outer boundary of the iron-group-element zone (inner white ellipse) and the maximum velocity parameter $\xi_{\text{max}} = 13\,750 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (outer black ellipse). The intensity distribution in the blue is more circular than the projected density contour: Q_{rot} is dominated by contributions along the minor axis, leading to a positive polarisation level. In contrast, the intensity distribution in the red is more similar to the projected density contour: Q_{rot} is dominated by contributions along the major axis and therefore biased towards a negative value.

For each v -packet contributing to the synthetic spectra, our simulations provide information regarding its polarisation state (i.e. its Stokes vector) and the location in the ejecta at which it was created. This allows us to create intensity (I) and polarisation (Q and U) map distributions that help us to better understand specific spectral signatures. For instance, these maps are very useful to explain the sign reversals seen from longer to shorter wavelengths in the Q_{rot} spectrum for both the PEM and the OEM. This behaviour, already found by previous studies (e.g. Dessart & Hillier 2011) and ascribed to variations in thermalisation depth with wavelength, is well captured by our simulations. Fig. 4.6 shows the intensity and polarisation distributions projected on

Figure 4.7: Evolution of the relative contribution of different scattering processes to the observed spectrum. Fractions are calculated for the PEM (left panels) and the OEM (right panels) with the DCT by selecting escaping packets based on their last interaction(s) prior to escape. The fraction of packets that underwent a depolarising interaction process (bound-bound, bound-free or free-free emission) as last interaction is shown in red. The contribution from packets that had a single electron scattering interaction since their last depolarising interaction is indicated in blue, and packets that suffered multiple electron scattering events prior to escaping are shown in black. Upper panels show contribution in the spectral region 3500 – 6000 Å, lower panels in the wavelength range between 6400 and 7200 Å.

the velocity plane (v_y, v_z). The maps have been calculated for the PEM selecting the emergent v -packets between 16.5 and 21.5 d after explosion and in the spectral region 3500 – 6000 Å and pseudo-continuum range 6400 – 7200 Å. In both wavelength intervals, the intensity emission region in projection is less elliptical than the density contour, and this is a stronger effect in the blue. This behaviour can be ascribed to the relative contributions of the line and the electron scattering opacities in different regions of the spectrum (see Fig. 4.7). The *blue* region is dominated by line opacities and thus the intensity distribution in projection is more circular than elliptical. This is because, among all the packets created at a given isodensity surface, those at highest projected velocities (i.e. around the major axis of the ellipsoid) sweep out the largest velocity range on their journey to the observer, and therefore encounter the greatest line opacity. In contrast, the *red* region is free from strong line opacities (see above) and therefore

Figure 4.8: Flux and polarisation spectra for the PEM (upper panels) and the OEM (lower panels) calculated for a viewing angle $\mathbf{n}_{\text{obs},2}$ (along x) at 14 (orange), 19 (red) and 24 (blue) d after explosion. Polarisation spectra are Savitzky-Golay filtered using a first-order polynomial and a window of 3 pixels ($\sim 50 \text{ \AA}$) for clarity. The model flux is given for a distance of 1 Mpc. Scaled isodensity contours are shown in green.

Figure 4.9: Polarisation light curves between 10 and 30 d after explosion for the PEM (left panels) and the OEM (right panels) viewed along the x -axis. Only Q_{rot}^* is reported here since U_{rot}^* is consistent with zero for both models. Grey lines represent contributions from the whole spectral range for which v -packets were calculated (3500 – 10000 Å), whereas blue and red lines are for packets escaping at short (3500 – 6000 Å) or longer (6400 – 7200 Å) wavelengths. Spectral flux integrated in the whole range is reported in the lower panels. One-sigma Monte Carlo noise error bars are derived using the procedure outlined in Section 4.3. Most of the error bars are not visible because they are smaller than the symbol sizes.

the projected intensity distribution is more similar to the elliptical density contour. Because contributions to Q_{rot} are typically positive from regions along the minor axis and negative along the major axis, different distributions in intensity lead to different values of the overall Q_{rot} polarisation: in the blue, polarisation in Q_{rot} is dominated by contributions along the minor axis and thus biased towards a positive value, while in the red the Q_{rot} emission is stronger along the major axis and thus biased toward a negative value. The same arguments explain why the Q_{rot} polarisation in the OEM changes from negative values in the blue to positive in the red.

4.5.2 Spectral evolution and light curves

The spectra of both ellipsoidal models are shown in Fig. 4.8 for three epochs (14, 19 and 24 d after explosion). The integrated luminosity in the wavelength range 3500 – 10000 Å peaks at ~ 19 d after explosion in the PEM, whereas the maximum is reached earlier in the OEM (~ 14 d after explosion, see bottom panels of Fig. 4.9). To quantify the time evolution of the polarisation, we have also computed intensity (I^*) and polarisation (Q_{rot}^* and U_{rot}^*) light curves by integrating the flux and polarisation spectra over selected wavelength ranges $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2]$:

$$\begin{bmatrix} I^*(t) \\ Q_{\text{rot}}^*(t) \\ U_{\text{rot}}^*(t) \end{bmatrix} = \int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} \begin{bmatrix} I(\lambda, t) \\ Q_{\text{rot}}(\lambda, t) \\ U_{\text{rot}}(\lambda, t) \end{bmatrix} d\lambda . \quad (4.4)$$

As expected, U_{rot}^* remains consistent with zero at all times. If we consider the entire synthetic spectrum (i.e. $\lambda_1 = 3500$ Å, $\lambda_2 = 10000$ Å), Q_{rot}^* in the PEM (OEM) evolves from negative to positive (positive to negative) values as we go from early to late epochs (see Fig. 4.9). This behaviour is due to changes in the relative contributions of the blue and red region as a function of time, and can easily be understood from polarisation light curves computed for the spectral intervals between $\lambda_1 = 3500$ Å and $\lambda_2 = 6000$ Å and between $\lambda_1 = 6400$ Å and $\lambda_2 = 7200$ Å (see Fig. 4.9). As can be anticipated from the polarisation spectra, Q_{rot}^* is positive in the blue and negative in the red for the PEM, whereas the opposite is true in the OEM. The OEM light curve evolves more rapidly than the PEM, having reached peak flux at around 14 d and then starting to decline. This more rapid evolution is also clearly evident in the degree of polarisation, which changes much more noticeably over this time period for the OEM. In particular, polarisation in the pseudo-continuum region between 6400 and 7200 Å is approximately constant ($Q_{\text{rot}}^*/I^* \sim -1$ per cent) in the PEM, whereas significant evolution is found for the OEM.

4.5.3 Comparison with observations

The goal of this section was to show how spectropolarimetry can be used to characterise asphericities in multi-dimensional explosion models. As a starting point, we investigated simple ellipsoidal morphologies with sufficiently large asymmetries (axis ratio of 0.5) so that the predicted polarisation levels could be easily distinguished from the Monte Carlo noise levels. Although the ellipsoidal models studied here are not very realistic, they do qualitatively reproduce the main features of SN Ia polarisation spectra. As shown in Fig. 4.10, the PEM predicts an overall small polarisation signal throughout the spectrum ($P \lesssim 1.5$ per cent) and polarisation levels across the lines comparable

Figure 4.10: Polarisation P spectrum for the PEM (red line) calculated ~ 4 d after B band maximum light. For comparison the black line shows the polarisation spectrum of SN 2004dt (Leonard et al. 2005) at the same epoch. The black bar marks the averaged errors in the observed polarisation spectrum. Polarisation levels predicted by the PEM across the lines are comparable (within a factor of two) to those observed, while the polarisation in the continuum (grey shaded area) is too high.

(within a factor of two) to those observed in strongly polarised SNe Ia. As expected, however, the comparison with data is far from perfect: the polarisation predicted in the pseudo-continuum region between 6400 and 7200 Å is too high (because of the strong asymmetry in the toy model) and the velocities of the line features are too small. Such discrepancies come as no surprise, given the simplicity of the model.

In this chapter we have focused on implementing our polarisation scheme in the radiative transfer code ARTIS and on testing its accuracy in calculating intensity and polarisation spectra for one- and two-dimensional models. This exploratory study has laid the groundwork for the calculations presented in the following chapter, where we will make quantitative comparisons between data and the results from polarisation calculations performed for full hydrodynamic explosion models.

Chapter 5

Application to Type Ia supernova multi-dimensional explosion models

“Science cannot solve the ultimate mystery of nature. And that is because, in the last analysis, we ourselves are part of nature and therefore part of the mystery that we are trying to solve.”

– Max Planck

In this chapter we present polarisation spectral synthesis for three different SN Ia explosion scenarios. In Section 5.1 we give a brief description of the specific hydrodynamic explosion models used, while in Section 5.2 we discuss the details of our radiative transfer calculations. In Section 5.3, we present polarisation spectra around maximum light for the three models and compare results with each others. We illustrate how asymmetries in the element distribution are linked to specific polarisation features in Section 5.4, while study the temporal evolution of the polarisation signals in Section 5.5. In Section 5.6, we then compare predictions from our models with spectropolarimetric data of SNe Ia. Finally, in Section 5.7 we discuss our results. Portions of this chapter have been adapted from two papers published in the Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society journal (Bulla et al. 2016a,b).

5.1 Explosion Models

As already discussed in Section 1.4, the exact circumstances leading to SN Ia explosions are unclear. Different scenarios have been proposed in the past few decades, but there is no consensus as to whether one single scenario is able to account comprehensively for the properties observed in SN Ia events. Nevertheless, comparisons of observations with synthetic light curves and spectra predicted by radiative transfer calculations have played a key role in identifying which explosions scenarios are most promising. As a starting point to our long-term project of predicting polarisation signatures for a series of modern SN Ia hydrodynamic models, here we focus on three widely-discussed scenarios: the “double-detonation” of a sub- M_{ch} WD, the “delayed-detonation” of a near M_{ch} WD and the violent merger of two CO WDs (see Section 1.4.3 for a detailed description of each class of models). Since multi-dimensionality is a relatively recent development in modelling SNe Ia, the number of 2D and 3D explosion models is rather small. For each class, we therefore perform polarisation calculations for one representative model that we have access to.

We first select an explosion model of Fink et al. (2010) which has been recently adopted in different studies (Scalzo et al. 2014a,b; Childress et al. 2015; Kosenko et al. 2015) as a reference model for the sub- M_{ch} double-detonation scenario. Then we choose the explosion model of Seitenzahl et al. (2013) as it has been widely used (Röpke et al. 2012; Summa et al. 2013; Scalzo et al. 2014a; Childress et al. 2015; Fransson & Jerkstrand 2015; Kosenko et al. 2015; Sneden et al. 2016) as representative of a class of delayed-detonation models in which a deflagration-to-detonation transition (DDT) is assumed to occur spontaneously during the propagation of the deflagration (see also Section 1.4.3). Finally we take the model of Pakmor et al. (2012), which has been considered as a benchmark for the violent merger scenario in several previous

studies (Röpke et al. 2012; Summa et al. 2013; Scalzo et al. 2014a; Seitzzahl et al. 2015). As discussed in Section 1.5, these models are difficult to discriminate based on predicted light curves and spectra as they reproduce data of normal SNe Ia comparably well (e.g. Röpke et al. 2012). In this respect, polarisation offers a promising opportunity to differentiate between these explosion models as their predicted ejecta geometries are considerably different (see below). Therefore, in the following we adopt these three example models and focus on the added value of synthetic spectropolarimetry in understanding the strengths and weaknesses of their respective explosion scenarios.

5.1.1 Double-detonation model

The six double-detonation models investigated by Fink et al. (2010) comprise WDs with carbon-oxygen (50 per cent ^{12}C and 50 per cent ^{16}O) core masses increasing from 0.81 to 1.38 M_{\odot} and helium-shell masses decreasing from 0.13 to $3.5 \times 10^{-3} M_{\odot}$. The specific helium-shell masses were selected to meet minimum conditions required for a helium detonation suggested by Bildsten et al. (2007, see Section 1.4.3). Hydrodynamic simulations were performed in 2D assuming azimuthal symmetry about the z axis. In all the models, the first detonation is ignited at a single point (see below) on the positive z axis at the interface between the core and the helium shell. While the detonation wave sweeps along the core-shell interface, a shock wave moves through the core and converges at an off-centre point on the negative z axis (Livne & Glasner 1990). A second detonation is then artificially inserted around this point if temperature and pressure conditions are sufficiently high (Niemeyer & Woosley 1997; Röpke et al. 2007b). We note that, although this model is only 2D, neither the adopted WD progenitor model nor the ignition condition break axial symmetry. In addition, while turbulent eddies breaking the initial symmetry can develop in deflagration models (see Section 1.4.3), a detonation triggered on the negative z axis is expected to preserve the azimuthal symmetry.

For our spectropolarimetric study, we select ‘model 3’ of Fink et al. (2010) since this configuration produces an amount of ^{56}Ni ($0.55 M_{\odot}$) in the range observed for normal SNe Ia (Stritzinger et al. 2006; Scalzo et al. 2014a; Childress et al. 2015) and is found to predict observables in reasonable – although not perfect (see Section 1.4.3) – agreement with normal SNe Ia (Kromer et al. 2010). This model (referred to as the D-DET model in the rest of the thesis) has a carbon-oxygen core of $1.025 M_{\odot}$ and a helium shell of $0.055 M_{\odot}$. At the time of the first detonation, the helium *shell* is at relatively low densities ($\lesssim 4.5 \times 10^5 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$). Therefore, 60 per cent of the helium is left unburned and much of the material that is burned does not reach NSE (see discussion

Figure 5.1: Density and composition of the ejecta at 100 s after explosion for the 2D D-DET (left-hand panels), 3D N100-DDT (middle panels) and 3D VM-11-09 models (right-hand panels) studied in this work. From top to bottom, the density ρ and mass fractions X_i of carbon, oxygen, silicon, calcium and IGEs (summed from scandium to zinc) are shown for a slice through the x - z plane.

Figure 5.2: Same as Fig. 5.1 but for a slice through the x - y plane.

in Section 1.4.2). Specifically, the conditions in the model favour burning products rich in IGEs lighter than ^{56}Ni , such as ^{52}Fe (11 per cent), ^{48}Cr (8 per cent) and ^{44}Ti (6 per cent). Aside from modest fractions of ^{40}Ca (4 per cent) and ^{36}Ar (4 per cent), very few IMEs are produced in the shell. In contrast, the *core* detonation synthesizes $0.55 M_{\odot}$ of ^{56}Ni (96 per cent of the total IGE production in the core) and $0.37 M_{\odot}$ of IMEs.

The left-hand panels in Fig. 5.1 and Fig. 5.2 show the density and composition of the ejecta for two slices through the x - z and the equatorial x - y plane, respectively. Density and composition maps are shown at ~ 100 s after explosion, when the system has already entered the homologous expansion phase (see Section 3.2.2). Owing to the azimuthal symmetry about the z axis, the ejecta in the x - y plane are symmetric. In contrast, the asymmetries introduced by the explosion mechanism causes the ejecta structure to be fairly aspherical in the x - z plane. First, since the helium detonation is ignited in a point on the positive z -axis, ejecta from the *shell* (e.g. the outer layer of calcium) are distributed over a wider range of velocities in the upper compared to the lower hemisphere. Second, the off-center ignition of the *core* detonation causes the upper regions of the core to be less compressed than those on the opposite side. This has the effect of producing IMEs (e.g. silicon) that are more abundant and extend over a wider velocity range in the upper compared to the lower hemisphere (see also section 4.3 of Fink et al. 2010). We note that the specific ejecta morphology depends on the ignition geometry. Asymmetries produced in the D-DET model of Fink et al. (2010) follow from the choice of a one-point ignition on the z -axis, while more symmetric ejecta are expected for more symmetric shell ignitions (see Fink et al. 2007).

5.1.2 Delayed-detonation model

The set of 3D DDT models studied by Seitenzahl et al. (2013) comprises WDs with mass close to M_{ch} and with initial compositions of 47.5 per cent ^{12}C , 50 per cent ^{16}O and 2.5 per cent ^{22}Ne (corresponding to a zero-age main-sequence progenitor with solar metallicity). Twelve of the fourteen models differ only in ignition geometry of the deflagration. This is parametrised in terms of a number of spherical ignition kernels, ranging from 1 to 1600 and eventually determining the amount of ^{56}Ni synthesised during the explosion. As explained in Section 1.4.3, a decreasing amount of ^{56}Ni (from ~ 1.1 to $0.4 M_{\odot}$) is produced for an increasing number of ignition sparks since the deflagration phase is increasingly stronger and thus the detonation occurs in a more pre-expanded and at lower density material. To investigate what impact the adopted WD central density has on the explosion products (e.g. ^{56}Ni), the remaining two models are alternative versions of the 100-kernel model that consider different central densities. For all the

models, the kernels were placed near the centre of the WD. Following the ignition, the deflagration flame propagates and turbulence develops. Once the turbulent velocity fluctuations at the flame front become sufficiently strong, a transition to a supersonic detonation is artificially inserted (see Sections 1.4.2 and 1.4.3), which totally disrupts the WD.

For our spectropolarimetric study, we select the ‘N100’ model of Seitenzahl et al. (2013). This model (hereafter referred to as N100-DDT model) is chosen as it yields an amount of ^{56}Ni ($0.6 M_{\odot}$) consistent with the values derived for the bulk of normal SNe Ia (Stritzinger et al. 2006; Scalzo et al. 2014a; Childress et al. 2015) and because it provides a good match to observed spectra and light curves (Röpke et al. 2012; Sim et al. 2013). This specific configuration produces $0.84 M_{\odot}$ of IGEs and $0.45 M_{\odot}$ of IMEs.

The middle panels of Fig. 5.1 and Fig. 5.2 show the density and composition of the ejecta 100 s after explosion for two slices through the x - z and x - y plane, respectively. The rather symmetric ignition geometry of this specific explosion simulation results in an overall distribution of the ejecta that is spherical and thus not strongly viewing-angle dependent. However, clear small-scale asymmetries are produced during the deflagration phase in the oxygen and IME distributions (see Section 1.4.3) and these can be expected to imprint observable signatures.

5.1.3 Violent merger model

The binary system studied by Pakmor et al. (2012) comprises two WDs with masses of $1.1 M_{\odot}$ and $0.9 M_{\odot}$ and initial compositions of 47.5% ^{12}C , 50% ^{16}O and 2.5% ^{22}Ne (solar metallicity). In this model (referred to as VM-11-09 in the rest of the thesis), a detonation is assumed to be ignited following the disruption of the secondary star. In particular, as discussed in Section 1.4.2, the ignition is artificially inserted when material on the surface of the primary reaches sufficiently high densities and temperatures (Seitenzahl et al. 2009). The detonation starts to propagate and the energy release from nuclear burning eventually leads to a thermonuclear explosion that unbinds the merging object.

Pakmor et al. (2012) followed the evolution of the system until 100 s after ignition, by which time the ejecta have entered the homologous expansion phase. During the explosion, $0.7 M_{\odot}$ of iron-group-elements (IGEs) are synthesised, of which the most abundant isotope ($0.61 M_{\odot}$) is radioactive ^{56}Ni . In addition, $0.5 M_{\odot}$ of IMEs and $0.5 M_{\odot}$ of oxygen are produced, with $0.15 M_{\odot}$ of carbon left unburned in low density regions.

The right-hand panels of Fig. 5.1 and Fig. 5.2 show two slices through the composi-

tion of the ejecta 100 s after explosion. The ejecta structure is highly aspherical, owing to the asymmetry of the merging object at the time of ignition. However, the ejecta are fairly symmetric about the $x - y$ plane (Fig. 5.1) in which the inspiral and the merger phases take place before the explosion (i.e. the orbital plane). A distinctive feature is given by the cavity in the IGE distribution. As described by Pakmor et al. (2012), this feature is created as a direct consequence of the different velocities with which the detonation flame propagates inside the merged object. Given that the propagation is faster through high density regions, the primary star burns first and its ashes have expanded considerably by the time the secondary is completely burned. Therefore, the inner parts of the ejecta are dominated by the ashes of the secondary WD. Since burning in the secondary occurs at relatively low density, this material does not contain IGEs (see Section 1.4.2).

5.2 Radiative transfer calculations

To extract synthetic observables for the explosion models presented in Section 5.1, we carry out calculations using ARTIS (see Section 4.1). Radiative transfer calculations for the same D-DET, N100-DDT and VM-11-09 models were already performed by Kromer et al. (2010), Sim et al. (2013) and Pakmor et al. (2012), respectively, but here we present new simulations that include polarisation. In addition, observables in these new calculations are extracted using the v -packet approach (see below) and thus flux spectra are of much better quality compared to those presented in previous studies (see also Section 4.4). We first remap each explosion model to a Cartesian grid: in line with the previous studies, we remap the 2D D-DET model to a 100^3 grid and the 3D N100-DDT and VM-11-09 models to 50^3 grids. We then follow the propagation of N_q Monte Carlo quanta from 2 to 120 days after explosion using a series of 111 logarithmically spaced time-steps. To speed up the calculations, we assume local thermodynamic equilibrium for the first 10 time-steps ($t < 2.95$ d) and a grey approximation for optically thick cells (Kromer & Sim 2009). Compared to the previous radiative transfer studies, here we use a more extended atomic data set that includes about 2.1×10^6 lines and ions I - VII for $21 \leq Z \leq 28$. A summary of the atomic data set used in this thesis is given in Table 5.1.

Synthetic observables (light curves, flux and polarisation spectra) are extracted for multiple observer orientations using the EBT (see Section 3.4.2 and Section 4.2). Flux and polarisation spectra are extracted for each orientation between 10 and 30 d after explosion in the wavelength range 3500–10 000 Å. To map out the range of polarisation covered by each explosion models, we first carry out *low signal-to-noise simulations* with a relatively small number of packets and selecting 20 orientations for the

Table 5.1: Atomic data set used in the radiative transfer calculations.

	Z=2	6 ≤ Z ≤ 20	21 ≤ Z ≤ 28	29 ≤ Z ≤ 30
Ions	I - III	I - V	I - VII	I - V
Levels	554	8200	27 168	672

2D D-DET model, 26 orientations for the 3D N100-DDT model and 35 viewing angles for the 3D VM-11-09 model. Specifically, $N_q = 1.536 \times 10^8$ packets are used for the D-DET and N100-DDT models, while $N_q = 1.024 \times 10^8$ for the VM-11-09 model. Results of these low signal-to-noise calculations will be presented in Section 5.6.2.

We then focus on a few orientations for each model and carry out *high signal-to-noise simulations* with a larger number of packets (see below) to study polarisation spectral features in better details. For the 2D D-DET model, we select three orientations in the x - z plane so that the ejecta asymmetries are properly sampled from $+z$ to $-z$ (see upper panel of Fig. 5.3): $\mathbf{l}_1 = (1/\sqrt{2}, 0, 1/\sqrt{2})$, $\mathbf{l}_2 = (1, 0, 0)$, $\mathbf{l}_3 = (1/\sqrt{2}, 0, -1/\sqrt{2})$. The choice of restricting our study to the x - z plane is sufficient since the model has azimuthal symmetry about the z axis. For the 3D N100-DDT model, we instead select five observer orientations (see middle panels of Fig. 5.3). Guided by the findings of Sim et al. (2013), we first choose the orientations for which the model is brightest, $\mathbf{n}_1 = (0, 0, -1)$, and faintest, $\mathbf{n}_2 = (-1/\sqrt{2}, 1/\sqrt{2}, 0)$, and then select three additional directions to sample the plane defined by \mathbf{n}_1 and \mathbf{n}_2 : $\mathbf{n}_3 = (-1/2, 1/2, 1/\sqrt{2})$, $\mathbf{n}_4 = (0, 0, 1)$ and $\mathbf{n}_5 = (1/\sqrt{2}, -1/\sqrt{2}, 0)$. We note that the choice of a specific plane is not restrictive as the ejecta of this model show a global spherical symmetry and thus no preferential direction (see Figs 5.1 and 5.2). Five orientations are also chosen for the VM-11-09 model (see lower panel of Fig. 5.3). We first follow previous results from Pakmor et al. (2012) and choose the two orientations for which the model is faintest, $\mathbf{m}_1 = (0, 0, 1)$, and brightest, $\mathbf{m}_2 = (0, 1, 0)$. We then place two observers with orientations that are aligned with the cavity in the IGE distribution that is due to material from the secondary (see Section 5.1.3): one facing the cavity, $\mathbf{m}_3 = (-1/\sqrt{2}, -1/\sqrt{2}, 0)$, and one at the opposite side, $\mathbf{m}_4 = (1/\sqrt{2}, 1/\sqrt{2}, 0)$. Finally, we select a viewing angle away from the orbital plane and the polar axis, specifically $\mathbf{m}_5 = (1/2, 1/2, 1/\sqrt{2})$.

For these high signal-to-noise calculations, a different number of Monte Carlo packets is used for each explosion model investigated. In particular, compared to the VM-11-09, the D-DET and N100-DDT models are characterised by smaller asymmetries in the ejecta (see Fig. 5.1 and Fig. 5.2) and thus expected to produce smaller polarisation signals. A larger number of Monte Carlo packets is then used for these two models in order to better discriminate intrinsic polarisation signals from Monte Carlo

Figure 5.3: Sketch depicting the observer orientations selected in this study for the D-DET (upper), N100-DDT (middle) and VM-11-09 (lower) model. Viewing angles are shown with respect to the ^{56}Ni distribution, which is reported only for regions where the ^{56}Ni mass fraction is larger than 0.25.

noise. Specifically, we utilize $N_q = 5.12 \times 10^8$ for both the D-DET (cf. with $N_q = 2 \times 10^7$ of Kromer et al. 2010) and the N100-DDT (cf. with $N_q = 1.024 \times 10^8$ of Sim et al. 2013) model, while $N_q = 2.048 \times 10^8$ for the VM-11-09 model (cf. with $N_q = 1 \times 10^8$ of Pakmor et al. 2012). Given that polarisation spectra are typically noisier in the red where the flux is lower, we perform additional calculations with $N_q = 2.048 \times 10^8$ (1.024×10^8) for the D-DET and N100-DDT (VM-11-09) models and selecting ν -packets escaping with rest-frame wavelengths between 5800 (6300) and 10 000 Å (see Section 4.2).

5.3 Polarisation around maximum light

In this section, we present polarisation spectra around maximum light for the 2D D-DET and the 3D N100-DDT and VM-11-09 models introduced in Section 5.1. As discussed in Section 4.3, the polarisation signal will be presented using the rotated Stokes parameter Q_{rot} and U_{rot} . Specifically:

- for the 2D D-DET model, we will exploit the axial symmetry of the explosion and plot Q as Q_{rot} and U as U_{rot} (i.e. $\alpha_{\text{rot}} = 0$). Thanks to the azimuthal symmetry about the z -axis, Q_{rot} is expected to contain *all* the polarisation signal, while U_{rot} should be consistent with zero (within the Monte Carlo noise level);
- for each observer in the 3D N100-DDT and VM-11-09 models, we will identify α_{rot} via a weighted least-squared fit of a straight line in the Q/U plane. Upon rotating Q and U by α_{rot} (see Eq. 4.1), Q_{rot} is expected to contain *most of* the polarisation signal, while U_{rot} to be reflective of deviations from a single-axis geometry.

5.3.1 Double-detonation model

In Fig. 5.4 we show flux and polarisation spectra for the selected D-DET model orientations \mathbf{l}_1 (north), \mathbf{l}_2 (equator) and \mathbf{l}_3 (south). Spectra are reported at $t_{\text{max}}^B = 18.5$ d after explosion, that is around B -band maximum light for all the observers. As described by Kromer et al. (2010), the asymmetries in the ejecta (see upper panels of Fig. 5.4) translate into strongly viewing-angle dependent flux spectra. Compared to packets escaping in the southern hemisphere (along \mathbf{l}_3), those on the opposite side (along \mathbf{l}_1) have to travel through a more extended layer of IGEs and are therefore more likely to be absorbed and reemitted at longer wavelengths. This effect leads to a much redder spectrum for the orientation in the northern hemisphere. Owing to the off-center ignition of

Figure 5.4: *Upper panels.* Orientations of the three observers selected for the D-DET model (l_1 , l_2 and l_3) with respect to the ejecta composition. The mass fractions of silicon (left), calcium (middle) and IGEs (right) are represented using the same colour scale of Fig. 5.1 and Fig. 5.2. *Lower panels.* Flux (top) and polarisation Q_{rot} (middle) spectra at 18.5 d after explosion (B -band maximum light) for the three chosen viewing angles. Polarisation signals in U_{rot} (bottom) are only due to statistical fluctuations in the simulations. The error bars mark the averaged Monte Carlo noise level in the polarisation spectra – estimated as explained in Section 4.3 – below (blue) and above (red) 6400 \AA . Polarisation spectra are Savitzky-Golay filtered using a first-order polynomial and a window of 3 pixels ($\sim 50 \text{ \AA}$) for clarity. The model flux is given for a distance of 1 Mpc.

Figure 5.5: Region of last scattering for polarising contributions at -5 (top), 0 (middle) and $+5$ (bottom) relative to maximum light. Distributions include radial velocities at the points where packets underwent a polarising interaction (i.e. electron scattering) as last interaction before escaping towards the observer. 10^6 packets have been used for the D-DET (blue), the N100-DDT (red) and the VM-11-09 (black) model.

the core (see Section 5.1.1), IMEs are also more abundant and distributed over a wider velocity range in the northern hemisphere. IME spectral features extracted along \mathbf{I}_1 are thus stronger and broader compared to those along \mathbf{I}_3 (see for instance the Si II $\lambda 6355$ line and Ca II IR triplet). Intermediate spectral properties are found for the equatorial observer orientation (\mathbf{I}_2).

Owing to the symmetry about the z axis, all the polarisation signal in the D-DET model is brought by Q_{rot} , while fluctuations in U_{rot} are representative of statistical Monte Carlo noise. Indeed, the averaged U_{rot} polarisation between 3500 and

Figure 5.6: Identification of individual spectral transitions for the D-DET model in the 5000–8500 Å wavelength region. Flux and polarisation spectra are the same as in Fig. 5.4 and are shown only for the \mathbf{l}_1 observer orientation. Signals in U_{rot} are only due to statistical fluctuations in the simulations. Vertical lines provide identifications of polarisation peaks with spectral transitions. Rest-frame wavelength and blueshift velocity of each transition are reported in the corresponding label. The error bars mark the averaged Monte Carlo noise level in the polarisation spectra below (blue) and above (red) 6400 Å. Polarisation spectra are Savitzky-Golay filtered using a first-order polynomial and a window of 3 pixels (~ 50 Å) for clarity.

9000 Å is equal to $|U_{\text{rot}}| = 0.038$ per cent, in excellent agreement with the Monte Carlo noise level of 0.039 per cent estimated with the approach described in Section 4.3. Polarisation levels in Q_{rot} are relatively low ($|Q_{\text{rot}}| \lesssim 0.7$ per cent) for all the three observer orientations. We find similar degrees of polarisation (Q_{rot} between -0.1 and -0.05 per cent, see also Section 5.5) for all observer orientations in the pseudo-continuum spectral range 6400–7200 Å. As discussed in Section 2.3.1, non-zero continuum polarisation in supernovae is representative of asymmetries in the underlying electron-scattering photosphere. Therefore, the extremely low levels found across the pseudo-continuum region 6400–7200 Å point towards very low asphericities in the

electron scattering medium. This is a direct consequence of the overall spherical symmetry of the inner regions of the ejecta (velocities between ~ 5000 and $15\,000\text{ km s}^{-1}$, see Fig. 5.1), where the density is largest and from which most of the electron-scattered polarising contributions originate (see middle panel of Fig. 5.5).

Despite the small signal in the pseudo-continuum, the polarisation increases at wavelengths corresponding to the absorption troughs of spectral lines. In Fig. 5.6, we report polarisation spectra between 5000 and 8500 \AA extracted along the \mathbf{I}_1 direction. Matches between spectral lines and polarisation peaks are unambiguous above 5000 \AA . The strongest polarisation feature in this range is a peak of about 0.7 per cent around 7700 \AA , which clearly corresponds to the Ca II IR triplet at high-velocities ($v \sim -26\,000\text{ km s}^{-1}$) and reflects the asymmetric distribution of calcium in the outer shell (but see also discussion in Section 5.4.1). Other peaks are predicted at lower velocities (between $-10\,000$ and $-13\,000\text{ km s}^{-1}$) and attributed to silicon, sulphur and oxygen transitions in the outer layers of the core detonation. Compared to calcium, these elements are more spherically distributed and thus characterised by weaker polarisation signatures ($|Q_{\text{rot}}| \lesssim 0.4$ per cent). Specifically, we find clear polarisation signals for the Si II $\lambda 6355$ line (see also Section 5.6.2), while smaller – and possibly null – signals for the S II $\lambda 5454$, S II $\lambda 5640$ and Si II $\lambda 5972$ lines. A clear polarisation feature is also seen around 7500 \AA , with negative Q_{rot} (i.e. 90° rotated from the rest of the features). In our simulations, this features can be attributed to a blend of O I $\lambda 7774$, Si II $\lambda\lambda 7849, 7850$ (Si II $\lambda 7849$) and Mg II $\lambda\lambda 7877, 7896$ (Mg II $\lambda 7887$), with relative contributions that depend on orientation and epoch. The nature of this polarisation signature and its 90° rotation from the rest of the features will be investigated in Section 5.4. With the exception of a polarisation peak around 3700 \AA , associated with the Si II $\lambda 3859$ and/or Ca H and K features, identifications to individual transitions are not obvious below $\sim 5000\text{ \AA}$ due to the strong line blending suffered by these blue regions.

5.3.2 Delayed-detonation model

In Fig. 5.7 we show flux spectra at $t_{\text{max}}^{\text{B}} = 17\text{ d}$ after explosion (around B -band maximum light) for all the five orientations selected in the N100-DDT model. As shown by Fig. 5.1 and Fig. 5.2, the ejecta distribution in this model is rather spherical and does not have IGE material at very high velocities, in contrast to the D-DET model. Compared to the D-DET model, the N100-DDT model is therefore characterised by a much smaller viewing angle dependence in the flux spectra (Sim et al. 2013). One noticeable difference is found for the blue-shifted absorption component of the Ca II IR

Figure 5.7: *Upper panels.* Orientations of the five observers selected for the N100-DDT model ($\mathbf{n}_1 - \mathbf{n}_5$) with respect to the ejecta composition. The mass fractions of silicon (left), calcium (middle) and IGEs (right) are represented in the plane described in Section 5.2 (with $v_r = v_x / \sqrt{2} - v_y / \sqrt{2}$) and using the same colour scale of Fig. 5.1 and Fig. 5.2. *Lower panels.* Flux (top) and polarisation Q_{rot} (middle) and U_{rot} (lower) spectra extracted for the N100-DDT model at 17 d after explosion (B -band maximum light) along the $\mathbf{n}_1 - \mathbf{n}_3$ (left) and $\mathbf{n}_4 - \mathbf{n}_5$ (right) orientations. Polarisation signals in U_{rot} reflect deviations from a single-axis geometry (see discussion in Section 4.3). The error bars mark the averaged Monte Carlo noise level in the polarisation spectra below (blue) and above (red) 6400 \AA . Polarisation spectra are Savitzky-Golay filtered using a first-order polynomial and a window of 3 pixels ($\sim 50 \text{ \AA}$) for clarity. The model flux is given for a distance of 1 Mpc.

Figure 5.8: Q/U planes for the N100-DDT model at maximum light as viewed from the $\mathbf{n}_1 - \mathbf{n}_5$ (from top-left to bottom-right) directions. A weighted least-squares fitting to the data is performed for each orientation and the result plotted as a solid black line. The α_{rot} angles determined from the fitting and used to convert Q and U to the polarisation spectra Q_{rot} and U_{rot} of Fig. 5.7 are also reported in each panel. For each Q/U plot, a white star indicates the averaged polarisation level in the pseudo-continuum range between 6400 and 7200 \AA , while the error bars mark the averaged Monte Carlo noise level in the polarisation spectra – estimated as explained in Section 4.3 – below (blue) and above (red) 6400 \AA . Black circles mark polarisation levels of 0.5 per cent. Q and U Stokes parameters are Savitzky-Golay filtered using a first-order polynomial and a window of 3 pixels ($\sim 50 \text{\AA}$) for clarity.

triplet, which is stronger when observed from an equatorial orientation \mathbf{n}_2 . This can be understood by noting that the calcium distribution is not perfectly spherical (see upper panels of Fig. 5.7) and offers higher opacities to packets escaping towards \mathbf{n}_2 compared to those escaping in the other directions.

Fig. 5.7 also reports polarisation spectra for the same five orientations. As shown in Fig. 5.8, the Stokes parameters Q_{rot} and U_{rot} are derived via a weighted least-squared fit of a straight line in the Q/U plane of each observer. Although the Q and U points for the polar viewing angles \mathbf{n}_1 and \mathbf{n}_4 seem to align along a preferential direction (associated with $\alpha_{\text{rot}} \sim 166^\circ$), we find no orientation displaying a strong dominant axis. Therefore, although the strongest polarisation signal is carried by Q_{rot} for all

Figure 5.9: *Upper panels.* Same as Fig 5.6 but for the N100-DDT model viewed along the \mathbf{n}_1 orientation. *Lower panel.* The same Q_{rot} spectra reported in the upper panels, together with smoothed versions (black) using a Savitzky-Golay filter with a window of 7 pixels ($\sim 120 \text{ \AA}$). No clear polarisation feature is found between 6500 and 7300 \AA .

the viewing angles, some residual polarisation is also found in U_{rot} . In particular, the fact that the averaged Monte Carlo noise level in the Q_{rot} and U_{rot} spectra is ~ 0.035 and 0.082 per cent below and above 6400 \AA , respectively, clearly confirms that polarisation levels in the U_{rot} spectra of the N100-DDT model, reaching up to 0.4 per cent levels, can not be solely due to statistical fluctuations. The strongest deviations from a single-axis geometry are generally associated with spectral lines, as seen for instance across the Si II $\lambda 6355$ feature in the \mathbf{n}_3 direction or for the Ca II IR triplet along \mathbf{n}_4 .

As in the flux spectrum, the largest line-of-sight variability in the polarisation percentage level is found across the Ca H and K and Ca II IR triplet profiles. Compared to the other orientations, the polarisation signal along \mathbf{n}_2 is a factor of ~ 3 stronger and reaches peak levels of ~ 0.45 per cent and ~ 0.8 per cent in the Ca H and K and Ca II IR triplet, respectively. Some viewing-angle variations are also observed for the Si II $\lambda 6355$ line, but the line-of-sight dependence of this profile is less pronounced compared to that of calcium (see also Section 5.6.2).

The pseudo-continuum region $6400\text{--}7200 \text{ \AA}$ is characterised by polarisation levels of about $0.1\text{--}0.3$ per cent for all the orientations (see also Section 5.5). As shown in Fig. 5.9 for the \mathbf{n}_1 orientation, our synthetic spectropolarimetry in this spectral range contains a number of small peaks. Most of these, however, can be ascribed to statistical fluctuations in the simulations since deviations from the mean degree of polarisation ($Q_{\text{rot}} \sim 0.3$ per cent) are typically smaller than the average Monte Carlo noise level in this range (~ 0.1 per cent, see red error bar). This is verified in the lower panels of Fig. 5.9, where we plot a smoothed version of the Q_{rot} spectrum. In the latter, pixel-to-pixel variations due to Monte Carlo noise are suppressed, while real features are still visible (see e.g. the Si II $\lambda 6355$ line). We note, however, that the peak around 7500 \AA appears real and, as mentioned above for the D-DET model, is associated with O I $\lambda 7774$, Si II $\lambda 7849$ and Mg II $\lambda 7887$. The origin of this feature will be investigated in Section 5.4.

5.3.3 Violent merger model

The upper panels of Fig. 5.10 reports flux spectra at 21 days after explosion (around B -band maximum light) for the VM-11-09 model viewed along the five orientations chosen in Section 5.2. As expected, we find the same strong viewing-angle dependences reported for the spectra by Pakmor et al. (2012, see Section 1.4.3). Packets escaping away from the equatorial plane (along \mathbf{m}_1 or \mathbf{m}_5) sweep out a larger velocity range in their journey to the observer compared to those escaping in the equatorial plane (see the ejecta distributions in the right panels of Fig. 5.1 and Fig. 5.2) and the correspond-

Figure 5.10: Flux (top) and polarisation Q_{rot} (middle) and U_{rot} (lower) spectra extracted for the VM-11-09 model at 21 d after explosion (B -band maximum light). Left panels show spectra calculated along the equatorial viewing angles \mathbf{m}_2 – \mathbf{m}_4 , while right panels those along the \mathbf{m}_1 and \mathbf{m}_5 orientations (see lower panels of Fig. 5.3). Polarisation U_{rot} spectra reflect deviations from a single-axis geometry (see discussion in Section 4.3). The error bars mark the averaged Monte Carlo noise level in the polarisation spectra – estimated as explained in Section 4.3 – below (blue) and above (red) 6400 Å. Polarisation spectra are Savitzky-Golay filtered using a first-order polynomial and a window of 3 pixels (~ 50 Å) for clarity. The model flux is given for a distance of 1 Mpc.

Figure 5.11: Same as Fig. 5.8 but for the VM-11-09 model. Note that the scale of the Q/U planes for the equatorial viewing angles $m_2 - m_4$ (top panels) is twice smaller than that for the m_1 and m_5 orientations (lower panels). For the m_1 orientation, we associate individual loops or structures in the Q/U plane with specific features in the spectra (see text).

ing spectra are therefore affected by broader features and stronger blending of lines. In addition, the projected areas of the ^{56}Ni along m_1 and m_5 are smaller than those along the chosen equatorial directions and this, together with the higher opacity seen by the escaping packets, translates into fainter spectra. Despite this general trend, the spectrum seen down the cavity (along m_3) is fainter than the other two equatorial viewing angles because less IGE material is located on the side near the observer. Compared to the other four orientations, the spectrum extracted along m_3 is also markedly different, in the sense that it is characterised by much weaker and less blue-shifted absorption lines. The latter results were also predicted by Kasen et al. (2004) for a somewhat similar situation in which a companion star in the single-degenerate scenario carves out a hole in the ejecta of an exploding WD (see Section 2.5). Unlike our model, however, Kasen et al. (2004) adopted a density profile that leads to lines-of-sight through the hole having a lower-than-average column density (see their fig. 1). Therefore, they predict spectra that are typically brighter when viewed through the hole, in contrast with what we see in our model.

As expected from the asymmetric distribution of the ejecta, non-zero polarisation levels are obtained for all the five chosen viewing angles. In particular, the symmetry about the orbital plane results in data points distributed along a dominant axis in the Q/U planes of \mathbf{m}_2 , \mathbf{m}_3 and \mathbf{m}_4 (upper panels in Fig. 5.11): the up/down near symmetry causes every contribution to U from the northern hemisphere to be approximately canceled by a contribution in the southern hemisphere and the U values are therefore consistent with zero. The polarisation angles derived by linear fitting in the Q/U planes are small ($|\chi| = \frac{1}{2} |\alpha_{\text{rot}}| \lesssim 3.2^\circ$) which, for these specific orientations, corresponds to an electric field oscillating almost perpendicular to the equatorial plane (see Fig. 2.2). In contrast, we do not see clear dominant axes for orientations out of the equatorial plane. In particular, Q/U planes for such viewing angles are characterised by loops associated with different spectral features, mainly Si II and Ca II. As described in Section 2.3.3, this behaviour is reflective of deviations from axial symmetry in the calcium and silicon projected distribution when viewed from these orientations. For instance, we see two distinct loops in the blue region below 4000 \AA when the system is viewed pole-on (along \mathbf{m}_1): the bluer loop is associated with the Si II $\lambda 3859$ line and shows a polarisation angle comparable to that of the Si II $\lambda 6355$ feature ($\chi \sim -30^\circ$); the redder loop is instead associated with the Ca H and K line and shows a polarisation angle comparable to that of the Ca II IR triplet ($\chi \sim -10^\circ$).

In the lower panels of Fig. 5.10 we show polarisation spectra Q_{rot} and U_{rot} for each of the five observer orientations. Because of the ejecta symmetry about the equatorial plane, almost all the polarisation signal for \mathbf{m}_2 , \mathbf{m}_3 and \mathbf{m}_4 (left panels) is found in the Q_{rot} spectra. Most of the signal in U_{rot} , instead, is consistent with the inferred Monte Carlo noise level (see Section 4.3) of about 0.11 and 0.17 per cent below and above 6400 \AA , respectively. In contrast, the departures from a single-axis geometry observed in the Q/U planes of \mathbf{m}_1 and \mathbf{m}_5 cause the polarisation signals of these orientations to be carried by both Q_{rot} and U_{rot} .

Compared to the D-DET and the N100-DDT models, the polarisation signals in the pseudo-continuum spectral range $6400 - 7200 \text{ \AA}$ are relatively strong for all the directions in the VM-11-09 model. This is because the inner regions of the ejecta – from which most of the electron-scattered polarising contributions originate (see middle panel Fig. 5.5) – are more asymmetric in the VM-11-09 compared to the other two models (see Figs. 5.1 and 5.2). Specifically, polarisation levels are modest (~ 0.3 per cent) for orientations in the equatorial plane ($\mathbf{m}_2 - \mathbf{m}_4$), while higher (0.5–1 per cent) for spectra extracted along \mathbf{m}_1 and \mathbf{m}_5 . Polarisation spectra for all the orientations are characterised by strong (1–2 per cent) peaks associated with blue-shifted absorption troughs of spectral lines. While the identification to individual transitions is obvious

Figure 5.12: Same as Fig 5.6 but for the VM-11-09 model viewed along the m_2 (upper panels) and m_4 (lower panels) orientations.

for some polarisation features (e.g. for Si II and Ca II lines), it is less clear in the blue region between 4000 and 5000 Å that is affected by stronger line blending.

Compared to the angular binning approach used by Pakmor et al. (2012), the EBT described in Section 3.4.2 allows us to extract spectra with lower Monte Carlo noise and thus to clearly identify weak lines in the red region of the spectrum. For instance, by combining information from intensity and polarisation spectra we attribute two features in the range 6200–7300 Å to C II λ 6580 and C II λ 7234 (see Fig. 5.12). While the C II λ 6580 feature along the \mathbf{m}_2 direction (upper panels) is predicted in our simulations as a notch in the emission wing of the Si II λ 6355 profile, the polarisation counterpart is not seen. This effect might be due to a balance between polarising contributions from the C II absorption trough and depolarising contributions from the Si II emission wing. Despite being weak and hard to see in the flux spectrum, however, the C II λ 7234 line does clearly show up in polarisation with ~ 1 per cent level at peak. These carbon features shows up even more clearly when the system is viewed from the \mathbf{m}_4 orientation (lower panels). Here, the polarisation peak associated with C II λ 7234 is unequivocal and we also see evidence of a polarisation signature across the C II λ 6580 line.

Carbon features are not seen in flux and polarisation spectra of the D-DET and N100-DDT models. In these models, carbon material is left unburned in the outer regions of the ejecta ($\gtrsim 13\,000$ km s $^{-1}$, see Figs. 5.1 and 5.2) where the densities are relatively low. Therefore, opacities of carbon lines are typically too small to produce any appreciable signature in the spectra. In contrast, C II lines predicted by the VM-11-09 model are found at rather low velocities ($v \sim -6800$ km s $^{-1}$ along \mathbf{m}_2 and $v \sim -6100$ km s $^{-1}$ along \mathbf{m}_4) and are therefore associated with unburned carbon material from the companion star in inner regions of the ejecta where densities are relatively high (see right panels of Figs. 5.1 and 5.2). These features are not normally observed at such low velocities ($v_{\text{obs}} \sim -12\,000$ km s $^{-1}$; Parrent et al. 2011; Thomas et al. 2011) or detected in polarisation (see e.g. Wang & Wheeler 2008).

5.4 Linking polarisation to the ejecta geometry

In this section, we will examine more closely the explosion models presented above and investigate how asymmetries in their element distributions are linked to individual polarisation features. In particular, we focus on two examples. In Section 5.4.1, we first investigate the link between the calcium distribution in the ejecta and the polarisation signatures detected across the Ca II IR triplet profile. In Section 5.4.2, we then look at the oxygen, magnesium and silicon morphologies to understand which of these elements are responsible for the polarisation features observed around 7500 Å (see Section 5.3). We frame our discussion in terms of the physical picture in which polarisation

variations across spectral lines can be understood as resulting from partial covering of the electron-scattering photosphere caused by the asymmetric distributions of elements in the ejecta (see Section 2.3.2).

We will present this as a comparative study and, for simplicity, investigate polarisation features for only two exemplifying cases: the 2D D-DET and the 3D N100-DDT model. These explosion models are selected as – unlike the VM-11-09 model – they produce rather small polarisation levels that are in better agreement with spectropolarimetric data of normal SNe Ia (see also Section 5.6). Due to differences in both the ignition configuration and combustion front propagation (see Section 1.4.3), the D-DET and the N100-DDT models are characterised by relatively different ejecta distributions. In the former, *large-scale* asymmetries are produced as a consequence of the single-point ignition of the helium shell and the off-centred ignition of the CO core (see also Section 5.1.1). In the latter, while a global symmetry is found as a result of the specific ignition configuration, *small-scale* asymmetries are created by turbulent motions during the deflagration phase (see Section 5.1.2). This comparative study can thus help assessing the extent to which these two explosion models can be distinguished based on their polarimetric signatures.

5.4.1 Interpreting the Ca II IR polarisation feature

In the D-DET model, the distributions of products from the helium-shell detonation are largely aspherical. This is a consequence of the single-point ignition on the $+z$ axis, which causes these elements to be distributed over a larger velocity range in the upper compared to the lower hemisphere (see Section 5.1.1). An important yield from the shell detonation is calcium. As shown in Fig. 5.13, the polarisation signature extracted across the Ca II IR triplet in the \mathbf{I}_1 direction is characterised by a transition from positive to negative Q_{rot} levels at around 7830 \AA (corresponding to velocities of about $-23\,500 \text{ km s}^{-1}$). This transition can be understood by inspecting the calcium distribution in the ejecta more closely. The colour maps in the right panels of Fig. 5.13 present column densities (N) for Ca calculated through the near-side hemisphere of the ejecta along the \mathbf{I}_1 direction. We first notice that the distribution of calcium at very high velocities ($-26\,000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, map A) preferentially covers the top side of the ejecta as viewed from the \mathbf{I}_1 orientation. Most of the electron-scattered contributions from this side of the ejecta – mainly polarised in the negative Q_{rot} direction – are thus absorbed by calcium and do not reach the observer. As a result, positive contributions from the left and right side of the ejecta dominate the signal and produce a polarisation peak with $Q_{\text{rot}} > 0$ in the Ca II IR triplet profile. Owing to the high large-scale asymmetries in the

Figure 5.13: Colour maps of the oxygen, magnesium, silicon (top panels) and calcium (right panels) column densities N calculated through the near-side hemisphere of the ejecta in the D-DET \mathbf{I}_1 direction. As shown by the grey areas in the Q_{rot} spectrum (bottom-left panel), column densities in each map are integrated over different velocity ranges through the ejecta to enclose the polarisation peaks in the Ca II IR triplet profile (map A and map B) and the feature around 7500 Å (map C). White circles mark a projected velocity of 15 000 km s $^{-1}$, within which most of the electron-scattering contributions originate (see middle panel Fig. 5.5). For each map, regions of the ejecta dominating the polarisation signal are indicated with Q_{rot}^+ or Q_{rot}^- if their contribution to Q_{rot} is positive or negative, respectively. The column densities of each map are scaled by the maximum value. Due to the axial symmetry of the D-DET model, maps display a left-right symmetry.

D-DET model, moving deeper into the ejecta ($-21\,500$ km s $^{-1}$, map B) leads to a significant change in the projected calcium distribution. Specifically, we notice that here the top, left and right sides are associated with larger opacities compared to the bottom side. Hence, packets are more likely to escape from the bottom side of the ejecta and bias the polarisation signal towards negative values ($Q_{\text{rot}} < 0$) in the Ca II IR profile.

In the N100-DDT model, positive Q_{rot} polarisation levels are detected across the Ca II IR profile for the N100-DDT \mathbf{n}_1 direction (see bottom panels of Fig. 5.14). In particular, no transition from positive to negative Q_{rot} is seen as was the case for the

Figure 5.14: Same as Fig. 5.13, but for the N100-DDT viewed along the \mathbf{n}_1 direction. Colour maps have been rotated of $\alpha_{\text{rot}}/2 = 83.65^\circ$ (see top left panel of Fig. 5.8) in the clock-wise direction to account for the transformation of Q and U to Q_{rot} and U_{rot} (see Section 4.3).

D-DET model. This is because lacking a large-scale asymmetry such as that seen in the D-DET shell, the N100-DDT model is characterised by calcium column densities maps that are relatively similar at different velocities in the ejecta. As shown in map A of Fig. 5.14, the positive signal observed in Q_{rot} along the \mathbf{n}_1 orientation is readily understood. When viewed from this direction, the asymmetric distribution of calcium offers higher opacities to packets escaping towards the observer from the bottom side of the ejecta. As a result, the polarisation signal across the Ca II IR profile is dominated by contributions coming from the left and right sides and thus biased towards positive values.

5.4.2 Interpreting the O I / Si II / Mg II polarisation feature

As pointed out in Section 5.3, spectra extracted for both the D-DET and N100-DDT models are characterised by a clear polarisation feature around 7500 Å. Three spectral transitions can be responsible for the variation in polarisation across this spectral region: O I λ 7774, Si II λ 7849 or Mg II λ 7887. A closer look at the oxygen, magnesium and silicon distributions in the ejecta can help us investigate what is the origin of this feature.

In the D-DET model, this feature is polarised in the negative Q_{rot} direction when viewed from the \mathbf{I}_1 orientation (Fig. 5.13), meaning that its polarisation angle is 90° rotated from most of the other features in the spectrum (e.g. the Si II λ 6355 line, see Fig. 5.6). As shown in the upper panels of Fig. 5.13, two distinct behaviours are seen in the distributions of oxygen, magnesium and silicon: the asymmetric distributions of magnesium and silicon will cause positive contributions from the left and right sides of the ejecta to dominate the polarisation signal¹. On the other hand, the distribution of oxygen will favour negative contributions (from the top side of the ejecta) dominating the signal. Therefore – although all the three aforementioned transitions are expected to affect the degree of polarisation to some extent – we confirm that the polarisation signal extracted around 7500 Å in the \mathbf{I}_1 direction is dominated by O I λ 7774. This identification explains why we see a 90° rotation between the feature around 7500 Å and the silicon lines (e.g. Si II λ 5972 and Si II λ 6355, see Fig. 5.6).

In the N100-DDT model, the 7500 Å feature is polarised in the positive Q_{rot} direction when viewed from the \mathbf{n}_1 viewing angle (Fig. 5.14). As shown in the top panels (maps B), magnesium and silicon column densities extracted along \mathbf{n}_1 are higher on the bottom side of the ejecta, thus favouring positive contributions to dominate the Q_{rot} polarisation signal. In a similar way to what is seen in the D-DET model, oxygen shows instead a distinct distribution, preferentially absorbing packets from the right side of the ejecta and thus biasing the Q_{rot} polarisation signal towards negative values. Based on this analysis, we therefore suggest that – unlike what is seen for the D-DET model – the polarisation signal across the 7500 Å feature is dominated by Si II λ 7849 and Mg II λ 7887. Although the contribution of O I λ 7774 appears not to be dominant in this case – i.e. around maximum light and towards the \mathbf{n}_1 observer orientation – we note that the same might not be true for different directions and at different epochs (see Section 5.6.3).

¹Note that this is consistent with the positive signals detected across the silicon lines, see Fig. 5.6.

5.5 Polarisation evolution

As mentioned in Section 5.2, spectra for each model are extracted between 10 and 30 d after explosion and thus the temporal evolution of the polarisation signal can be investigated in detail. The fact that the observed polarisation signal in normal SNe Ia typically decreases from pre- to post-maximum (see Section 2.4.2) offers an important constraint for models, and thus the time evolution of polarisation in our simulations can become an additional discrimination factor between the models. Specifically, in this section we use Eq. (4.4) and calculate intensity (I^*) and polarisation (Q_{rot}^* and U_{rot}^*) light curves over three different spectral ranges: from 3500 to 5900 Å (“blue” range), from 5900 to 6300 Å (Si II λ 6355 range) and from 6400 to 7200 Å (pseudo-continuum range). These ranges are selected to encompass different spectral regions and to study how the polarisation signal (and its time evolution) changes as a function of wavelength. Given that Monte Carlo noise levels integrated in these three wavelength ranges are low for all the models – ranging from ~ 0.004 in the blue to ~ 0.05 per cent in the red – polarisation bias (see Section 4.3) is less an issue here. Therefore, in this section we restrict our discussion to the time evolution of the integrated polarisation percentage P^* defined as

$$P^*(t) = \frac{\sqrt{Q_{\text{rot}}^*(t)^2 + U_{\text{rot}}^*(t)^2}}{I^*(t)}. \quad (5.1)$$

Fig. 5.15 reports P^* between -5 and $+5$ d relative to maximum light for the D-DET, N100-DDT and VM-11-09 models in the three selected ranges.

In line with what is seen at maximum light (Section 5.3), we find similar polarisation levels for the D-DET and the N100-DDT model in all ranges and at all epochs. In particular, the D-DET model shows very low degrees of polarisation ($\lesssim 0.2$ per cent) for all the orientations investigated, while the N100-DDT model is more orientation-dependent and is characterised by slightly larger values ($\lesssim 0.4$ per cent). We notice, instead, a more extreme behaviour for the VM-11-09 model. This model is characterised by a strong viewing-angle dependence at all wavelengths, with polarisation that varies from ~ 0.1 – 0.5 per cent along the equatorial directions ($\mathbf{m}_2 - \mathbf{m}_4$) to levels $\gtrsim 1$ per cent along the remaining two orientations (\mathbf{m}_1 and \mathbf{m}_5). This is consistent with the stronger ejecta asymmetries produced by the VM-11-09 compared to the D-DET and N100-DDT models.

A distinct behaviour between the VM-11-09 and the other two models is also seen in the temporal evolution of the polarisation signal. For most of the orientations, polarisation levels for the D-DET and the N100-DDT models reach their peak between 0 and 5 d before B -band maximum light and decrease thereafter. While similar predictions

Figure 5.15: Polarisation light curves between -5 and $+5$ d relative to B -band maximum light calculated in three different wavelength ranges: 3500–5900 Å (left-hand panel, “blue” range), 5900–6300 Å (middle panel, around the Si II $\lambda 6355$ line) and 6400–7200 Å (right-hand panel, pseudo-continuum range). Monte Carlo noise levels for the D-DET model around maximum light are ~ 0.004 , 0.015 and 0.019 per cent in the left-hand, middle and right-hand panel, respectively. Similar noise levels are found for the N100-DDT (0.004, 0.016 and 0.028) and the VM-11-09 (0.012, 0.049 and 0.036) model. For the VM-11-09 model, stars denote orientations \mathbf{m}_1 and \mathbf{m}_5 , while diamonds equatorial viewing angles $\mathbf{m}_2 - \mathbf{m}_4$.

are also found for the equatorial orientations $\mathbf{m}_2 - \mathbf{m}_4$ in the VM-11-09 model, polarisation light curves for the \mathbf{m}_1 and \mathbf{m}_5 show a different behaviour and typically increase from -5 to $+5$ d relative to maximum light. For instance, the degrees of polarisation extracted in the pseudo-continuum region $6400-7200 \text{ \AA}$ (right panel of Fig. 5.15) for both the D-DET and the N100-DDT model decrease from a maximum of $\sim 0.1-0.3$ per cent before peak to lower values at later times. In contrast, the VM-11-09 \mathbf{m}_1 and \mathbf{m}_5 viewing angles are associated with stronger polarisation signals that are still increasing 5 d after maximum. Both in terms of absolute values and temporal evolution, polarisation levels extracted in the pseudo-continuum for the D-DET and the N100-DDT models and for the $\mathbf{m}_2 - \mathbf{m}_4$ orientations in the VM-11-09 model are in strikingly good agreement with spectropolarimetric observations of SNe Ia (see Section 2.4).

The different time evolution behaviour between the VM-11-09 and the D-DET and N100-DDT model can be understood by noting that, as time passes, the electron-scattering photosphere moves inward in velocity space and therefore polarising contributions originate in inner regions of the ejecta. For our simulations, this is shown in Fig. 5.5. In the VM-11-09 model, for instance, the distribution of polarising contributions peaks at $\sim 11\,000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ at 5 d before maximum while at $\sim 7\,000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ 10 d after. The influence of the secondary star in this model makes the inner regions of the density distribution much more asymmetric than the outer ones (see right panels of Figs 5.1 and 5.2), and thus polarisation levels become stronger from -5 to $+5$ relative to maximum. In contrast, inner regions of the density distributions are typically more spherical than the outer regions in the D-DET and N100-DDT model (see left and middle panels of Figs 5.1 and 5.2). This, together with the decrease in the electron-scattering opacity as time passes, leads to polarisation levels that become smaller from pre- to post-maximum.

A closer look at Fig. 5.15 highlights an additional distinction between the VM-11-09 and the other two models. Both the D-DET and the N100-DDT model are characterised by an *increase* in the degree of polarisation with wavelength, a behaviour that can not be ascribed solely to Monte Carlo noise growing from blue to red regions of the spectra (see above). In contrast, most of the orientations investigated in the VM-11-09 model show the opposite behaviour, producing polarisation signals that *decrease* at redder wavelengths. The former behaviour provides a better match with what is usually observed in both normal (e.g. Wang et al. 1997) and sub-luminous (e.g. Howell et al. 2001) SNe Ia (see Section 2.4). Our calculations suggest that the wavelength dependence in the overall polarisation signal can be ascribed to the relative contribution between electron-scattering and line opacity in different regions of the spectra. In the D-DET (N100-DDT) model, the fraction of escaping packets having a line interaction (that is a depolarising interaction, see Section 2.2.2) as last event increases

from 0.38 (0.23) at 7000 Å to 0.82 (0.81) at 4000 Å. That is, blue wavelengths suffer strong line blanketing that causes a decrease in the overall polarisation level. In the VM-11-09 model, instead, the same effect is weaker, with the relative fraction of packets whose last event was a line interaction increasing from 0.18 at 7000 Å to only 0.51 at 4000 Å. A possible explanation for the weaker line blanketing in the VM-11-09 model is given by the particular “apple-like” distribution of IGE material in the ejecta (see Fig. 5.1). Except for viewing angles close to the $+z$ and $-z$ directions, most of the orientations – and particularly those near the cavity created by the secondary star – are associated with relatively small IGE opacities and are therefore affected by a weak line blanketing.

5.6 Comparison with observations

In Sections 5.3–5.5, we have presented results of our simulations and described polarisation features and their time evolution for the D-DET, N100-DDT and VM-11-09 models. Here we compare synthetic observables extracted from our models with spectropolarimetric data of normal SNe Ia. In Section 5.6.1, we first present comparisons of our model predictions with three individual SNe Ia observed at multiple epochs and with high signal-to-noise. In the subsequent sections, we then focus our attention on polarisation signals predicted across specific spectral features and compare them to those observed in the currently available spectropolarimetric data of normal SNe Ia. Specifically, we study the Si II $\lambda 6355$ line (Section 5.6.2), the O I / Si II / Mg II feature around 7500 Å (Section 5.6.3) and the Ca II IR profile (Section 5.6.4). Polarisation values P are used throughout this section, as has been common practice in previous studies including those that present the observational work to which we will compare (see also Section 4.3).

5.6.1 Comparison with Type Ia supernova polarisation spectra

The sample of normal SNe Ia with multiple-epoch and high signal-to-noise spectropolarimetry is currently limited to a handful of objects (see Section 2.4.2). Among these, we select SN 2012fr, SN 2001el and SN 2004dt and compare polarisation spectra observed for these objects with those predicted by the D-DET, N100-DDT and VM-11-09 models. Along with their good data quality, these three SNe are chosen as they span a polarisation range that encompasses the distribution observed for normal SNe Ia, going from the rather low levels observed for SN 2012fr to a high degree of polarisation in SN 2004dt (see also Section 2.4). Unless otherwise stated, we present synthetic spectra for the three orientations (one for each model) that provide best matches with observed flux and polarisation spectra. We note, however, that spectra in better

agreement with observations might be found for viewing angles not investigated in this study.

SN 2012fr

SN 2012fr was observed in polarisation using the Focal Reducer and low dispersion Spectrograph (FORS1) at the ESO Very Large Telescope (VLT). Polarisation levels were found to be generally very small (~ 0.1 per cent in the pseudo-continuum range), although higher signals of ~ 0.5 – 0.6 per cent were detected across the Si II $\lambda 6355$ and Ca II IR triplet features (Maund et al. 2013). In particular, a clear transition from high- (pre-maximum) to low- (post-maximum) velocity components was observed in the calcium profile (see Section 2.4.2).

In Fig. 5.16, we show spectropolarimetric data of SN 2012fr at -5 and $+2$ d relative to B -band maximum together with synthetic spectra extracted for the three explosion models at the same epochs. The \mathbf{l}_2 (upper panels), \mathbf{n}_3 (middle panels) and \mathbf{m}_4 (lower panels) orientations provide the best match between observed spectra and those predicted for the D-DET, N100-DDT and VM-11-09 model, respectively.

- D-DET model. There is a remarkably good match between the D-DET model and SN 2012fr at both epochs. Flux spectra of SN 2012fr are reproduced rather well by this model, both in terms of spectral shapes and velocities. The agreement is particularly good at 5 d before maximum, although we note two important discrepancies: the flux spectrum is too red and the velocity of Ca II IR triplet too low in our simulations. As discussed by Kromer et al. (2010), the red colour can be attributed to the composition of the burning yields in the outer shell (see Section 1.4.3). Specifically, the moderate amount of IGEs produced in the helium shell (see left-hand panels in Fig. 5.1) leads to strong line blanketing in the blue spectral regions and flux redistribution to redder wavelengths (see also discussion in Section 5.3.1). The discrepancy in the velocity of the Ca II IR triplet is directly related to the specific distribution of calcium in the outer regions of the D-DET ejecta. Velocities of $\sim 17\,000$ km s $^{-1}$ measured in the synthetic profile are consistent with the calcium opacity predicted along the \mathbf{l}_2 orientation (see Fig. 5.1), but too small to reproduce those observed in the high-velocity features of SN 2012fr ($\sim 20\,000$ km s $^{-1}$, but see also Section 5.6.4). The agreement between the D-DET model and observations is particularly striking in terms of polarisation. The match in the pseudo-continuum range (6400 – 7200 Å) and in the bluer regions of the spectra ($\lesssim 6000$ Å) is remarkable both pre- and post-maximum. In addition, the degrees of polarisation observed across the Si II $\lambda 6355$

Figure 5.16: Flux and polarisation spectra predicted for the D-DET (upper panels, blue lines), N100-DDT (middle panels, red lines) and VM-11-09 (lower panels, black lines) models viewed from the $\mathbf{l}_2 = (1, 0, 0)$, $\mathbf{n}_3 = (-1/2, 1/2, 1/\sqrt{2})$ and $\mathbf{m}_4 = (1/\sqrt{2}, 1/\sqrt{2}, 0)$ orientations, respectively. Spectra are reported at -5 (left-hand panels) and $+2$ (right-hand panels) d relative to B -band maximum light. For comparison, grey lines show observed spectra of SN 2012fr at the same epochs after correction for the ISP component (~ 0.24 per cent; Maund et al. 2013). Grey bars mark the averaged errors in the observed polarisation spectra. Both synthetic and observed flux spectra have been normalized to their values at 6500 \AA for illustrative purposes.

line are nearly identical to those predicted by the D-DET model at -5 (~ 0.3 per cent) and $+2$ (~ 0.4 per cent) d relative to maximum. In contrast, we notice a poor match between model and data for the only other polarimetric feature clearly detected in SN 2012fr, the Ca II IR triplet. While the calcium profile in SN 2012fr is characterised by a transition from a high-velocity component to three distinct low-velocity components, our model predicts a fairly strong and broad feature 5 d before maximum that almost disappears a week after. We note, however, that since the model fails to provide a convincing match to the Ca IR triplet in the flux spectrum (see above), it is not surprising that the match in polarisation across this feature is also relatively poor. The disagreement between modelled and observed calcium profiles suggests that more work is needed to understand the origin of the high-velocity calcium features (see also discussion in Section 5.6.4).

- N100-DDT model. As shown in the middle panels of Fig. 5.16, the degree of polarisation predicted for the N100-DDT model is broadly consistent with the levels observed in SN 2012fr. The polarisation signals in the blue part of the spectrum and across the Si II $\lambda 6355$ profile agree reasonably well with the data. However, we see larger discrepancies compared to those found in the D-DET case. First, the model predicts velocities along \mathbf{n}_3 that are typically higher than those observed (e.g. 30 per cent larger for the Si II $\lambda 6355$ profile 5 d before maximum). Second, velocities for the calcium IR triplet ($\sim 13\,000$ km s $^{-1}$) are definitely too low to account for the high-velocity component observed in SN 2012fr (see also Section 5.6.4). Finally, the 6400–7200 Å pseudo-continuum range in the N100-DDT model spectrum is too highly polarised (~ 0.3 per cent) at both epochs to match the small signal of ~ 0.1 per cent detected in SN 2012fr.
- VM-11-09 model. As mentioned in the previous sections, equatorial directions $\mathbf{m}_2 - \mathbf{m}_4$ yield smaller polarisation signals compared to the \mathbf{m}_1 and \mathbf{m}_5 orientations and are thus more promising for reproducing the low levels observed in SN 2012fr. As shown in the bottom panels of Fig. 5.16, the pseudo-continuum polarisation predicted along the \mathbf{m}_4 direction at both epochs is fairly consistent² with the level observed in SN 2012fr. This suggests that the strong asymmetries in the nickel distribution of Pakmor et al. (2012) might not necessarily lead to high polarisation levels in the pseudo-continuum range (see also discussion in Section 5.3.3). However, the most striking discrepancy between the model and the data is the wealth of strong polarisation features predicted in our simulation. As highlighted in Fig. 5.10 and Fig. 5.12, these strong features are associated with the absorption troughs of spectral lines and are typically too strong to match the modest polarisation signals

²Although the model predicts that several polarised line features do form in the pseudo-continuum region.

of SN 2012fr. This fact suggests that the element distribution in the model ejecta is too asymmetric to account for the overall low levels of polarisation observed in SN 2012fr and similar SNe Ia.

Among the other equatorial directions, it is worth noting that \mathbf{m}_2 is associated with similar spectra to those extracted along \mathbf{m}_4 (see Fig. 5.10) and thus it produces relatively similar discrepancies with data of SN 2012fr. In contrast, the degree of polarisation associated with the other equatorial direction, \mathbf{m}_3 , is typically weaker and thus provides better agreement – although still imperfect – with SN 2012fr if one considers only polarisation (see figure 13 of Bulla et al. 2016a). However, the flux spectra extracted for this direction are characterised by very broad and shallow features that are clearly inconsistent with the observations of SN 2012fr. We note that, while in the D-DET model discrepancies in the flux spectra could be resolved by e.g. different composition of the helium shell (see above), it is difficult to find a resolution for those seen in the flux spectra of the VM-11-09 model along the \mathbf{m}_3 direction.

SN 2001el

Spectropolarimetric observations of SN 2001el were triggered with FORS1 at ESO VLT. A polarisation signal of ~ 0.2 – 0.3 per cent – typical for the bulk of normal SN Ia events – was detected in the pseudo-continuum range (Wang et al. 2003). Two distinct components were clearly visible in the Ca II IR triplet: a significantly polarised (~ 0.7 per cent) high-velocity component and a distinct low-velocity component polarised at ~ 0.2 – 0.3 per cent level (see also Section 2.4.2). We refer the reader to Section 2.5 for the interpretation of the SN 2001el data in terms of different idealised geometries with simple departures from spherical symmetry (Kasen et al. 2003).

In Fig. 5.17, we compare observations of SN 2001el at -7 , -2 and $+7$ d relative to B -band maximum with synthetic spectra extracted for the D-DET (upper panels), the N100-DDT (middle panels) and the VM-11-09 (lower panels) model at the same epochs. Specifically, we report the best matches found in each case, which are for the D-DET \mathbf{l}_2 , the N100-DDT \mathbf{n}_5 and the VM-11-09 \mathbf{m}_4 (lower panels) orientations.

- D-DET model. Spectra extracted for the D-DET model along the equatorial \mathbf{l}_2 orientation are broadly consistent with those observed in SN 2001el. Polarisation levels in the pseudo-continuum region and across the Si II $\lambda 6355$ profile are in good agreement with data, although velocities in the synthetic spectra are slightly larger than those observed. The most striking difference, however, concerns the Ca II IR triplet region. The calcium distribution in the outer shell of the D-DET model (see Fig. 5.1) is able

Figure 5.17: Flux and polarisation spectra predicted for the D-DET (upper panels, blue lines), N100-DDT (middle panels, red lines) and VM-11-09 (lower panels, black lines) models viewed from the $\mathbf{l}_2 = (1, 0, 0)$, $\mathbf{n}_5 = (1/\sqrt{2}, -1/\sqrt{2}, 0)$ and $\mathbf{m}_4 = (1/\sqrt{2}, 1/\sqrt{2}, 0)$ directions, respectively. Spectra are reported at -7 (left-hand panels), -2 (middle panels) and $+7$ (right-hand panels) d relative to B -band maximum light. For comparison, grey lines show observed spectra of SN 2001el at the same epochs after correction for the ISP component (~ 0.6 per cent; Wang et al. 2003). Grey bars mark the averaged errors in the observed polarisation spectra. Both synthetic and observed flux spectra have been normalized to their values at 6500 \AA for illustrative purposes.

to reproduce the high-velocity component seen in SN 2001el, but is not sufficiently asymmetric to explain the relatively high polarisation level of 0.6–0.7 per cent observed. In this respect, it is worth noting that such strong polarisation signals are predicted – at least around maximum – for the \mathbf{l}_1 orientation of the D-DET model (see for instance Fig. 5.4). However, this orientation is characterised by (i) spectra that are much too red and by (ii) a calcium line that is too strong and too fast to match the observations (see discussion in Section 5.6.4).

- N100-DDT model. Spectra extracted for the N100-DDT model along \mathbf{n}_5 agree reasonably well with data of SN 2001el, although we again notice systematically larger velocities in the model. The match is particularly good before maximum light, with the predicted spectral shape (see also Röpke et al. 2012) and degrees of polarisation found to be consistent with observations. As in the D-DET model, however, the region around the Ca II IR triplet is poorly reproduced by the N100-DDT model (see Section 5.6.4). Here, the polarisation signal is a factor of ~ 2 smaller than that observed. Furthermore, the velocity is also too slow to reproduce the high-velocity component seen in SN 2001el before maximum.
- VM-11-09 model. Similarly to what we have seen for the SN 2012fr case, the agreement between the VM-11-09 model and SN 2001el is good in terms of flux spectra while rather poor in terms of polarisation. Although the pseudo-continuum levels extracted along the \mathbf{m}_4 direction are only slightly larger than those observed, the overall polarisation signal is too high to match the levels detected in SN 2001el. In particular, several peaks polarised at 0.5 to 1 per cent levels show up in the synthetic spectra at all epochs, in clear contrast with the overall low degree of polarisation observed in SN 2001el. As already noticed in the comparison with SN 2012fr and discussed in Section 5.5, such discrepancies are more pronounced at wavelengths bluer than $\sim 6000 \text{ \AA}$.

SN 2004dt

Spectropolarimetric observations of SN 2004dt were acquired with FORS1 at ESO VLT about a week before maximum (Wang et al. 2006) and with the Shane telescope at Lick Observatory 4 d after maximum (Leonard et al. 2005). Except for the pseudo-continuum range, where degrees of polarisation typical of normal SNe Ia (~ 0.3 – 0.4 per cent) were detected, SN 2004dt displayed unusual polarisation properties. Together with a very strong (~ 2 – 2.5 per cent) peak around 3650 \AA , several features polarised at ~ 1 per cent level were observed in the blue region and attributed to Si II,

Figure 5.18: Flux and polarisation spectra predicted for the $\mathbf{I}_1 - \mathbf{I}_3$ D-DET (upper panels, blue lines), $\mathbf{n}_1 - \mathbf{n}_5$ N100-DDT (middle panels, red lines) and the \mathbf{m}_5 VM-11-09 (lower panels, black lines) orientation. Spectra are reported at -7 (left-hand panels) and $+4$ (right-hand panels) d relative to B -band maximum light. For comparison, grey lines show observed spectra of SN 2004dt at the same epochs after correction for the ISP component (~ 0.28 per cent; Leonard et al. 2005; Wang et al. 2006). Grey bars mark the averaged errors in the observed polarisation spectra. Both synthetic and observed flux spectra have been normalized to their values at 6500 \AA for illustrative purposes.

Mg II and Fe II lines (Wang et al. 2006). Furthermore, the Si II $\lambda 6355$ line was unusually strong in polarisation, with a level of ~ 1.7 – 1.8 per cent at peak (see Fig. 2.9). Taken together, these properties make SN 2004dt the most polarised SN Ia ever observed.

Fig. 5.18 shows pre- and post-maximum polarisation spectra of SN 2004dt together with those extracted for the three explosion models investigated. Specifically, for the D-DET and the N100-DDT models (upper and middle panels) we show synthetic spectra extracted for all the $\mathbf{l}_1 - \mathbf{l}_3$ and $\mathbf{n}_1 - \mathbf{n}_5$ orientations studied in this work, while for the VM-11-09 model (lower panels) present spectra predicted along \mathbf{m}_5 that provide the best match with data.

- D-DET and N100-DDT models. The agreement in the flux spectra of the models with SN 2004dt is of comparable quality to that with SN 2001el and SN 2012fr. However, we clearly see that none of the orientations investigated for the D-DET and N100-DDT model can reproduce the degrees of polarisation observed in SN 2004dt. Specifically, for both models, the synthetic spectropolarimetry hardly ever exceeds a level of 0.5 per cent, which is clearly insufficient to account for the exceptional polarisation levels of SN 2004dt.
- VM-11-09 model. Although the velocities in the VM-11-09 model along \mathbf{m}_5 are lower than those observed (e.g. $\sim -14\,500$ km s $^{-1}$ instead of $\sim -17\,000$ km s $^{-1}$ for the absorption trough of the Si II $\lambda 6355$ line 7 days before maximum), the simulated spectral shapes agree reasonably well with the data of SN 2004dt at both epochs. In particular, the agreement a week before maximum is remarkable. The polarisation level in the pseudo-continuum range 6400–7200 Å is well reproduced and the predicted line polarisation features are very similar to those observed. The match is particularly good for the silicon lines (e.g. Si II $\lambda 3859$, Si II $\lambda 5979$ and Si II $\lambda 6355$). In contrast, the model produces a degree of polarisation that is too high in the region around 5000 Å.

Synthetic spectra 4 days after maximum are still consistent with data for SN 2004dt, though with stronger deviations. The most striking difference concerns the region across the Ca II IR triplet feature, which appears to be too strong in the model. The fact that the calcium line is also prominent in the flux spectrum, however, suggests that the discrepancy might be ascribed to the simplified excitation/ionisation approximation of ARTIS (Kromer & Sim 2009), rather than only to the geometry of the model.

The comparison of our three explosion models with SN 2012fr, SN 2001el and SN 2004dt has clearly highlighted the power of spectropolarimetry. Indeed, while all

Figure 5.19: Flux and polarisation spectra for the N100-DDT n_5 (red) and the VM-11-09 m_5 (black) orientations 2 d before maximum light, together with spectra observed for SN 2001el at the same epoch (grey).

the models reproduce the flux spectra observed for each SN reasonably well, polarisation does provide a clear distinction. This is shown in Fig. 5.19, where we plot flux and polarisation spectra around maximum light for the N100-DDT and VM-11-09 models, together with spectra for SN 2001el at similar epochs. As already pointed out by Röpke et al. (2012, see also Section 1.5 and Fig. 1.9), flux spectra extracted for these two models are very similar to each other and reproduce flux spectra observed for normal SNe Ia comparably well (top panel). Based on a flux spectra comparison only, it would then be hard to favour one model over the other. We instead find a striking difference between the two models in terms of polarisation spectra (bottom panel). Polarisation levels extracted for the N100-DDT model are typically below 0.5 per cent, while those predicted for the VM-11-09 model are generally larger than 0.5 per cent and reach values up to ~ 2 per cent across the Si II $\lambda 6355$ and the Ca II IR lines and ~ 4 per cent across the Ca II H and K feature. Because of this clear distinction in the predicted polarisation spectra, comparison with data is much more effective in discriminating between the

two models. Indeed, as shown in this section, the low polarisation signals extracted for the N100-DDT model are in much better agreement with those observed for the bulk of normal SNe Ia and thus favour this model over the VM-11-09 model (see also Section 5.6.2).

While in this section we have compared our model predictions with polarisation data of three individual SNe Ia, in the following sections we will investigate polarisation levels extracted across specific spectral features and present comparisons with SN Ia population properties.

5.6.2 Distribution of polarisation of the Si II $\lambda 6355$ feature

As discussed in Section 2.4.2, the Si II $\lambda 6355$ line is typically found to be polarised in SNe Ia. In this section, we compare the distribution of values observed in normal SNe Ia with those predicted in this study for the D-DET, the N100-DDT and the VM-11-09 model. Observed values include 16 normal SNe Ia from Wang et al. (2007), SN 2006X from Patat et al. (2009), SN 2012fr from Maund et al. (2013) and SN 2014J from Patat et al. (2014) and Porter et al. (2016). To facilitate the comparison with data, we follow the convention of Wang et al. (2007) and present synthetic polarisation values estimated via Gaussian fitting of the Si II $\lambda 6355$ profile at 5 d before B -band maximum light. To explore the full range of polarisation covered by each model, here we also include predictions from our low signal-to-noise calculations with spectra extracted for an additional 17 (D-DET), 21 (N100-DDT) and 30 (VM-11-09) orientations (see Section 5.2).

Fig. 5.20 shows the solid-angle-weighted distribution of Si II $\lambda 6355$ polarisation values extracted for our models compared to those detected in normal SN Ia events. This comparison clearly demonstrates that the D-DET and the N100-DDT models produce polarisation signals in a range ($\lesssim 1$ per cent) comparable to the values observed. Although the range of polarisation predicted by the two models is relatively similar, the D-DET model typically produces lower levels of polarisation than the N100-DDT model (in line with the findings of Section 5.3 and Section 5.5) and it provides a good match with observed SNe at the low-polarisation end of the distribution. Nonetheless, neither the D-DET nor the N100-DDT model can account for the relatively high Si II $\lambda 6355$ polarisation levels ($\gtrsim 1$ per cent) observed in a handful of SNe Ia (Wang et al. 2007; Patat et al. 2009). As discussed in Section 2.4, however, polarisation signals for objects at the upper end of the distribution are associated with high photospheric velocities of the Si II $\lambda 6355$ profile. As neither the D-DET nor the N100-DDT explosion model are able to produce high velocities in the Si II $\lambda 6355$ line, it is not surprising that the match in polarisation with these relatively highly-polarised

Figure 5.20: Solid-angle-weighted distribution of Si λ 6355 polarisation at 5 d before B -band maximum for the D-DET (blue distribution), the N100-DDT (red distribution) and the VM-11-09 (dashed black distribution) models, together with the distribution of values observed for normal SNe Ia (grey distribution, Wang et al. 2007; Patat et al. 2009; Maund et al. 2013; Patat et al. 2014; Porter et al. 2016). The distribution of each explosion model includes orientations from both high and low signal-to-noise calculations (see Section 5.2).

objects is also poor. Despite predicting Si λ 6355 velocities that are smaller than those observed – as is the case for the D-DET and N100-DDT models – the VM-11-09 model provides a better match to highly-polarised objects for a few orientations (e.g. the \mathbf{m}_5 direction, see Fig. 5.18). This latter model, however, is associated with silicon lines that are typically too highly polarised, with levels above 1.75 per cent for about half of the orientations.

5.6.3 Polarisation of the O I / Si II / Mg II feature

Unlike the cases of Si II and Ca II, no unambiguous polarisation signature has ever been observed for the O I feature in SNe Ia (Wang & Wheeler 2008). However, as mentioned in Section 2.4.2, oxygen is found at similar velocities to those seen for silicon and calcium lines, and thus the lack of polarisation across the O I λ 7774 line has been interpreted as a proof that aspherically-distributed IMEs might share the same velocity space of a more spherically-distributed oxygen layer (Wang et al. 2006; Höflich et al. 2006).

As shown in the left and middle panels of Fig. 5.1 and Fig. 5.2, the distribution of oxygen, calcium and silicon in the ejecta of the D-DET and the N100-DDT models is consistent with this interpretation. Indeed, as expected, the more spherical distribution of oxygen, compared to those of silicon and calcium, results in weaker polarisation levels across the O I $\lambda 7774$ region than across the Si II and Ca II lines. Despite being weak, however, polarisation signatures in the O I $\lambda 7774$ wavelength region are clearly discernible in both our models and may be detectable with slightly more sensitive spectropolarimetric observations. This is shown in Fig. 5.21, where we present a zoom into the O I $\lambda 7774$ region for the observed spectra of SN 2012fr (bottom right panel) and the synthetic spectra predicted by the D-DET and N100-DDT models (top panels). Spectra are reported at 5 d before maximum and are the same as in the left-hand panels of Fig. 5.16. Polarisation peaks at the 0.3 and 0.4 per cent level are predicted across this spectral region by both explosion models. In particular, a similar analysis to that presented in Section 5.4 suggests that the polarisation signal across this feature is dominated by O I $\lambda 7774$ for both these orientation/model/epoch combinations, and the predicted velocities for this feature are $\sim -10\,000$ km s $^{-1}$ for the D-DET and $\sim -17\,000$ km s $^{-1}$ for the N100-DDT model. Although Maund et al. (2013) did not discuss any possible signal associated with O I $\lambda 7774$, we notice a marginal increase in the polarisation levels up to ~ 0.2 – 0.3 per cent between $-10\,000$ and $-15\,000$ km s $^{-1}$ that, owing to the resemblance with the predicted profiles, might be associated with O I $\lambda 7774$.

At variance with the D-DET and N100-DDT model, the distribution of oxygen in the VM-11-09 model is more aspherical (see right panels of Fig. 5.1 and Fig. 5.2) and therefore produces a stronger polarisation signature across the O I $\lambda 7774$ line (0.5–0.6 per cent, see bottom-left panel of Fig. 5.21). In particular, the polarisation feature peaks at $\sim -6\,000$ km s $^{-1}$ and thus can be associated with oxygen material from the companion star (cf. with Fig. 5.1). The identification of this feature with the secondary star is consistent with that made around maximum light for the polarisation signatures of unburned carbon (see discussion in Section 5.3.3).

Overall, we conclude that the spectral region around the O I / Si II / Mg II feature is an interesting target for future spectropolarimetric observations since the models predict that weak signatures may be present here. In addition, predictions from the D-DET model suggest that these signatures may be observed rotated by 90° with respect to Si II $\lambda 6355$, Ca II IR and other lines in the spectrum. However, we caution that interpretation will be complicated by the competing roles of the O I, Si II and Mg II spectral features in this range for which the relative contributions is likely to vary as a function of epoch and observer orientation, as highlighted by the discussion in Sec-

Figure 5.21: Polarisation spectra (solid lines) around the $O\text{I } \lambda 7774$ feature at 5 d before maximum. Spectra extracted for the D-DET \mathbf{l}_2 (top left panel), the N100-DDT \mathbf{n}_3 (top right panel) and the VM-11-09 \mathbf{m}_4 (bottom left panel) orientations are reported together with those observed for SN 2012fr (bottom right panel). Flux spectra are arbitrarily scaled for presentation and reported with dashed lines in each panel. Error bars mark the uncertainties on the synthetic and observed polarisation spectra.

tion 5.4.

5.6.4 Polarisation of the Ca II IR triplet feature

As shown in Section 5.6.1, our explosion models fail to reproduce the polarisation signatures observed in SNe Ia across the Ca II IR triplet feature. The disagreement is particularly evident across the high-velocity ($\sim 15\,000\text{--}20\,000\text{ km s}^{-1}$) components of this line that are frequently detected in both intensity (e.g. Mazzali et al. 2005a,b; Blondin et al. 2013; Childress et al. 2014; Maguire et al. 2014; Silverman et al. 2015; Zhao et al. 2015) and polarisation (e.g. Wang et al. 2003; Maund et al. 2013) spectra of SNe Ia (see also Section 2.4).

As highlighted by the spectral comparison with SN 2001el (Fig. 5.17) and SN 2012fr (Fig. 5.16), the N100-DDT and VM-11-09 models are not able to reproduce velocities and polarimetric properties observed in the data. For the N100-DDT model, typical values for the velocities ($\sim 12\,000\text{--}15\,000\text{ km s}^{-1}$) and the polarisation signals (~ 0.3 per cent) are too low to match the observations. This comes as no surprise, since the calcium distribution in the ejecta of this model extends up to $\sim 15\,000\text{ km s}^{-1}$ and is not strongly asymmetric (see Fig. 5.1 and Fig. 5.2). For the VM-11-09 model velocities are also too low ($\sim 7\,000\text{--}15\,000\text{ km s}^{-1}$) but the polarisation signatures is now generally too strong (~ 1 per cent) as a consequence of the asymmetric distribution of calcium in the ejecta (see Fig. 5.1).

The D-DET model appears more promising for matching the calcium high-velocity components since the distribution of calcium in this model can reach up to $\sim 30\,000\text{ km s}^{-1}$ for orientations close to $+z$. Indeed, we find a reasonable match between velocities predicted for the D-DET model along the equatorial direction (\mathbf{l}_2) and those observed in both SN 2001el (Fig. 5.17) and SN 2012fr (Fig. 5.16). This orientation, however, is associated with polarisation signals across the calcium line that are inconsistent with data. Because of the strong asymmetries in the outer shell of this model (see Fig. 5.1), selecting orientations out of the equatorial plane typically leads to poorer matches with observations: calcium lines for viewing angles in the southern hemisphere are typically too weakly polarised and too slow, while those in the northern hemisphere too strongly polarised and too fast (see polarisation spectra around maximum light in Fig. 5.4).

Although high-velocity features in the Ca II IR triplet are frequently observed in SN Ia spectra, their origin remains unclear and may be associated with either a density increase (Gerardy et al. 2004; Mazzali et al. 2005a; Tanaka et al. 2006), a composition enhancement (Mazzali et al. 2005a) or a ionization effect (Blondin et al. 2013) in

the outer ejecta. In the single-degenerate scenario, a density increase might be associated with circumstellar material (Gerardy et al. 2004; Mazzali et al. 2005a; Tanaka et al. 2006). If that is the case, the lack of high-velocity features in the N100-DDT and VM-11-09 models would not be surprising as circumstellar material is not captured by the Seitenzahl et al. (2013) and Pakmor et al. (2012) explosion models. Alternatively, an abundance enhancement in the outer regions of the ejecta (Mazzali et al. 2005a) would seem qualitatively consistent with the calcium distribution predicted in the He-shell by our D-DET model. As noted above, however, the D-DET model struggles to simultaneously reproduce spectroscopic and polarimetric properties of this high-velocity material. In the future development of double-detonation models, it will be particularly important to consider whether better agreement in the high-velocity Ca II features can be achieved by models in which properties of the ash of the He-shell detonation (both composition and geometry) differ from the predictions of the Fink et al. (2010) simulations. In particular, we note that it has already been suggested that changes in the He-shell properties are likely required if such models are to provide a good match to observed optical light curves and colours (see e.g. Kromer et al. 2010). It remains to be seen whether multi-dimensional explosion models with altered He shell properties can produce morphologies more consistent with the observed spectropolarimetry of high-velocity features.

5.7 Summary and discussion

In this chapter we have presented polarisation calculations for three multi-dimensional explosion models suggested as promising candidates to explain normal SNe Ia: (i) one axisymmetric double-detonation model from Fink et al. (2010, here referred to as D-DET), with asymmetries arising prevalently in the outer regions of the ejecta; (ii) one delayed-detonation model from Seitenzahl et al. (2013, here N100-DDT), characterised by globally spherical ejecta with small-scale asymmetries; (iii) one violent merger model from Pakmor et al. (2012, here VM-11-09), showing strong asymmetries at large scales. In particular, we calculated polarisation spectra around maximum light for each model and focused on three orientations for the 2D D-DET model and five for the 3D N100-DDT and VM-11-09 model. In order to map out the range of polarisation covered by the models, we also performed extra-calculations that provide lower signal-to-noise spectra for an additional 17 (D-DET), 21 (N100-DDT) and 30 (VM-11-09) viewing angles.

Polarisation spectra predicted by the D-DET and N100-DDT models match particularly well those observed for the majority of normal SNe Ia, as clearly highlighted by the comparison with the two well-studied SN 2001el and SN 2012fr. Polarisation lev-

els in the pseudo-continuum range (between 6400 and 7200 Å) are found to decrease from ~ 0.1 – 0.3 per cent at maximum light to lower values at later times, in strikingly good agreement with observations. Higher degrees of polarisation are predicted at wavelengths corresponding to the troughs of absorption lines. In particular, the set of polarisation signals extracted across the Si II $\lambda 6355$ feature ($\lesssim 1$ per cent) provides a remarkable match with the distribution of values observed in normal SNe Ia, while the low degrees of polarisation found in the O I $\lambda 7774$ region are consistent with the non-detection of this feature in currently available data. Taken together, these findings lead us to conclude that the geometries of these two explosion models are broadly consistent with those of normal SNe Ia.

For the VM-11-09 model, a reasonable match with the peculiarly strongly polarised SN 2004dt is found along one of the orientations investigated. Nevertheless, we find rather unlikely that this specific violent merger model can be regarded as a good model for SNe Ia as the extracted polarisation levels are typically too high to match those observed for the bulk of normal SNe Ia. Degrees of polarisation in the pseudo-continuum range are larger than 0.5 per cent and still increasing ~ 10 d after maximum light for about half of the 35 orientations investigated, behaviour that clearly deviates from what is observed in normal SNe Ia. Interestingly, most of these orientations are oriented close to the cavity in the ^{56}Ni distribution, which is filled by material from the companion star. The negative impact of the material from the explosion of the companion star on the model is also suggested by the identification in our spectra of carbon and oxygen polarisation signatures at rather low velocities ($v \sim -6800$ km s $^{-1}$). The strong polarisation signals ($\gtrsim 0.5$ per cent) predicted across the O I $\lambda 7774$ are not seen in SNe Ia, and the C II lines, associated with unburned carbon material from the companion, are not normally observed at such low velocities ($v_{\text{obs}} \sim -12000$ km s $^{-1}$; Parrent et al. 2011; Thomas et al. 2011) or detected in polarisation (see e.g. Wang & Wheeler 2008). Therefore, in the future it will be crucial to investigate alternative scenarios with revised explosion/secondary properties. Possibilities include selecting different mass ratios, a different location and time of ignition or a larger distance between the two stars. This might reduce the ejecta asymmetries and thus lead to better agreement with spectropolarimetric data of SNe Ia.

As highlighted in Fig. 5.19, the analysis presented in this chapter demonstrates the power of spectropolarimetry in testing and comparing different explosion models. While the three models investigated here reproduce SN Ia light curves and spectra comparably well (see also Röpke et al. 2012) – and would then be hard to differentiate – polarisation provides a clear distinction and favours the D-DET and N100-DDT models over the VM-11-09 model. Polarisation levels extracted for the first two models can account for the small signals, and their time evolution, typically observed in normal

SNe Ia. At the moment, however, placing a strong preference for one model over the other appears difficult. This is largely due to the fact that polarising electron scattering contributions originate in rather spherical regions of the ejecta for both these models, and thus their overall polarisation levels are small and hard to distinguish. As shown in Section 5.4, investigating individual polarisation features (e.g. the Ca II IR triplet and the O II feature) can help discriminating between the two models, but this needs to be addressed in a more systematic way in future studies (see Chapter 7).

Although the D-DET and N100-DDT models are hard to distinguish based on their polarisation signatures, it is important to note that we have only calculated polarisation signatures for two specific models and the results presented here are not necessarily representative of the whole Fink et al. (2010) double-detonation and Seitenzahl et al. (2013) DDT studies. While the different double-detonation models of Fink et al. (2010) are all characterized by relatively similar geometries – and are thus expected to produce comparable polarisation signals – the DDT models of Seitenzahl et al. (2013) yield ejecta whose morphologies are strongly dependent on the ignition configuration (see also Section 5.1.2). In particular, compared to the N100 model used in this thesis, models in which the explosion is initiated with a smaller number of kernels (1 to 40) are typically more asymmetric and thus likely to be more polarised. In the future, it will be important to map out the polarisation range spanned by the full set of models of Fink et al. (2010) and Seitenzahl et al. (2013) to understand whether the two scenarios can be effectively distinguished via variations between the polarisation signatures across the model sequences.

Chapter 6

Interpreting spectropolarimetry for superluminous supernovae

*“E quando miro in cielo arder le stelle;
dico fra me pensando:
a che tante facelle?
Che fa l’aria infinita, e quel profondo
infinito seren? che vuol dir questa
solitudine immensa? ed io che sono?”*

– Giacomo Leopardi, *Night song of a wandering shepherd in Asia*, 84-89

While in the rest of this work we have focussed on characterising polarisation signatures of SNe Ia, in this chapter we present an application of our polarisation scheme to a different type of SNe. Specifically we will exploit our test code (Section 3.5) to interpret the first spectropolarimetric observations of a “superluminous” SN. This class of transients is introduced in Section 6.1, while in Section 6.2 we describe spectroscopic and spectropolarimetric data of the superluminous SN 2015bn. We then present our interpretation of the observed polarisation spectra in Section 6.3 and discuss its implication for identifying the explosion mechanism of superluminous SNe in Section 6.4. Finally, we summarise our findings and draw conclusions in Section 6.5. Part of the contents of this chapter has been published in the *Astrophysical Journal* (Inserra et al. 2016).

My contribution to this work has been important both on the observational and the theoretical side. Although data were collected by C. Inserra, I contributed in reducing and analysing the data. In particular, spectropolarimetric data for SN 2015bn have been reduced by me and C. Inserra independently as a cross-check. On the theoretical side, the modelling of the polarisation spectra presented in Section 6.3 is my own.

6.1 Superluminous supernovae

Superluminous SNe (SLSNe) are a class of extremely bright transients that has been discovered and extensively studied in the past few years. Specifically, SLSNe are characterised by intrinsic luminosities that are a factor of about 5–50 larger than those typically observed in normal SNe Ia (Quimby et al. 2011; Chomiuk et al. 2011; Inserra & Smartt 2014). They can be divided in two main groups: hydrogen free, and hence labeled SLSNe I, and hydrogen rich, therefore called SLSNe II. The first class is better studied: SLSNe I show blue continua at maximum light, a distinctive “W” feature due to O II at early epochs and, at about 30 days after peak they are spectroscopically similar to SNe Ic at peak luminosity (Pastorello et al. 2010). Consequently, they are also usually labeled SLSNe Ic (e.g. Inserra et al. 2013).

The enormous luminosities involved in SLSN events call for an explanation about their explosion mechanisms and progenitor systems. Among the possible scenarios proposed, three have been widely-discussed as promising channels:

1. *Central engine.* In this scenario, ejecta from a core-collapse SN are thought to be powered by a central engine. The latter is a compact object left behind during the core-collapse event that can be either a magnetar (a highly-magnetised rapidly-rotating pulsar; Kasen & Bildsten 2010; Woosley 2010; Dessart et al. 2012) or a black-hole (Dexter & Kasen 2013). The former is the currently favoured sce-

nario. Here, the rotational energy from the newly-born magnetar is deposited into the ejecta and can significantly enhance the luminosity of the explosion.

2. *Pair-instability SN.* In this scenario, SLSNe are believed to arise from the explosions of extremely massive stars (e.g. Heger & Woosley 2002; Gal-Yam et al. 2009; Kozyreva & Blinnikov 2015). For stars with initial masses between ~ 140 and $260 M_{\odot}$, core temperatures are so high that photons are transformed to e^+/e^- pairs. As gravity is no longer balanced by the photon radiative pressure, the star becomes to collapse. Explosive oxygen burning is triggered and leads to a thermonuclear runaway (see Section 1.4.2). First predicted by Barkat et al. (1967) and Rakavy & Shaviv (1967), these pair-instability SNe (PISNe) would produce up to $40 M_{\odot}$ of ^{56}Ni (roughly 100 times that synthesised in SNe Ia) and therefore be able to power extremely bright events such as SLSNe.
3. *Interaction.* Another scenario proposed to explain the high luminosities of SLSNe is that of interaction between the SN ejecta and some circumstellar material (CSM, e.g. Woosley et al. 2007; Chevalier & Irwin 2011; Chatzopoulos et al. 2012). The most promising mechanism is that of a pulsational pair-instability SN (PPISN, Woosley et al. 2007), arising from stars with lower masses ($\sim 95\text{--}130 M_{\odot}$) compared to those leading to PISNe. In P-PISNe, the pair-instability mechanism is not able to unbind the star but instead leads to the ejection of massive shells of material. These eruptions repeat until the final core-collapse of the star. Then, the interaction between the SN ejecta and the previously-ejected shells might produce sufficiently high luminosities to explain the brightness of SLSNe.

A powerful diagnostic to distinguish between scenarios is polarimetry since it can unveil information on the geometry of the explosion and hence increase our understanding of these transients. If a magnetar is the central engine that powers the extreme luminosities of SLSNe, then the strong magnetic field ($B \sim 10^{14}$ G) and rapid rotation could lead to large scale asymmetries and axisymmetric ejecta (e.g. Chen et al. 2016). As shown by previous studies (Fryer et al. 2001; Joggerst & Whalen 2011; Baranov et al. 2013; Chen et al. 2014a), it would instead be hard to break the symmetry in PISNe as in most cases either no instabilities or only mild ones arise in the explosion. In the P-PISN interaction scenario, emitted shells are overall spherical and thus we would not expect to see a strong axial symmetry in the ejecta. Interaction of the ejecta with the emitted shells, however, is believed to create strong mixing and fluid instabilities (Chen et al. 2014b) which break the overall spherical symmetry and might result in polarisation signatures across individual spectral features (e.g. Q/U plane loops).

Imaging polarimetry of a SLSN Ic has been reported by Leloudas et al. (2015) but no evidence of asymmetries was found. With imaging polarimetry, however, any information about lines and continuum contribution from the ejecta is omitted and hence the results are hard to interpret (see Section 2.3.3). In contrast, spectropolarimetry offers a more in depth probe of the geometry of SN explosions, as demonstrated in the previous chapters of this thesis. Recently, we have therefore started a project aimed to characterize spectropolarimetric features for SLSNe. Here we report the first spectropolarimetric observations of a SLSN Ic, namely SN 2015bn.

6.2 SN 2015bn

SN 2015bn was discovered by the Catalina Real-time Transient Survey (Drake et al. 2009) on 23 December 2014 and subsequently by the Pan-STARRS Survey for Transients (Huber et al. 2015) on 2015 February 15 UT. It was classified on the 17 February 2015 by the the Public ESO Spectroscopic Survey for Transient Objects (PESSTO, Smartt et al. 2015) as a SLSN Ic at $z = 0.11$. The main PESSTO follow-up campaign is presented by Nicholl et al. (2016). Spectropolarimetric observations of SN 2015bn were collected by C. Inserra with VLT + FORS2 on the 22 February 2015 and 20 April 2015, which correspond to -23.7 and $+27.5$ d relative to maximum light in the g -band (Nicholl et al. 2016). Both epochs are close to the broad peak of the SLSN light curve. Spectropolarimetric data were reduced by me and C. Inserra independently and no significant differences were found.

6.2.1 Flux spectra

Our first flux spectrum, taken ~ 24 days before maximum light, is shown in the upper-left panel of Fig. 6.1. A black-body fit to the available spectral range yields $T \sim 10\,000$ K, which corresponds to a radius of 6.5×10^{15} cm and a black-body peak bluer (2897.8 \AA) than covered by our wavelength range. The spectrum is dominated by metal lines: the Ca H and K lines are visible on the blue edge of our spectrum, redward of which are two double peak absorption features at 4400 and 5000 \AA , most likely due to a combination of Fe III and Fe II with a possible contribution of O II. Redward, the spectrum is again dominated by iron up to 5500 \AA , while Na I D and Si II $\lambda 6355$ are visible around 6000 \AA . The region around 7500 \AA shows a shallow O I absorption line, together with another shallow P-Cygni profile at 7200 \AA tentatively identified as C I (see fig. 11 in Nicholl et al. 2016). According to the modelling of SLSNe Ic spectra reported by Mazzali et al. (2016), an alternative identification for the 7200 \AA line could be O II.

Figure 6.1: Flux (top) and Stokes parameters Q (middle) and U (bottom) spectra for SN 2015bn. Data of the first (-23.7 d) epoch are shown on the left panels, while those of the second ($+27.5$ d) epoch on the right panels. The horizontal black lines in the left panels refer to the 100 \AA spectral regions where the Stokes parameters for the ISP are calculated.

The second flux spectrum, taken ~ 28 days after maximum light, is shown in the top-right panel of Fig. 6.1. The black-body fit gives a slightly lower black-body temperature ($T \sim 9400 \text{ K}$) and larger black-body radius $8 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}$ compared to the first epoch. At this epoch, Fe III has been replaced by Fe II. The noticeable changes are in the region blueward of Si II. The semi-forbidden Mg I] $\lambda 4571$ line appears in emission and replaces Fe III and – together with the increase of Fe II features with respect to the previous epoch – reshapes the profile of that region that no longer shows the two absorption features. The other distinguishable change is the shift to the red of the broad profile around 5300 \AA that is due again to Fe II lines replacing their higher ionized ions. The other two P-Cygni profiles redder than Si II are still present and due to the same elements of the first epochs, even if the feature around 7200 \AA could now have a small contribution from the forbidden [Ca II] $\lambda \lambda 7291, 7323$ features as also shown by Nicholl et al. (2016).

6.2.2 Polarisation spectra

Polarisation Q and U spectra of SN 2015bn at the two epochs are shown in the middle and bottom panels of Fig. 6.1. These spectra are not corrected for the interstellar dust

contribution. As pointed out in Section 2.4.1, it is important to correctly estimate the ISP due to intervening dust in the line of sight to SN 2015bn and remove it from the spectra if one aims to study the intrinsic polarisation signal of the SN.

Interstellar polarisation

The Galactic reddening toward the position of the SN is $E(B-V) = 0.02$ (Schlafly & Finkbeiner 2011). No Na ID $\lambda\lambda 5890, 5896$ was detected in our spectra. Therefore, we assume the host galaxy reddening to be negligible and the total reddening to be equal to the Galactic component. For the adopted reddening, the Serkowski law places a limit on the maximum polarisation $P_{\text{ISP}} < P_{\text{max}} \sim 0.2$ per cent (see Section 2.4.1). In addition, we found three stars from the Heiles (2000) catalog within 3 degrees of the SN position, which have polarisation levels $P = 0.07 \pm 0.04\%$, $P = 0.10 \pm 0.12\%$, $P = 0.05 \pm 0.03\%$ and angles $\chi = 115 \pm 14^\circ$, $\chi = 79 \pm 31^\circ$ and $\chi = 98 \pm 19^\circ$ corresponding to mean values of $\bar{P} = 0.07 \pm 0.04\%$ (in full agreement with the low Galactic ISP along the line of view, P_{max}) and $\bar{\chi} = 97 \pm 13^\circ$. Furthermore, as an independent test, we have derived the ISP value directly from our spectropolarimetric observations assuming that the intrinsic polarisation in regions of strong emission lines or line blanketing is negligible (see Section 2.2.2 and discussion in Section 2.4.1). With this assumption, polarisation signals in these spectral regions can be attributed to the ISP. We identified the region of the emission of Si II $\lambda 6355$ and the region around 4500 \AA affected by Fe II and Fe III blending (see Section 6.2.1) as suitable for such analysis. The Stokes parameters were averaged over a range of 100 \AA . In the first epoch we measured $Q_{\text{ISP}} = -0.15\%$ and $U_{\text{ISP}} = -0.06\%$, which gives us a polarisation level $P_{\text{ISP}} = 0.16\%$ and angle $\chi_{\text{ISP}} = 101^\circ$ consistent with the previous limits. At the second epoch, polarisation levels in the same ranges are larger compared to the first epoch and are thus likely to be a combination of interstellar and intrinsic polarisation signals. Therefore – as the interstellar polarisation is time independent – we correct both epochs using the values inferred from pre-maximum.

Q/U planes and rotated Stokes parameters

In Fig. 6.2 we show our spectropolarimetric dataset in the Q/U plane (see Section 2.3.3). The polarisation reaches a maximum of about 1.4 per cent in the first and almost 2 per cent in the second epoch. The distribution of our data points in the Q/U plane clearly suggests a preferred direction, which we identify by fitting the data with a least squares fit. The best fits to the available dataset give a dominant axis with a position angle $\chi = \alpha/2$ of $-8^\circ \pm 1$ for the pre-maximum and $-6^\circ \pm 1$ for the post maximum

Figure 6.2: Q/U plane of SN 2015bn at -23.7 days from peak (left) and $+27.5$ (right) relative to maximum light. Concentric dashed circles are equivalent to $P = 1$ per cent and $P = 2$ per cent from the inner to the outer. The black stars represents the ISP value in the Q/U plane. The black solid line represents the best linear fit representing the dominant axis.

epoch. In principle, a polarisation angle evolution might indicate an intrinsic change of the dominant axis from the first to the second epoch and hence a different dominant orientation between the outer and inner layers of the ejecta. However, the change in angle of the best fit between the two epochs is sufficiently small, and comparable with the errors, that it can be attributed to measurement uncertainties only.

As discussed in Section 4.3, it is convenient to rotate the polarisation Q and U vectors to a new coordinate system that has a component along the dominant axis (Q_{rot}), which represents global geometric deviations from spherical symmetry, and an orthogonal component to the dominant axis (U_{rot}), which shows physical deviations from axial symmetry. Specifically, Eq. (4.1) is used to rotate the original Stokes parameters Q and U

$$\begin{pmatrix} Q_{\text{rot}} \\ U_{\text{rot}} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (Q - Q_{\text{ISP}}) \cos \alpha + (U - U_{\text{ISP}}) \sin \alpha \\ -(Q - Q_{\text{ISP}}) \sin \alpha + (U - U_{\text{ISP}}) \cos \alpha \end{pmatrix} \quad (6.1)$$

after subtraction of the ISP values Q_{ISP} and U_{ISP} .

In Fig. 6.3 we show polarisation spectra Q_{rot} and U_{rot} . While our data show a strong deviation from spherical symmetry (seen in Q_{rot}), there is only weak evidence of physical deviation from axial symmetry (i.e. U_{rot} is fairly consistent with zero), suggesting that the ejecta are approximately axisymmetric. Most of the peaks in the polarisation Q_{rot} signal are roughly coincident with the absorption minima of identifiable P-Cygni profiles in the spectra. This is consistent with what is seen in other

Figure 6.3: Flux (top) and Q_{rot} (middle) and U_{rot} (bottom) spectra for the first (black) and second (gray) epoch.

classes of SNe, indicating a common origin of the polarisation signal in which resonant line scattering occurs above and electron-scattering photosphere (see Section 2.3.2). At both epochs, Q_{rot} shows a wavelength dependence decreasing from blue to the red. At the first epoch, we find a clear sign reversal with Q_{rot} changing from positive values for blue wavelengths ($\lesssim 6000 \text{ \AA}$) to negative values in the red. The second epoch is more polarised than the first and does not show a sign reversal.

6.3 Modelling polarisation spectra

As discussed in the previous section, polarisation spectra for SN 2015bn are characterized by a well-defined axis of symmetry. In addition, the polarisation component along the dominant axis, Q_{rot} , shows a strong wavelength dependence at both epochs and a pronounced evolution between pre- and post-maximum. In the following we present a simple toy-model that can account for these observed polarisation signatures. Our primary goal is to constrain the physical mechanisms responsible for (i) the wavelength dependence and (ii) the time evolution of the overall *line-continuum* polarisation level, rather than to model polarisation features associated with individual spectral transitions.

To interpret the polarisation spectra for SN 2015bn we will consider simple ellipsoidal geometries using the Monte Carlo test code presented in Section 3.5. Monte Carlo packets are created unpolarised at a spherical photosphere of radius R_{ph}^1 , emitted assuming constant surface brightness and propagated throughout an envelope. As the data suggests the presence of a single axis of symmetry, this envelope is modelled as a prolate ellipsoid defined by

$$\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} + \frac{z^2}{c^2} = 1 \quad , \quad a = b < c \quad . \quad (6.2)$$

The latter can be rewritten in cylindrical coordinates as

$$\frac{r^2}{A^2} + z^2 = c^2 \quad (6.3)$$

where we have introduced the axis ratio $A = a/c < 1$. Our calculations adopt ellipsoidal isodensity surfaces

$$\rho(\xi, t) = \frac{\rho_0(t)}{\xi^n} \quad , \quad (6.4)$$

where

$$\xi = \sqrt{\frac{r^2}{A^2} + z^2} \quad . \quad (6.5)$$

For all our calculations we use a power-law index $n = 7$ as suggested by previous studies (e.g. Mazzali et al. 2016). On their journey throughout the ejecta, Monte Carlo packets can interact with matter and change their polarisation state. Two sources of opacity are used: a grey electron scattering opacity and a wavelength-dependent line opacity (see below). The former is assumed to partially polarise the radiation, while the latter regarded as a depolarising contribution (see Section 2.2). Polarisation spectra are extracted for an equatorial viewing angle (that is along the semi-minor axis of the pro-

¹Although we could explore different geometries for the photosphere, here we prefer to keep the number of free-parameters small.

Table 6.1: Parameters used in our calculations. Element abundances are reported as mass fractions.

Model	Epoch	L_{bot} erg s ⁻¹	v_{ph} km s ⁻¹	v_{out} km s ⁻¹	ρ_{ph} g cm ⁻³	He	C	O	Ne	Mg	Si	S	Ca	Ti	Fe	Co	Ni
A	02/22	1.58×10 ⁴⁴	8×10 ⁸	1.6×10 ⁹	7.3×10 ⁻¹⁴	0.10	0.40	0.475	0.02	7×10 ⁻⁴	2×10 ⁻³	5×10 ⁻⁴	5×10 ⁻⁵	2×10 ⁻⁵	5×10 ⁻⁴	3×10 ⁻⁴	1×10 ⁻⁵
A	04/20	1.26×10 ⁴⁴	7×10 ⁸	1.6×10 ⁹	3.6×10 ⁻¹⁴	0.10	0.40	0.475	0.02	5×10 ⁻⁴	2×10 ⁻³	5×10 ⁻⁴	5×10 ⁻⁵	2×10 ⁻⁵	5×10 ⁻⁴	3×10 ⁻⁴	1×10 ⁻⁵
B	02/22	1.58×10 ⁴⁴	8×10 ⁸	1.6×10 ⁹	7.3×10 ⁻¹⁴	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.414	0.585	3×10 ⁻⁴
B	04/20	1.26×10 ⁴⁴	7×10 ⁸	1.6×10 ⁹	3.6×10 ⁻¹⁴	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.626	0.374	1×10 ⁻⁶

late ellipsoid). Moving the observer orientation from the equatorial plane towards +z would result in smaller polarisation levels and thus would require larger asphericities than those predicted below.

The electron scattering coefficient and line opacity distribution adopted in our calculations are estimated using the 1D TARDIS radiative transfer code (Kerzendorf & Sim 2014). In particular, calculations with two different ejecta compositions have been carried out: one (hereafter referred to as *Model A*) adopting the ejecta composition proposed by Mazzali et al. (2016) and one (*Model B*) assuming an extreme case of ⁵⁶Ni-dominated ejecta at the time of explosion. In the latter case, we derive the relative abundances of each element by calculating the fraction of Ni that has decayed to Fe and Co at both the observed epochs of SN 2015bn. The specific ejecta compositions used for each calculation are reported in Table 6.1. TARDIS provides values for the electron scattering coefficient and the Sobolev optical depth of each transition in each zone from which tables of wavelength-dependent expansion opacities can be calculated (Karp et al. 1977; Friend & Castor 1983; Eastman & Pinto 1993). The opacities obtained for TARDIS zones close to the photosphere in TARDIS are plotted in Fig. 6.4. At both epochs, *Model A* produces only a weak wavelength dependence in the line opacity distribution across the wavelength interval covered by our observations (~ 4000 to 8000 Å), with values that are a factor of ~10 lower than the electron scattering opacity ($k_{\text{sc}}^{A,1} = 0.047 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and $k_{\text{sc}}^{A,2} = 0.027 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ at the first and second epoch, respectively). In contrast, the line opacity distribution extracted for *Model B* is strongly wavelength dependent in this region. While spectral regions around 8000 Å are still dominated by electron scattering opacity ($k_{\text{sc}}^{B,1} = 0.015 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and $k_{\text{sc}}^{B,2} = 0.014 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$), the line opacity contribution steadily increases toward the bluer regions of the spectrum and becomes dominant around 4000 Å.

Fig. 6.5 reports results of two simulations relative to the first epoch of SN 2015bn. Both calculations adopt opacities from *Model A* and assume an ellipsoidal envelope with axis ratio $A = 0.88$ and outer boundary at $\xi_{\text{out}} = 2 \times R_{\text{ph}}$. The maximum electron

Figure 6.4: Electron scattering (red) and line (blue) opacities extracted from the flux spectra using TARDIS. *Left panels:* opacities extracted for the first (top) and second (bottom) epoch with an ejecta composition as suggested by Mazzali et al. (2016) (*Model A*, Table 6.1). *Right panels:* same as the left-hand panels but with the extreme case of pure Ni ejecta at the time of explosion (*Model B*, Table 6.1). A fit to the line opacity is shown as dashed green line and used in our polarisation code to model a line-continuum of line. Dashed black, vertical lines encompass the rest-frame wavelength region covered by our spectra.

scattering opacity to the boundary

$$\tau_{\max} = \int_{R_{\text{ph}}}^{\xi_{\text{out}}} k_{\text{sc}} \rho(\xi, t) dz \quad (6.6)$$

is set to unity. From the latter equation, this choice for the maximum opacity places a constraint on the density at the photospheric radius $\xi = R_{\text{ph}}$. Ejecta are modeled 70 d after explosion and the photosphere placed at $v_{\text{ph}}^{\text{1st}} = 8 \times 10^3 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (Nicholl et al. 2016). The density at $\xi = R_{\text{ph}}$ and the mass in the envelope are $\rho_{\text{ph}}^{\text{1st}} = 2.7 \times 10^{-14} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ and $M^{\text{1st}} = 2.5 M_{\odot}$, respectively. The first polarisation spectrum (red dashed line) corresponds to a calculation including only electron scattering ($k_{\text{sc}}^{\text{A},1}$) and provides a good

Figure 6.5: Flux (top) and polarisation (bottom) spectra of SN 2015bn at 23.7 d before maximum light (black lines), together with polarisation levels predicted by our toy model. A single ellipsoidal region with axis ratio $A = 0.88$ is used, while opacities are selected from *Model A*. The red dashed line corresponds to a calculation including only electron scattering opacity, while the solid blue line shows a calculation with both electron scattering and line opacities.

match to the polarisation level detected for SN 2015bn in the wavelength region around 7000 \AA that is devoid of strong optical features. The second polarisation spectrum (solid blue line) shows instead a simulation in which both electron scattering and line opacities are included. Specifically, we adopt a polynomial fit to the line opacity distribution as representative of the line-continuum absorption component (see upper left panel of Fig. 6.4). Compared to the line-free calculation, the latter produces lower polarisation levels since the line opacity acts as a depolarising contribution. This effect becomes stronger moving from redder to bluer wavelengths, as a consequence of the increasing contribution of line to the total opacity (see upper left panel of Fig. 6.4). The match between predicted and observed polarisation levels, however, is poor as the wavelength dependence in the line opacity of *Model A* is not sufficiently strong to bring the overall Q_{rot} level toward positive values below $\sim 5500 \text{ \AA}$, as observed for SN 2015bn.

Compared to *Model A*, line opacities extracted for *Model B* are characterized by a more pronounced wavelength dependence (see right panels of Fig. 6.4). Therefore, we construct a new model that includes opacities from both *Model A* and *Model B*.

Figure 6.6: Ejecta geometries in the two-zone model at the first, pre-peak (left panel) and at the second, post-peak epoch (right panel). The external layer retains its prolate geometry ($A_{\text{out}} = a/c = 0.88$), while the inner shell has increased its asphericity from $A_{\text{in}} = 0.88$ to $A_{\text{in}} = 0.60$. The pictured ellipsoids have the same asphericity reported in the figure and in the text.

Specifically, we divide the envelope in two different ellipsoidal zones (see Fig. 6.6):

- A “*metal-rich*” inner region modeled as a prolate ellipsoid with $\xi_{\text{in}} = 1.5 \times R_{\text{ph}}$. Opacities in this region are selected from *Model B*. Specifically, we adopt $k_{\text{sc}}^{B,1\text{st}}$ (pre-maximum) and $k_{\text{sc}}^{B,2\text{nd}}$ (post-maximum) as electron scattering coefficients and use a polynomial fit to the line opacity distribution for the line-continuum absorption component (see right panels of Fig. 6.4).
- A “*metal-poor*” outer region modeled as a prolate ellipsoid with $\xi_{\text{out}} = 2 \times R_{\text{ph}}$. Opacities in this region are selected from *Model A*. Here, we adopt electron scattering coefficient $k_{\text{sc}}^{A,1\text{st}}$ (pre-maximum) and $k_{\text{sc}}^{A,2\text{nd}}$ (post-maximum) and a polynomial fit to the line opacity distribution for the line-continuum absorption component (see left panels of Fig. 6.4).

The shapes of the two zones (i.e. the axis ratios A_{in} and A_{out}) are taken as free parameters in our models, together with the maximum electron scattering opacity to the boundary τ_{max} . A suitable choice for τ_{max} is selected (see below) and the axis ratios A_{in} and A_{out} chosen to reproduce the observed polarisation spectra.

Figure 6.7: *Left panels:* flux and polarisation spectra of SN 2015bn at 23.7 d before maximum light (black lines), together with polarisation levels predicted by our toy model. The red dashed line corresponds to a calculation including only electron scattering opacity, while the solid blue line shows a calculation with both electron scattering and line opacities. The geometry used for both these calculations is discussed in the text and reported in the upper panel of Fig. 6.6. *Right panels:* flux and polarisation spectra of SN 2015bn at 27.5 d after maximum light (grey lines), together with different polarisation predictions from our toy model. The red dashed line and green-dot dashed line are calculated adopting the same geometry used for the first epoch and excluding or including line opacities, respectively. The blue solid line assumes instead a different geometry (see lower panel of Fig. 6.6) and includes both electron scattering and line opacities.

The left panel of Fig. 6.7 shows results of our simulations compared to the first epoch of SN 2015bn. As in the one-zone model presented above, these calculations are carried out at 70 d after explosion and assume $v_{\text{ph}}^{1\text{st}} = 8 \times 10^3 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and $\tau_{\text{max}}^{1\text{st}} = 1$. The inner and the outer ellipsoidal envelopes have the same axis ratio, namely $A_{\text{out}}^{1\text{st}} = A_{\text{in}}^{1\text{st}} = 0.88$. Estimated values for the density at $\xi = R_{\text{ph}}$ and for the mass in the envelope are $\rho_{\text{ph}}^{1\text{st}} = 7.3 \times 10^{-14} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ and $M^{1\text{st}} = 6.7 M_{\odot}$, respectively. The first simulation (dashed red line) includes only electron scattering in the ejecta and is found to reproduce the degree of polarisation observed for SN 2015bn around 7000 Å ($Q_{\text{rot}} \sim -1$ per cent). While the grey electron scattering opacity assumed in the latter calculation yields a constant degree of polarisation as a function of wavelength, including contributions from line absorption (solid blue line) results into a strong wavelength dependence of the line-continuum level. This causes a sign reversal of Q_{rot} around 5000 Å, in good agreement with what is observed for SN 2015bn. The similarity between our predictions and the overall line-continuum level of SN 2015bn thus suggests that an increasing contribution of line opacities towards the bluer regions of the spectra

is responsible for the strong wavelength dependence observed.

The right panel of Fig. 6.7 shows results of our simulations relative to the second epoch of SN 2015bn. The latter is modeled 121 d after explosion and with the photosphere placed at $v_{\text{ph}}^{2\text{nd}} = 7 \times 10^3 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (Nicholl et al. 2016). Following the ejecta expansion, the density at $\xi = R_{\text{ph}}$ and the maximum electron scattering opacity drop to $\rho_{\text{ph}}^{2\text{nd}} = 3.6 \times 10^{-14} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ and $\tau_{\text{max}}^{2\text{nd}} = 0.61$, respectively, while the mass in the envelope increases to $M^{2\text{nd}} = 11.9 M_{\odot}$. As shown in Fig. 6.7, keeping the axis ratios of the “metal-rich” and “metal-poor” regions fixed to the values they have at the first epoch leads to polarisation levels that are clearly inconsistent with those observed in SN 2015bn (dashed-dot green line). If we instead keep the same axis ratio for the outer region ($A_{\text{out}}^{2\text{nd}} = A_{\text{out}}^{1\text{st}} = 0.88$) and assume a more aspherical inner region ($A_{\text{in}}^{2\text{nd}} = 0.60$), we obtain a polarisation spectrum in good agreement with data (solid blue line).

To summarise, our ellipsoidal toy model suggests that (i) the strong wavelength dependence observed in both polarisation spectra of SN 2015bn is given by a strong increase in the line opacity from redder to bluer regions of the spectra; (ii) the time evolution of the polarisation level from pre- to post-maximum is given by a change in the asphericity of the inner layers (from $A_{\text{in}}^{1\text{st}} = 0.88$ to $A_{\text{in}}^{2\text{nd}} = 0.60$). The ejecta geometries proposed by our calculations are reported in Fig. 6.6. The implications of these results for the different progenitor scenarios will be discussed in Section 6.4.

We stress that the simple ellipsoidal modelling developed here is only intended to broadly characterize the data and frame their interpretation. In particular, we did not attempt to model any discrete spectral features nor investigate the extent to which the two epochs are consistent with evolution in homologous expansion. Instead we have considered the two epochs individually.

6.4 On the geometry of superluminous supernovae

Our spectropolarimetric observations are the first carried out for a SLSN and provide new insights into the geometry of these explosions. We can now consider the implications of this for identifying the explosion mechanism responsible for their extreme luminosity. The data show a deviation from spherical symmetry and the presence of a dominant axis which implies an axisymmetric configuration of the ejecta. To explain the observed increase in the Q_{rot} vector from the pre-peak to the post-peak epoch (see Fig. 6.3) we need an increase in the asphericity of the inner layers of the ejecta or the photosphere to recede into inner layers which are less spherical. The geometric parameters inferred from our toy ellipsoidal modelling of the inner zone ($A_{\text{in}}^1 = 0.88$ and $A_{\text{in}}^2 = 0.60$, see Sec. 6.3) are certainly model dependent and so can only be taken as

indicative: they depend in detail on the composition/line opacity adopted and on all parameters controlling the shape and density distribution. To fully understand degeneracies among these parameters, and to construct a self-consistent model that accounts for both epochs is beyond the scope of the simplistic approach used here. Nevertheless, the calculations illustrate that moderate departures from sphericity combined with substantial wavelength-dependent opacity can qualitatively account for the observed spectropolarimetric properties. Although we used ellipsoidal toy models to characterize the data (shown in Fig. 6.6), it is important to note that alternative axisymmetric configurations, including bipolar ejecta morphologies, would also be able to match the observations.

Together, the data and modelling presented above suggest that, as time passes, the spectral forming region recedes into increasingly aspherical (but axi-symmetric) ejecta layers. In the following, we consider the ramifications of this conclusions for our understanding of SLSN explosion models, bearing in mind models involving a dominant axis are favored by the data.

Multi-dimensional simulations of magneto-rotational core-collapse SNe have already shown axisymmetric ejecta and asymmetries on large scales (Mösta et al. 2014). 2D simulations of magnetar-powered SLSNe (Chen et al. 2016) have shown that fluid instabilities and mixing occurs if energy is deposited in a relatively small mass of material which could be, approximately, the mass of the inner ejecta. The amount of energy deposited needs to be comparable to that of the ejecta kinetic energy of the explosion. These instabilities and mixing could alter the geometry of the ejecta if the initial magnetar period is less than 3 ms (Chen et al. 2016). Notably, the magnetar models proposed for the bolometric light curve of SN 2015bn do satisfy this condition (2.1 ms and 1.7 ms for the two best fit shown in Nicholl et al. 2016). In this scenario, the increase of the inner region asymmetries with time could be a consequence of a magnetar jet-like flow stalled within the core in a similar fashion to the picture proposed by Maund et al. (2009) for a jet-induced SN event. The central engine scenario, however, seems hard to be reconciled with the suggestion from our modelling (Section 6.3) that a metal-rich composition is needed to explain the wavelength dependence in the polarisation spectra of SN 2015bn.

Ejecta from a PISN explosion have a metal rich inner composition that might account for the strong line opacities suggested by our model. However, it is hard for such massive explosions to break the original spherical symmetry as shown by several multidimensional simulations (Fryer et al. 2001; Joggerst & Whalen 2011; Baranov et al. 2013; Chen et al. 2014a). A multidimensional simulation including rotation was actually able to produce an axisymmetric inner ejecta for a highly rotating CO core

(Chatzopoulos et al. 2013), but this was at the cost of lower luminosity and redder spectra than those of non-rotating PISNe.

The last scenario to consider is that of the CSM interaction. As mentioned in Section 6.1, the most promising mechanism to explain the high luminosity in the framework of interaction is that of a P-PISN. As shown by Chen et al. (2014b), mixing and fluid instabilities are produced by the interaction between the ejecta and the shell(s) expelled before explosion. Although these can break the symmetry on small scales, however, they are not able to alter the overall spherical symmetry of the shells. It is therefore hard to reconcile the strong axial symmetry observed in the spectropolarimetric data of SN 2015bn with the P-PISN model.

6.5 Summary and conclusions

In this chapter, we have presented the first spectropolarimetric data for a SLSN, SN 2015bn. Two epochs were gathered by C. Inserra, one pre-peak at -23.7 d and the second $+27.5$ d relative to maximum light. My first contribution to this work was to help in reducing and analysing the data. Our analysis indicates:

1. the presence of a dominant axis and no physical departure from it;
2. a strong wavelength dependence of the polarisation spectra; and
3. an increase in the mean degree of polarisation from the first to the second epoch of observations.

My second contribution was to interpret the polarisation signatures observed in SN 2015bn. Specifically, I used our Monte Carlo test code (Section 3.5) to interpret the wavelength dependence and the time evolution observed in the polarisation spectra. We calculated polarisation spectra for prolate ellipsoidal geometries accounting for electron scattering and resonant line scattering. We were able to reproduce the wavelength dependence of the polarisation by adopting a line opacity distribution for the inner ejecta that is rich in IGEs. This poses some challenges as the high line opacities required might lead to a line blanketing in the flux spectra that is too strong compared to what we see in SN 2015bn. This, however, will need to be tested with full radiative transfer calculations. We have also show that the evolution of the overall line-continuum level can be replicated via two-zone aspherical ejecta models with an outer zone having $A_{\text{out}} = 0.88$ at both epochs and an inner zone showing an increase in the asymmetry from the first ($A_{\text{in}} = 0.88$) to the second ($A_{\text{in}} = 0.60$) epoch. These values are calculated for an equatorial viewing angle and thus should be considered as lower

limits on the asphericities of the ejecta. Orientations away from the equatorial plane would lead to lower polarisation signals and would then require smaller axis ratio values. In addition, we caution that the specific values derived here ($A_{\text{in}} = 0.88 - 0.60$ and $A_{\text{out}} = 0.88$) are model dependent. However, our findings qualitatively demonstrate that the SN 2015bn spectropolarimetry can be reproduced by an ellipsoidal geometry – or alternatively a bipolar geometry – with an inner region that increases its asymmetry as time passes.

Among all the suggested scenarios for SLSNe I, these new data tend to favour a core-collapse explosion and a central inner engine as explanation for the inferred axisymmetric geometry, as well as the increase of the inner asymmetry. Currently, this scenario does not comfortably reproduce the wavelength dependence we observe, since it seems challenging to obtain enough line opacity. On the other hand, we did not explore other opacity options than a simple iron core and hence a more complete modelling is needed (including self-consistent predictions of flux and polarisation spectra).

With this work, we have demonstrated that detecting polarisation signatures for nearby ($z < 0.2$) SLSNe is possible with the instrumentation currently mounted at ESO VLT. Following this study, the next step will be to increase our sample and to collect further observations of the future nearby SLSNe at least at two epochs, ideally one before and one post maximum light. This will be important to investigate whether other SLSNe I and SLSNe II show similar properties to those seen in SN 2015bn. Despite the uncertainties that still exist with our relatively simple modelling approach, the data presented here should also drive new initiatives in how to model these explosions. Of the three main explosion scenarios proposed to explain SLSNe, the magnetar model is the most promising to explain the axial symmetry observed in SN 2015bn. Predicting observables, and especially polarisation signatures, for multi-dimensional hydrodynamic explosion models of magnetar-powered SNe (e.g. Chen et al. 2016) will be crucial to test whether this scenario can account for the properties observed in SLSNe. As demonstrated in the earlier work in this thesis on SNe Ia, we are now in a good position to perform this type of calculations.

Chapter 7

Conclusions

“The important thing is not to stop questioning. Curiosity has its own reason for existing. One cannot help but be in awe when he contemplates the mysteries of eternity, of life, of the marvellous structure of reality. It is enough if one tries merely to comprehend a little of this mystery each day.”

– Albert Einstein

7.1 Summary

The goal of this work has been to develop and apply a Monte Carlo radiative transfer scheme to calculate synthetic spectropolarimetry for contemporary SN Ia explosion models. We have demonstrated that the validity of modern multi-dimensional models can be assessed by studying their asymmetric ejecta geometries and testing whether the predicted polarisation signals can account for the small levels ($\lesssim 1$ per cent) typically observed in SNe Ia. Using an idealised test code, we have also demonstrated the applicability of our Monte Carlo polarisation scheme to other classes of SNe (e.g. superluminous SNe).

At the time this work was initiated, polarisation predictions for a hydrodynamic explosion model had been performed by only one study (Kasen & Plewa 2007). This was in part because extracting polarisation levels of the order of a few tenth of a per cent – as those detected in SNe Ia – is computationally prohibitive. In Monte Carlo calculations, noise levels in the extracted observables are expected to decrease with the square root of the number of packets. To achieve the same signal-to-noise as in the flux spectra, extracting polarisation levels smaller than 1 per cent thus requires a factor of about 10^4 more packets. Clearly, this is computationally very expensive. As a first step, in this work we have therefore investigated different Monte Carlo noise reduction techniques to make our goal computationally feasible. Inspired by previous suggestions (e.g. Yusef-Zadeh et al. 1984; Knigge et al. 1995; Lucy 2005), we have investigated a technique in which viewing-angle observables are calculated by summing contributions from virtual packets (v -packets) created at each Monte Carlo quanta interaction point and forced to escape to a selected observer orientation.

The v -packet approach was validated via application of an idealised test code to simple geometries. Observables extracted with the v -packet technique agree well with those predicted with the usual angular binning approach but, compared to the latter, they are much less affected by Monte Carlo noise levels. This indicates that the v -packet approach is much more suitable to reproduce very weak polarisation signals. However, the need of creating and handling v -packets introduces a computational overhead and therefore limits the number of orientations for which polarisation spectra can be extracted with high signal-to-noise ratio. Specifically, only a handful of viewing angles were investigated with good statistics for each model presented in this thesis. This is an important limitation since, before carrying out any simulation, it requires us to closely analyse the ejecta geometries of each model under investigation and make an *a-priori* selection of interesting orientations. In addition, the need to restrict to a small number of orientations makes a full mapping of the polarisation signatures from a given model difficult to achieve.

Nevertheless, we have implemented the ν -packet scheme in our multi-dimensional radiative transfer code `ARTIS` (Sim 2007; Kromer & Sim 2009) and tested its accuracy in calculating intensity and polarisation spectra for simple models with SN Ia compositions and opacities. First, we carried out calculations for the parametrised one-dimensional W7 model (Nomoto et al. 1984; Iwamoto et al. 1999), known to provide a good agreement with SN Ia light curves and spectra. We have verified that the ν -packet approach (i) is able to predict polarisation levels consistent with zero for spherically symmetric models and (ii) that, despite the computational overhead introduced by the creation and handling of the ν -packets, the gain in terms of computational time is a factor of about 200 with respect to the usual angular binning approach. Secondly, we investigated two-dimensional ellipsoidal models and explored how asymmetries in the density and element distributions can be effectively studied by inspecting polarisation levels in the continuum and across individual spectral features.

Motivated by the success of these exploratory studies, we then started our long-term project to predict polarisation signatures for contemporary multi-dimensional explosion models of SNe Ia. In this work, we have focused our attention on three explosion scenarios that have been proposed as viable channels to explain normal SNe Ia: the M_{ch} “delayed-detonation”, the sub- M_{ch} “double-detonation” and the sub- M_{ch} “violent merger” scenarios. Ideally, one would like to choose the best explosion model among different incarnations of each scenario. In practice, however, multi-dimensionality is a relatively recent development in modelling SN explosions and the number of two-dimensional and three-dimensional SN Ia models is currently rather small. Admittedly, this poses a limitation to our study. Nevertheless, here we have selected three available explosion models that we consider among the current best examples of the explosion scenarios they represent: one double-detonation model from Fink et al. (2010, here referred to as D-DET), one delayed-detonation model from Seitenzahl et al. (2013, N100-DDT) and one violent merger model from Pakmor et al. (2012, VM-11-09). For each explosion models, we extracted polarisation spectra around maximum light for multiple observer orientations.

These polarisation calculations have highlighted the power of spectropolarimetry to test the validity of different explosion models. As already found by previous studies (e.g. Röpke et al. 2012), the D-DET, N100-DDT and VM-11-09 models reproduce light curves and flux spectra of normal SNe Ia comparably well and are thus very hard to differentiate. Spectropolarimetry provides instead a clear distinction as it can probe the rather different ejecta morphologies of these three explosion models. Specifically, our study indicates that the D-DET and N100-DDT models provide a better agreement with data compared to the VM-11-09 model. For the first two models, polarisation extracted in the continuum decrease from ~ 0.1 – 0.3 per cent around maximum light to

lower values thereafter, in excellent agreement with spectropolarimetric data of normal SNe Ia. Higher degrees of polarisation are found across individual spectral lines. In particular, the synthetic Si II $\lambda 6355$ profiles are polarised at levels that match remarkably well those observed in normal SNe Ia, while the low degrees of polarisation predicted across the O I $\lambda 7774$ region are consistent with the non-detection of this feature in current data. In contrast, our study suggests that the VM-11-09 model studied here is not a good model to explain normal SNe Ia. Specifically, this model is too strongly polarised to account for the low polarisation signals observed for the bulk of normal SNe Ia.

Although our study shows that the VM-11-09 model can be rejected as a good model for SNe Ia, placing a strong preference for either the D-DET or the N100-DDT model appears challenging. In both models, electron scattering contributions originate from relatively spherical regions of the ejecta and thus lead to polarisation levels that are typically small and difficult to distinguish. This indicates that, while some models may be excluded and distinguished easily from each others, others might be more difficult to discriminate based on their polarisation signatures only. In the future, it will be crucial to check whether the combination of spectroscopic and polarimetric properties and/or the detailed investigation of individual spectral features might offer additional constraints for models (see Section 7.2).

7.2 Outlook

Although the main focus of this work has been on predicting polarisation signatures, in the future we will carry out a more systematic study of the D-DET, N100-DDT and VM-11-09 models including both spectroscopic and polarimetric analysis. As a by-product of the substantial reduction in Monte Carlo noise levels achieved in this study, very high signal-to-noise flux spectra can now be extracted from our simulations. Thanks to this improvement, we will be able to characterise velocities of individual spectral features with high accuracy and search for possible correlations between spectroscopic and polarimetric properties. Combining flux and polarisation spectral properties might offer additional constraints on the three explosion models and facilitate their comparisons with data. In addition, this work might highlight different behaviours between models that can be tested by future spectroscopic and polarimetric observations, thus stimulating observers to collect new data and increase the currently limited sample of spectropolarimetric data of SNe Ia.

Combining flux and polarisation predictions will also be crucial to test if studying individual spectral features can help us discriminate between different models. For instance, we will address the question of whether any of our models can account for

the high-velocity ($\sim 15\,000\text{--}20\,000\text{ km s}^{-1}$) components of the Ca II IR triplet. These features are frequently observed in both intensity and polarisation spectra of SNe Ia, but their origin is still debated. Preliminary indications from the work of this thesis suggest that the D-DET scenario is more promising in reproducing these high-velocity components as the calcium in the outer shell of this model leads to velocities in the right range for some orientations. However, at least for the three orientations for which we have predicted high signal-to-noise flux and polarisation spectra, the D-DET model is not able to simultaneously reproduce the spectroscopic and polarimetric signatures characteristic of this high-velocity material. In the future we will investigate this model further and predict flux and polarisation levels across the Ca II IR triplet for a larger number of orientations. By studying how velocities and polarisation signatures change for different orientations, we will answer the question of whether the D-DET model can account for the Ca II IR triplet high-velocity features.

Another interesting feature that deserves more attention in the future is the O I $\lambda 7774$ line. Polarisation signals across this feature have never been detected, and upper limits of about 0.3 per cent have been placed for strongly polarised objects. In contrast, our models indicate that modest (0.3–0.5 per cent) polarisation signatures should be detectable in this spectral range. In particular, for the three orientations investigated in this thesis, the D-DET model is characterised by a distinctive 90° rotation of O I compared to other Si II and Ca II lines, behaviour that is not observed in the N100-DDT and VM-11-09 models. In the future, we will investigate the D-DET model in a more systematic way and predict polarisation levels across this feature for more orientations. This will tell us whether the 90° rotation of the O I compared to the other lines is a characteristic feature of the D-DET model that can be used to distinguish it from other explosion models.

Regarding the study of new explosion models, we will pursue two different lines of investigation. On the one hand, we will map out the parameter space of the three scenarios investigated in this thesis and perform polarisation calculations for different realisations of each class of models. This is crucial because it will allow us to understand whether entire classes of models can be distinguished – or even ruled out – by their spectroscopic and polarimetric predictions. On the other hand, we will investigate alternative scenarios for both normal and peculiar SNe Ia. Special attention will be given to the pure deflagration models of Kromer et al. (2013, 2015), for which light curves and spectra have been found to match those observed in peculiar “O2cx-like” objects remarkably well.

In this thesis we have demonstrated how spectropolarimetry can be used to effectively distinguish between different SN Ia explosion scenarios. Specifically, the analysis

of the VM-11-09 model showed that some models might be excluded as good candidates for SNe Ia based on their polarisation predictions only. In contrast, as highlighted by the comparison between the D-DET and the N100-DDT model, other explosion models might reproduce spectropolarimetric data of SNe Ia comparably well and would therefore require additional information to be told apart. In particular, when ambiguities remain, our study suggests that looking at individual spectral features and combining polarimetric and spectroscopic properties can help discriminating between different models. In the effort of understanding SN Ia explosions from a synthesis of theory and observations, this work is an important step forward as it provides a powerful way to connect predictions of hydrodynamic explosion models to observational data. With the rapidly increasing number of SNe Ia discovered, this approach will help us identifying the most promising explosion scenarios for SNe Ia and thus solving the long-standing enigma surrounding these extraordinary explosions.

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